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DOCTORAL THESIS

Redox processes in energy-related technologies – use
of mixed ionic-electronic conductors for oxygen
production

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Abstract

This dissertation is focused on the hexagonal rare-earth manganites, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ (R – smaller rare earth elements), a group of mixed ionic-electronic conductors (MIEC), and their potential application in energy-related technologies. Thanks to the Mn-related redox process occurring in $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ accompanied by the large changes in oxygen nonstoichiometry δ , these manganites can be considered so-called oxygen storage materials (OSM) and have multiple possible applications. One such application is O_2 production via air separation in the process of temperature swing absorption (TSA). The unique feature of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ is the temperature, where redox reactions take place – in the range of 200-300 °C, exceptionally low, compared to other OSM groups. This work aims to address the following issues:

- To develop an $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ able to work in air atmosphere in the TSA process.
- Find possible correlations between chemical composition and operating parameters of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ to allow designing materials adjusted to a desired working environment.
- Asses the competitiveness of TSA with conventional O_2 production methods.

The dissertation contains ten chapters divided into three main sections: *Introduction* (chapters 1-3), *Experimental methods* (chapters 4-5), and *Results and discussion* (chapters 6-10), followed by *Summary and conclusions*, and two appendices (Appendix A and B).

Chapter 1. entitled *Oxygen production and applications* provides a broad review of current conventional and alternative methods of O_2 production, including cryogenic distillation of air, pressure swing adsorption, oxygen separation membranes, electrolysis of water, and more. Classification of O_2 production methods is proposed by the author and definitions of the main parameters characterizing oxygen production methods are introduced. In the end, all the discussed technologies are compared according to their production capacity, specific power consumption, purity of generated O_2 , etc. Applications of industrially produced O_2 are also introduced briefly, and the classification of those is proposed by the author.

Chapter 2. entitled *Oxygen storage materials* contains a general introduction to mixed ionic-electronic conductors and describes oxygen storage materials as a specific group of MIECs. A brief review of the current and potential applications of OSMs is provided. Finally, the most important OSM groups are extensively described, with emphasis on their characteristic operating parameters, like oxygen storage capacity (OSC), temperatures of redox processes, cost material, or working atmospheres.

Chapter 3. entitled *Hexagonal rare-earth manganites, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$* is dedicated to providing a comprehensive review of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSMs. Possible crystal structures adopted by $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ are discussed, depending on the ionic radius of R and the magnitude of oxygen nonstoichiometry δ . Examples of parameters reported in the literature are given, including OSC and operating temperatures. Literature data are discussed in terms of the possible influence of chemical composition and preparation route on the oxygen storage behavior of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$.

Chapter 4. entitled *Preparation of materials* describes how the chemical compositions of studied materials were selected. The series of R -substituted $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials was designed – R : Pr, Gd or Yb, and $x = 0, 0.05, 0.075, \text{ or } 0.1$. In the following part of this chapter,

the preparation of materials is described in detail – autocombustion sol-gel synthesis followed by high-temperature annealing in an Ar atmosphere was employed.

Chapter 5. entitled *Characterization of materials* contains a detailed description of experimental procedures employed for the characterization of physicochemical properties of studied materials: crystal structure and phase composition after synthesis and after oxidation, oxygen storage behavior, microstructure, and charge transport properties. Utilized techniques include ambient and non-ambient X-ray diffractometry, thermogravimetry, electron microscopy, direct current electrical conductivity, thermoelectric power measurements, and X-ray absorption spectroscopy.

Chapter 6. is entitled *Influence of the mean ionic radius of $Y_{1-x}R_x$ on $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ properties ($R = Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Yb$)*. Research presented in this chapter is focused on determining the influence of the ionic radius of $Y_{1-x}R_x$ on the most important parameters of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$, i.e. oxygen storage capacity and reduction and oxidation temperatures. It is shown that proper manipulation of chemical composition allows for a great improvement of the material's OSC, enables efficient operation in air atmosphere, and gives the possibility of adjustment of working temperatures.

Chapter 7. entitled *Extended studies on $Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$* aims to provide an in-depth insight into the redox processes occurring in $Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$ – the best-working material among the all reported in the previous chapter. Structural evolution and phase transformations during oxidation are studied, a rate-limiting factor of the oxidation reaction is determined, and the performance in the air-operating TSA process is evaluated.

Chapter 8. is entitled *Combined chemical and microstructural improvement: $Y_{0.95}Nd_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$* . In this chapter, a chemical refinement of the oxygen storage performance of Nd005 (reached by $x = 0.05$ substitution with Nd in $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$) is further combined with microstructural modification to evaluate the possibility of additional improvement. Nine differently prepared samples of $Y_{0.95}Nd_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$ are examined in terms of their phase composition oxygen absorption characteristics.

Chapter 9. entitled *Oxygen transport properties* is focused on exploring the charge transport properties of selected hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials. Total electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power measurements are conducted in three different atmospheres (Ar, air, and O_2) to determine the influence of chemical composition and oxygen partial pressure on charge transport.

Chapter 10. is entitled *HEX-based TSA: Assessment of applicability for O_2 separation from air* and provides a general description of the designed prototype of an air separation unit, dedicated to operating in TSA mode and utilizing hexagonal OSMs developed in this work. Moreover, the possible specific power consumption of O_2 production via the TSA process utilizing $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSMs is estimated and compared to the conventional methods of oxygen production.

In the *Summary and conclusions* section, the main achievements and drawn conclusions are summarized. Also, the possible impact of this work on the research field and industry is briefly discussed.

Appendix A entitled *Measurement errors calculations* contains information on how the error values were determined in particular measurements.

Appendix B entitled *Pr005 as a SOFC electrode material* contains the results and discussion of preliminary research performed to assess the applicability of hexagonal rare-earth manganites, $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$, as an air electrode in solid oxide fuel cells. For these experiments, $Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$ (Pr005) composition is chosen, as it exhibits improved conductivity in air atmosphere, compared to parent $YMnO_{3+\delta}$, and the fastest oxygen exchange characteristics among all materials studied in this work.

Streszczenie

Tytuł pracy: **Procesy redoks w technologiach energetycznych – wykorzystanie materiałów o mieszanym przewodnictwie jonowo-elektronowym do produkcji tlenu**

Niniejsza rozprawa skupia się na heksagonalnych manganianach ziem rzadkich $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ (R – mniejsze pierwiastki ziem rzadkich), grupie mieszanych przewodników jonowo-elektronowych (MIEC) oraz ich potencjalnym zastosowaniu w technologiach związanych z energetyką. Dzięki procesom redoks zachodzącym w $RMnO_{3+\delta}$, którym towarzyszą duże zmiany niestechiometrii tlenowej δ , manganiany te można uznać za tzw. materiały do magazynowania tlenu (OSM), mające wiele potencjalnych zastosowań. Jednym z takich zastosowań jest produkcja O_2 poprzez separację powietrza w procesie absorpcji zmiennotemperaturowej (TSA). Unikalną cechą $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ jest temperatura, w której zachodzą reakcje redoks – w zakresie temperatur 200-300 °C, wyjątkowo niskich w porównaniu z innymi grupami OSMów. Celem tej pracy jest rozwiązanie następujących problemów:

- Opracowanie $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ zdolnego do pracy w atmosferze powietrza w procesie TSA.
- Znalezienie możliwych korelacji między składem chemicznym a parametrami pracy $RMnO_{3+\delta}$, aby umożliwić projektowanie materiałów dostosowanych do pracy w żądanych warunkach.
- Ocena konkurencyjności TSA wobec konwencjonalnych metod produkcji O_2 .

Rozprawa zawiera dziesięć rozdziałów podzielonych na trzy główne części: *Wprowadzenie (Introduction, rozdziały 1-3)*, *Metody eksperymentalne (Experimental methods, rozdziały 4-5)* oraz *Wyniki i dyskusja (Results and discussion, rozdziały 6-10)*, następnie *Podsumowanie i wnioski (Summary and conclusions)* oraz dwa załączniki (Appendix A i B).

Rozdział 1. zatytułowany *Produkcja i zastosowania tlenu* zawiera szeroki przegląd obecnych konwencjonalnych i alternatywnych metod produkcji O_2 , w tym kriogenicznej destylacji powietrza, adsorpcji zmiennociśnieniowej, membran do separacji tlenu, elektrolizy wody i innych. Przedstawiona jest klasyfikacja metod produkcji O_2 zaproponowana przez autora, oraz definicje głównych parametrów charakteryzujących metody produkcji tlenu. Na koniec porównano wszystkie omówione technologie pod kątem ich wydajności produkcyjnej, jednostkowego zużycia energii, czystości wytwarzanego O_2 itp. Pokróćce przedstawiono również zastosowania produkowanego przemysłowo tlenu, a autor zaproponował sposób ich klasyfikacji.

Rozdział 2. zatytułowany *Materiały magazynujące tlen* zawiera ogólne wprowadzenie do mieszanych przewodników jonowo-elektronowych i opisuje materiały magazynujące tlen jako specyficzną grupę MIEC. Przedstawiono krótki przegląd obecnych i potencjalnych zastosowań OSMów. Na koniec obszernie opisano najważniejsze grupy OSM, z naciskiem na charakterystyczne dla nich parametry pracy, takie jak pojemność magazynowania tlenu (OSC), temperatury procesów redoks, koszty materiałowe czy atmosfera pracy.

Rozdział 3. zatytułowany *Heksagonalne manganiany ziem rzadkich, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$* jest poświęcony kompleksowemu przeglądowi OSMów $RMnO_{3+\delta}$. Omówiono możliwe struktury krystaliczne przyjmowane przez $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ w zależności od promienia jonowego R i wielkości

niestechiometrii tlenowej δ . Przytoczono przykładowe parametry na podstawie literatury, w tym OSC i temperatury pracy. Dane literaturowe omówiono pod kątem możliwego wpływu składu chemicznego i preparatyki materiałów na proces magazynowania tlenu przez $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$.

W rozdziale 4. zatytułowanym *Przygotowanie materiałów* opisano sposób doboru składu chemicznego badanych związków. Zaprojektowano serię materiałów podstawionych różnymi R , $\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ – R : Pr, Gd lub Yb, oraz $x = 0, 0,05, 0,075$ lub $0,1$. W dalszej części rozdziału szczegółowo opisano sposób przygotowania materiałów – wykorzystano syntezę zol-żel z samozapłonem połączoną z wysokotemperaturowym wygrzewaniem w atmosferze Ar.

Rozdział 5. zatytułowany *Charakterystyka materiałów* zawiera szczegółowy opis procedur eksperymentalnych wykorzystanych do scharakteryzowania właściwości fizykochemicznych badanych materiałów: struktury krystalicznej i składu fazowego po syntezie i po utlenieniu, właściwości magazynowania tlenu, mikrostruktury i transportu ładunku. Stosowane techniki obejmują dyfraktometrię rentgenowską w warunkach normalnych i w wysokiej temperaturze, termogravimetrię, mikroskopię elektronową, stałoprądowe pomiary przewodnictwa elektrycznego i siły termoelektrycznej oraz absorpcyjną spektroskopię rentgenowską.

Rozdział 6. zatytułowany jest *Wpływ średniego promienia jonowego Y_{1-x}R_x na właściwości $\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ ($R = \text{Pr}, \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}, \text{Gd}, \text{Yb}$)*. Badania przedstawione w tym rozdziale koncentrują się na określeniu wpływu promienia jonowego Y_{1-x}R_x na najważniejsze parametry $\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$, tj. pojemność magazynowania tlenu oraz temperatury redukcji i utleniania. Wykazano, że odpowiednia manipulacja składem chemicznym pozwala na znaczną poprawę OSC materiału, umożliwia wydajną pracę w atmosferze powietrza oraz daje możliwość dostosowania temperatur pracy.

Rozdział 7. zatytułowany *Rozszerzone badania nad $\text{Y}_{0,95}\text{Pr}_{0,05}\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$* ma na celu pogłębienie wiedzy na temat procesów redoks zachodzących w $\text{Y}_{0,95}\text{Pr}_{0,05}\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ – materiale działającym najlepiej spośród wszystkich opisanych w poprzednim rozdziale. Badane są zmiany strukturalne i przemiany fazowe zachodzące podczas utleniania, określony jest czynnik limitujący szybkość reakcji utleniania oraz oceniona jest wydajność w procesie TSA realizowanym w powietrzu.

Rozdział 8. zatytułowany jest *Połączone ulepszanie chemiczne i mikrostrukturalne: $\text{Y}_{0,95}\text{Nd}_{0,05}\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$* . W tym rozdziale chemiczna poprawa wydajności magazynowania tlenu przez Nd005 (osiągnięta przez podstawienie $x = 0,05$ Nd w $\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$) jest dodatkowo połączona z modyfikacją mikrostrukturalną w celu oceny możliwości dodatkowej poprawy. Dziewięć różnie przygotowanych próbek $\text{Y}_{0,95}\text{Nd}_{0,05}\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ zbadano pod kątem charakterystyki absorpcji tlenu ich składu fazowego.

Rozdział 9. zatytułowany *Właściwości transportu tlenu* koncentruje się na badaniu właściwości transportu ładunku w wybranych heksagonalnych materiałach $\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$. Pomiary całkowitego przewodnictwa elektrycznego i siły termoelektrycznej przeprowadzono w trzech różnych atmosferach (Ar, powietrze i O_2) w celu określenia wpływu składu chemicznego i ciśnienia parcjalnego tlenu na transport ładunku.

Rozdział 10. zatytułowany jest *TSA oparte na HEX: Ocena stosowalności do separacji O_2 z powietrza* i zawiera ogólny opis zaprojektowanego prototypu urządzenia do separacji powietrza, dedykowanego do pracy w trybie TSA i wykorzystującego heksagonalne OSMY opracowane w tej pracy. Ponadto oszacowano możliwe jednostkowe zużycie energii produkcji

O₂ w procesie TSA z wykorzystaniem OSMów $RMnO_{3+\delta}$, i porównano je z konwencjonalnymi metodami produkcji tlenu.

W części *Podsumowanie i wnioski* podsumowano główne osiągnięcia i wyciągnięte wnioski. Pokróctce omówiono również możliwy wpływ tej pracy na dziedzinę nauki i przemysł.

Załącznik A pt. *Obliczenia błędów pomiarowych* zawiera informacje o sposobie wyznaczenia wartości błędów w poszczególnych pomiarach.

Załącznik B zatytułowany *Pr005 jako materiał elektrodowy SOFC* zawiera wyniki i omówienie wstępnych badań przeprowadzonych w celu oceny przydatności heksagonalnych manganianów ziem rzadkich, $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$, jako elektrody powietrznej w stałotlenkowych ogniwach paliwowych. Do tych eksperymentów wybrano skład $Y_{0,95}Pr_{0,05}MnO_{3+\delta}$ (Pr005), który wykazuje lepsze przewodnictwo w atmosferze powietrza w porównaniu z macierzystym $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ oraz najszybszą charakterystykę wymiany tlenu spośród wszystkich materiałów badanych w tej pracy.

List of abbreviations

4DC	4 -probe(also: 4-point) D irect C urrent method
ASP	<i>Air Separation Plant</i>
ASR	<i>Area-Specific Resistance</i>
ASU	<i>Air Separation Unit</i>
BET	<i>Brunauer-Emmet-Teller</i>
BOS	<i>Basic Oxygen Steelmaking</i>
CA	<i>Citric Acid</i>
CAR	<i>Ceramic Autothermal Recovery</i>
ChEC	<i>Chemical Expansion Coefficient</i>
CLAS	<i>Chemical Looping Air Separation</i>
CLC	<i>Chemical Looping Combustion</i>
COG	<i>Chemical Oxygen Generator</i>
CPE	<i>Constant Phase Element</i>
CSZ	<i>Ceria-Stabilized Zirconia</i>
COVID-19	<i>Coronavirus Disease 2019</i>
DSC	<i>Differential Scanning Calorimetry</i>
EDX, EDS	<i>Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy</i>
EG	<i>Ethylene Glycol</i>
EIS	<i>Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy</i>
EVA	<i>Extravehicular Activity</i>
FCC	<i>Fluid Catalytic Cracking</i>
GAN	<i>Gaseous Nitrogen</i>
GOX	<i>Gaseous Oxygen</i>
H-L	<i>Hampson-Linde (cycle)</i>
H-MIEC	<i>Heterogeneous Mixed Ionic-Electronic Conductor (i.e. multi-phase MIEC)</i>
HEX	<i>Hexagonal Rare-Earth Manganites, RMnO_{3+δ}</i>
HT	<i>High-Temperature</i>
IGCC	<i>Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle</i>
ITM	<i>Ionic Transport Membrane</i>
J-T	<i>Joule-Thomson (effect)</i>
LAR	<i>Liquid Argon</i>

LIN	<i>Liquid Nitrogen</i>
LOX	<i>Liquid Oxygen</i>
MIEC	<i>Mixed Ionic-Electronic Conduct-or/-ivity</i>
MI	<i>Metal Ions</i>
NO _x	<i>Nitrogen Oxide(s)</i>
OFC	<i>Oxy-Fuel Combustion</i>
OPM	<i>Oxygen Permeable Membrane</i>
OSC	<i>Oxygen Storage Capacity</i>
OSM	<i>Oxygen Storage Material</i>
PGAN	<i>Pressurized Gaseous Nitrogen</i>
PGOX	<i>Pressurized Gaseous Oxygen</i>
POM	<i>Partial Oxidation of Methane</i>
PSA	<i>Pressure Swing Ab- / Adsorption</i>
R&D	<i>Research and Development</i>
RT	<i>Room Temperature</i>
SAR	<i>Sulfuric Acid Regeneration</i>
SEM	<i>Scanning Electron Microscopy</i>
SEOS TM	<i>Solid Electrolyte Oxygen Separator</i>
SG	<i>Sol-Gel</i>
SOFC	<i>Solid Oxide Fuel Cell</i>
SOEC	<i>Solid Oxide Electrolyzer Cell</i>
SPC	<i>Specific Power Consumption</i>
SRU	<i>Sulfur Recovery Unit</i>
SSA	<i>Specific Surface Area</i>
SSR	<i>Solid-State Reaction</i>
TEC	<i>Thermal Expansion Coefficient</i>
TEM	<i>Transmission Electron Microscopy</i>
TEY	<i>Total Electron Yield</i>
TG, TGA	<i>Thermogravimetry, Thermogravimetric Analysis</i>
TRL	<i>Technology Readiness Level</i>
TPSA	<i>Temperature-Pressure Swing Ab- / Adsorption</i>
TSA	<i>Temperature Swing Ab- / Adsorption</i>
TWC	<i>Three-Way Catalyst</i>
VPSA	<i>Vacuum-Pressure Swing Ab- / Adsorption</i>

VSA	<i>Vacuum Swing Ab- / Adsorption</i>
XAS	<i>X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy</i>
XPS	<i>X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy</i>
XRD	<i>X-ray Diffractometry</i>

List of author's publications

Part of the results discussed in this dissertation has been already published by the author in the following articles:

- *Towards efficient oxygen separation from air: Influence of the mean rare-earth radius on thermodynamics and kinetics of reactivity with oxygen in hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$*
Kacper Cichy, Konrad Świerczek, Katarzyna Jarosz, Alicja Klimkowicz, Mateusz Marzec, Marta Gajewska, Bogdan Dabrowski
Acta Materialia 205 (2021) 116544 [1]
- *Influence of doping on the transport properties of $Y_{1-x}Ln_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ (Ln: Pr, Nd)*
Kacper Cichy, Konrad Świerczek
Crystals 11 (2021) 510 [2]
- *Evaluation of applicability of Nd- and Sm-substituted $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ in temperature swing absorption for energy-related technologies*
Kacper Cichy, Marcin Zając, Konrad Świerczek
Energy 239 (2022) 122429 [3]

The author has also participated in the following works, which are not part of the current dissertation but are focused on the same research field:

- *Reversible oxygen intercalation in hexagonal $Y_{0.7}Tb_{0.3}MnO_{3+\delta}$: toward oxygen production by temperature-swing absorption in air*
Alicja Klimkowicz, Kacper Cichy, Omar Chmeissem, Bogdan Dabrowski, Bisham Poudel, Konrad Świerczek, Keith M. Taddei, Akito Takasaki
Journal of Materials Chemistry A 7 (2019) 2608-2618 [4]
- *Oxygen separation from air by the combined temperature swing and pressure swing processes using oxygen storage materials $Y_{1-x}(Tb/Ce)_xMnO_{3+\delta}$*
Alicja Klimkowicz, Takao Hashizume, Kacper Cichy, Sayaka Tamura, Konrad Świerczek, Akito Takasaki, Teruki Motohashi, Bogdan Dabrowski
Journal of Materials Science 55 (2020) 15653-15666 [5]

Aim of the work

The ever-growing global development of many industries using technical gases entails constant challenges. Among these gases, oxygen plays an important role, the use of which is necessary for the production of steel and non-ferrous metals, petrochemicals, glass, and ceramics, as well as in medicine or power generation technologies. The oxygen demand for medical and industrial needs grows by 3.6% annually since 2015, and it is estimated that the oxygen market will grow even faster between 2020 and 2025 – from \$26.2 to \$37.3 billion, giving an annual growth rate of 7.4%. According to The Business Research Company, this growth will be also driven by the COVID-19 pandemic and the medical needs it imposes [6].

Currently, most of the oxygen gas for industrial uses is produced by cryogenic distillation of air. Despite this process being well-known and at the top technology readiness level (TRL) of 9, it is still an expensive method, due to the associated high energy consumption needed to liquify air by cooling it to cryogenic temperatures. Other, less-mature, production methods include pressure and vacuum-pressure swing adsorption (PSA, VPSA) or the use of polymeric gas separation membranes. Nonetheless, the intensifying restrictions and regulations related to environmental protection and energy efficiency create the need of developing new, low-cost, and efficient technologies for oxygen production. One of the alternatives, currently in the research and development (R&D) stage, is temperature swing absorption (TSA).

The concept of TSA is relatively new – no air separation unit operating in this mode has been reported – neither well-developed commercial equipment nor prototypes. The only research reports concern materials that could work in this process, and what is more, the topic emerged just in the last two or three decades.

A specific group of mixed ionic-electronic conductors, so-called oxygen storage materials (OSM) are the crucial component of the TSA technology. OSMs are the type of chemical compounds that are able to reversibly capture and release oxygen between their structure and the surrounding atmosphere. This process is driven by the change of external conditions – temperature swing, in the case of TSA. Absorption and desorption of oxygen by the OSM are accompanied by corresponding redox reactions occurring in the material – at least one of the elements in the chemical formula of OSM is being oxidized or reduced to balance the charge introduced or removed with oxygen. Among numerous groups of OSMs, one particularly stands out – hexagonally structured rare-earth manganites, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$, also abbreviated as HEX. The unique feature of these OSMs is their low operating temperature – HEX can work in TSA mode even in the 200-300 °C range instead of e.g. 500-700 °C.

However, despite their attractive operating temperatures and good oxygen storage capacity (on the order of ~2-3 wt.%), HEX OSMs exhibit one significant drawback. Up to the day the here-reported research started, there was no HEX capable to work in air atmosphere. All the published data reported effective oxygen absorption only in pure O_2 , which eliminates the practical application of HEX materials in O_2 separation from air. The previous research in the field of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ showed that the oxygen storage behavior of these OSMs depends on the elements present in the rare earth sublattice, but no trends have been found and described. What is more, the morphology of HEX has been shown to influence the material's oxygen storage performance as well.

Consequently, this work is aimed to answer the following questions:

- Is it possible to develop an $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSM which would be able to efficiently operate in an air atmosphere in a low-temperature TSA process?
- Are there any correlations between chemical composition (i.e. cations present on R site) and the elementary operating parameters of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ (temperatures of oxygen absorption and release, oxygen storage capacity, etc.), so some general guidelines could be provided on how to design an $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSMs dedicated to working in a given environment?
- Can the TSA (utilizing hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$) be an O_2 production method competitive to the conventional ones?

The remaining aims of this work can be stated as follows:

- The physicochemical properties of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials will be comprehensively characterized with a particular focus on their oxygen storage-related features and how they are influenced by their chemical composition and morphology.
- Trials will be undertaken to design and build the first prototype TSA air separation unit, utilizing hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSMs.
- The foundations for further development of HEX-based TSA technology will be established.

According to the established aim of this work, the following objectives can be formulated:

1. Synthesis of the series of materials from the group of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ (R : Yb, Gd, Sm, Nd, Pr; $x \leq 0.1$) by sol-gel autocombustion method followed by high-temperature annealing in Ar. The respective compositions have been properly chosen to have different sizes of mean ionic radius of $Y_{1-x}R_x$ cations. Detailed justification of how the compositions were selected is provided in chapter 4.
2. Structural analysis and phase composition determination of as-synthesized materials by X-ray diffractometry, and examination of their morphology with scanning electron microscopy.
3. Characterization of oxygen storage behavior of prepared samples in pure O_2 and air using thermogravimetry. Determination of oxygen storage capacity and temperatures of oxidation and reduction. Structural analysis of materials oxidized in thermogravimetric experiments.
4. Establishment of the possible correlations between the mean ionic radius of $Y_{1-x}R_x$ and properties of the HEX material: the ones directly related to the oxygen storage process (temperatures of oxidation and reduction, oxygen storage capacity), and not directly related, including structural parameters, phase composition, and morphology.
5. Extended studies on the selected, best-working material, to provide a deeper insight into the processes ongoing in HEX materials upon oxygen absorption and release. These include the following experiments: high-temperature structural analysis, verification of oxidation states of elements in the selected

- compound, determination of near-equilibrium oxygen content as a function of temperature and O₂ partial pressure, search for the rate-limiting phenomenon of oxidation reaction, optimization of reduction and oxidation temperatures, assessment of activation energy of oxygen absorption and desorption, etc.
6. Application of the best-working HEX in a thermogravimetric experiment simulating the separation of air via the TSA method and estimation of the possible productivity of this process.
 7. Modification of preparation route (temperature and time of the final annealing step during synthesis) to alter the morphology of selected HEX OSM, and to find its possible influence on oxygen storage performance. Characterization of crystal structure, phase composition, and microstructure of the as-synthesized materials prepared with different annealing conditions.
 8. Measurements of transport properties (conductivity, thermoelectric power) and how are they influenced by the chemical composition of HEX and O₂ content in the atmosphere.
 9. Design and construction of the small-scale TSA air separation unit prototype.
 10. Estimation of the possible specific power consumption of O₂ generation with HEX-based TSA and comparison to the conventional O₂ production methods.

Introduction

1. Oxygen production and applications

This chapter aims to introduce the reader into the topic of oxygen production – a summary of the most important facts regarding conventional and alternative methods of O₂ generation is given. An extensive comparison of operational parameters in different technologies is provided. Moreover, selected applications of oxygen in various sectors are briefly summarized.

1.1. Classification of oxygen production methods

The principle of operation of most techniques for oxygen production is to grab O₂ from air and transfer it to some clean/empty volume, relatively free of particles other than O₂; alternatively, to grab every particle other than O₂, and let only the O₂ pass to target space. This “grabbing” or “catching” is implemented using condensation and evaporation, weak bonding to the surface of certain materials (adsorption), incorporation into the crystal structure of other compounds (absorption) or physically blocking larger particles from passing through the membrane – generally speaking, using any physicochemical phenomena, where air constituents vary with their behavior (i.e. O₂ liquefies at a different temperature than N₂, O₂ adsorbs weaker on the surface of some adsorbents than N₂, etc.). Methods that break chemically bonded oxygen out of the compounds naturally occurring on Earth are in a minority among all the O₂ generation methods described in this work (and in general as well).

O₂ production methods which are described in the following chapters are divided into two groups: *conventional* and *alternative* methods, respectively. The first group includes two main, commercially used technologies: cryogenic distillation of air and pressure swing adsorption (PSA), and its variations: vacuum- (VSA) and vacuum-pressure swing adsorption (VPSA). The second group includes oxygen permeable membranes (OPM, both polymeric and ceramic), electrolysis of water, chemical oxygen generators, and temperature swing ad-/absorption (TSA).

However, after a thorough literature study, the author of this work decided that it is worth introducing an additional classification, a description of which is given from here to the end of subchapter 1.1. The proposed classification takes into account two factors: 1) the source of oxygen and 2) the principle of operation (**Figure 1.1**). By the O₂ source, it is meant from where the oxygen is extracted: from a mixture of gases (e.g. air), or from chemical compounds containing oxygen (e.g. water, sodium chlorate). The principle of operation means that the process makes use of either physical (e.g. adsorption, distillation), or chemical phenomena (e.g. absorption, chemical reaction, electrolysis).

Methods utilizing air as an oxygen source are collectively called *air separation methods*. In special technological applications, O₂ can be also separated from other O₂-containing gas mixtures, but for the purpose of O₂ production, air is used as the O₂ source. From air (and other gas mixtures), O₂ can be separated physically or chemically. The first group of methods includes cryogenic distillation, polymeric membranes, and adsorptive swing methods. The latter includes ionic transport membranes (ITM) and absorptive swing methods.

In the case of methods that use chemical compounds as an oxygen source, this oxygen can be extracted only in a chemical process. The process can be a chemical reaction between two or more substances (e.g. thermally activated to react and release oxygen) or an

electrochemical reaction (using the electrical potential difference to decompose O₂-containing substance and release oxygen, e.g. electrolysis of water).

Taking a closer look at **Figure 1.1**, it can be seen that a group of swing-type air separation methods was distinguished. Among these, the following divisions can be made:

- regarding swing-controlling parameter: pressure- and temperature-driven swing (or mixed temperature-pressure swing),
- regarding separation mechanism: adsorption and absorption methods.

Taking these two above factors, multiple variations of swing-type air separation methods can be named:

- Surface-working (i.e. adsorption methods):
 - pressure swing (PSAd, VSAd, VPSAd),
 - temperature swing (TSAd),
 - temperature-pressure swing (TPSAd).
- Bulk-working (i.e. absorption methods):
 - pressure swing (PSAb, VSAb, VPSAb),
 - temperature swing (TSAb),
 - temperature-pressure swing (TPSAb).

For the purpose of this classification, suffixes “d” and “b” were added to distinguish swing methods, regarding their working mechanism, between adsorptive and absorptive, respectively. This distinction into “d” and “b” methods is quite vital, in the author’s opinion, as the difference in the separation mechanism itself (i.e. the way how and which air constituents are being captured) is elementary and it significantly affects the properties and applicability of a certain swing method.

In many research papers and other works, PSA (or TSA, VSA, etc.) is used interchangeably – once in relation to aD sorption, and another time to aB sorption process [7–14]. Also, the term *chemical looping air separation* (CLAS) was used concerning pressure-driven swing absorption [15]. This term is accurate to be used as a general name for all the abovementioned absorptive methods: PSAb/VSAb/VPSAb, TSAb, and TPSAb, as in all of these, O₂ is *separated* from *air* by *chemically* reacting with sorbent material and a process proceeds in a *loop*. The CLAS name is also included in **Figure 1.1**. In the following chapters, “d” and “b” suffixes will be omitted, and the absorptive or adsorptive nature of a given swing method will be clearly stated in the text, where crucial.

Figure 1.1 Classification of O₂ production methods, proposed by the author of this work, considering the source of O₂ and the principle of operation. Suffixes “-Ad” and “-Ab” stand for adsorption and absorption, respectively.

1.2. Parameters characterizing oxygen production methods

A place where oxygen is produced on an industrial scale is called an *air separation plant* (ASP). A specific installation or device which purpose is to generate oxygen (either in ASP or as a separate appliance) is called an *air separation unit* (ASU; sometimes ASU and ASP are used interchangeably). Air separation technologies implemented in ASPs/ASUs differ from each other in terms of the operating conditions, thermodynamic parameters of the process, energetic efficiency, and therefore, economic viability. Some of these factors might decide whether a specific technology is applicable in a given case. A literature review allowed the author of this work to gather the following parameters [16–19]:

- *Minimum and maximum temperatures and pressures during the process* – these extremal conditions, which are dictated by the nature of a given separation technology, induce some application-related consequences, like the type of materials that can be used for the construction of ASU, the form of the final product (liquid, gas, compressed gas or other), the need of additional heating/cooling or compression/decompression of the product, or magnitude of power consumption and energy efficiency of a separation process. Altogether those details translate to the total cost of O₂ generation.
- *Specific power consumption (SPC)* – also called air separation work, is expressed by the energy required to separate one ton [kWh t⁻¹] or one normal cubic meter [kWh Nm⁻³] of

oxygen. Simply, it means how expensive is it to generate O₂ using a given separation technology.

- *Oxygen production/separation capacity* – this parameter says how fast the O₂ can be generated using a given separation process. It is expressed in tons of separated oxygen per day [tpd] or normal cubic meters per day [Nm³pd]. This quantity is often also given in normal cubic meters per hour [Nm³h⁻¹].
- *Purity of separated gases* – in reality, it is practically impossible to obtain 100% pure substances. Even for the purest O₂, there are present some impurities measured e.g. in ppb (parts per billion), which come for instance from the starting mixture, like air, so those can be traces of N₂, Ar, CO₂, etc. The purity of gases is most often given in %, while the information about impurities and their maximum concentration is also usually provided (e.g. in ppb or ppm, parts per million). The purity of highly pure gases is also often expressed as the degree of purity – it says how many times a digit “9” occurs in a given purity (e.g. gas with 99.99% purity has a 4.0 degree of purity and the rest, 100 ppm, are impurities). Some separation technologies can typically provide up to 95% pure O₂, while for others even 99.99999% (7.0N) is achievable.
- *Component yield* – the ratio of the mass flow of the component (O₂ in this case) in the product (output of a separation system) to the mass flow of this component in the feed air (input of a separation system), expressed in %.
- *Startup time* – it says how long it takes from a “push of a START button” to a moment when the ASU is ready to deliver O₂ at a declared rate (separation capacity) and purity. For commonly and currently used technologies, this time varies from several minutes to hours.
- *Investment costs* – it says how much it costs to build ASU/ASP from scratch to when it is ready to start the operation. Together with the abovementioned *specific power consumption* of O₂ generation, it can determine if the use of a certain separation technology is economically justified in a given case.
- *Size of ASU/ASP* – this regards the space occupied by the plant. It determines if a specific separation technology is suitable to be used in a particular place (e.g. as an oxygen supply for a hospital or to be integrated with an oxy-combustion power plant, could it be even used as a personal/portable oxygen concentrator in a home health care, or is it rather more adequate to use for large scale production as a separate facility). Sometimes the size of ASU is given in terms of its footprint – the area of the land that ASU occupies.
- *Scalability* – it says if a certain separation technology can be adjusted to multiple application fields varying with the level of O₂ demand. This parameter is related to the above, i.e. dimensions of ASU.
- *Ease of integration with other processes* – this one is a wider issue, connected with all of the above parameters. It takes into consideration the specificity of the technology that ASU is to be integrated with (i.e. its thermodynamic conditions, O₂ demand, etc.) and ASU parameters (like the size, scalability, process parameters (temperature, pressure) of the ASU or purity of generated O₂), and determines if the one or both technologies could be tweaked

so they operated as a single setup (and how complex would it be). Examples of the processes that ASU could be integrated with, are oxy-fuel combustion, coal gasification, or the production of chemicals.

In terms of specific power consumption, O₂ production technologies can be compared not only between each other but also, which is no less important, to the theoretical minimum air separation work. Fortunately, thermodynamics provides the tools to calculate such value [20]. To completely separate the mixture of n components (like air), which mole fractions are y_i , into pure components at temperature T , the minimum required work can be calculated as:

$$w_{min,mixture} = -RT \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \ln y_i \quad (\text{Equation 1.1})$$

expressed in joules per mole of the mixture, [J mol⁻¹], where R is the universal gas constant.

Therefore, the minimum work needed to separate only one component (like O₂) from the mixture, w_{min} , is:

$$w_{min} = -RTy \ln y \quad (\text{Equation 1.2})$$

and is expressed in joules per mole of separated component, [J mol⁻¹].

In the case of air, O₂, N₂, and Ar can be taken for the calculation of $w_{min,mixture}$, as the mole fractions of other components (like CO₂, Xe, Ne, He, etc.) are negligible (**Table 1.1**). The value of such calculated minimum work is accurate enough for herein performed comparisons (because *SPC* in real ASUs is multiple times higher than theoretical separation work, as can be seen in the next subchapters) and is also commonly used in the literature [14,16,18,21,22]. Minimum separation work is typically given for standard conditions, i.e. 0 °C (273.15 K) and 1 bar (10⁵ Pa) [23]. **Table 1.1** gives the averaged volume concentration of dry atmospheric air constituents at standard temperature and pressure (STP). Approximating air as an ideal gas, mole fractions in Equation 1.3 and Equation 1.2 are equal to the volume concentrations given in **Table 1.1** [24]. Thus, using Equation 1.3, minimum air separation work can be calculated:

$$w_{min,air} = -RT(y_{O_2} \ln y_{O_2} + y_{N_2} \ln y_{N_2} + y_{Ar} \ln y_{Ar}) = 1281.5 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$$

The minimum work of 1281.5 J per mole (of separated air) corresponds to 191.2 MJ or 53.1 kWh per one ton of separated air (kWh t⁻¹).

Table 1.1 Average composition of dry air at standard temperature and pressure at sea level [25,26].

Component	Concentration [vol.%]	Component	Concentration [vol.%]
Nitrogen, N ₂	78.08	Methane, CH ₄	2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴
Oxygen, O ₂	20.95	Krypton, Kr	1.1 × 10 ⁻⁴
Argon, Ar	0.934	Hydrogen, H ₂	5.0 × 10 ⁻⁵
Carbon dioxide, CO ₂	0.034	Nitrous oxide, N ₂ O	3.1 × 10 ⁻⁵
Neon, Ne	1.8 × 10 ⁻³	Carbon monoxide, CO	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁵
Helium, He	5.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	Xenon, Xe	8.7 × 10 ⁻⁶
		Others: SO ₂ , O ₃ , NO ₂ , NO, etc.	ca. 1.5 × 10 ⁻⁵

Despite that in the literature the *SPC* is compared to the minimum separation work of whole air, it would be maybe more adequate (or at least interesting) to compare it also to the minimum separation work of a single component, i.e. O₂, as in this the method of O₂ production

are discussed in this work. Thus, according to Equation 1.2, the minimum separation work of O₂ from air, w_{min,O_2} , at standard conditions is:

$$w_{min,O_2} = -RT y_{O_2} \ln y_{O_2} = 743.6 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$$

which corresponds to 111.0 MJ or 30.8 kWh per one ton of separated oxygen.

1.3. Conventional methods of oxygen production

1.3.1. Cryogenic distillation of air

Cryogenic distillation of air is the most widely used method for the production of oxygen – it covers over 90% of the O₂ demand [16]. Generally, in this method air is cooled down to the temperatures where the individual air constituents liquefy and can be separated from the mixture. O₂ purities above 99% are easily achievable in this process, however, proper tweaking allows to obtain the O₂ gas of high purity – even up to 99.99999% (7.0N), with N₂ and Ar impurities being below 0.1 and 10 ppb, respectively [16,18,27,28]. Besides high purity, another benefit of cryogenic distillation is the availability of byproducts: mainly N₂, but also Ar and other noble gases.

However, the temperature below which the oxygen liquefies is drastically low – this makes the distillation of air a highly energy-consuming process. For pure nitrogen, oxygen, and argon (i.e. main air constituents), boiling points (in other words, condensation temperatures) under ambient pressure are $-195.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (77.4 K), $-183.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (90.2 K), and $-185.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (87.3 K), respectively [16,17]. It needs to be mentioned that for a mixture of gases, which air is, the respective condensation temperatures slightly differ from the boiling points [29], and, vary with pressure. For example, under approx. 6.2 bar, those temperatures are still in the cryogenic regime ($-174.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $-158.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and $-161.7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for nitrogen, oxygen, and argon, respectively [30]), as the temperature of the critical point of air is $-140.7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (i.e. the air cannot be liquefied above that temperature, regardless of pressure) [17,31,32].

It is hard to name one person who deserves fame for the first liquefaction of oxygen, as in the late 19th century, there were several prominent scientists, each of whom contributed to this achievement. The very first man to liquefy oxygen, however utilizing enormously high pressure, was Raoul Pictet, a Swiss physicist. On December 22, 1877, he announced that he succeeded to do it under the pressure of 320 atm and at the temperature of $-140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [33]. He employed the evaporation heat of compressed sulfur dioxide and carbon dioxide to achieve the temperature. Next people whose works largely influenced the world of cryogenic research were Polish scientists, Zygmunt Wróblewski and Karol Olszewski, who liquefied the oxygen in 1883 [34–36]. They achieved the liquid state of oxygen by cooling the gas down to $-130 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ but while keeping it under the pressure of about 20 atm [36]. Contrary to Pictet’s method, the cooling down below the condensation temperature was achieved not by using very high pressure, but by applying the Joule-Thomson (J-T) effect. Briefly speaking, the J-T effect is the phenomenon of temperature decrease (or increase in specific cases) of the fluid, when this fluid passes through an orifice, throttling valve, porous plug, or so on. Upon this flow, the pressure of the fluid decreases and this throttling occurs with approximately no enthalpy change (isenthalpic process) [37].

Also, Wróblewski suggested that the future of the liquefaction of oxygen on a large scale is to develop Pictet's method and apply the cascade of evaporation of several liquified gases to reach the condensation temperature of O_2 . A few years later James Dewar developed his apparatus, based on Pictet's process. Dewar's equipment produced the liquid O_2 in quantities allowing him to pour oxygen from vessel to vessel like water, which brought fame to the Royal Institution of England and himself.

However, not so long after, in 1895/1896, Carl von Linde turned again toward the J-T effect, not the cascade of evaporations, as a source of cold. He developed the process allowing to deliver the liquid oxygen under atmospheric pressure and in the early years of the 20th century, the first separation plants using von Linde's technology started to appear [17,38,39]. Independently of von Linde, William Hampson designed the apparatus operating in a similar manner and patented it only two weeks before von Linde patented his solution [40]. Thus today, this process is known as the Hampson-Linde (H-L) cycle. A basic schematic of the H-L cycle and its thermodynamic representation in temperature-entropy (T-S) coordinates is shown in **Figure 1.2**. The cycle consists of the following steps [41]:

1. $1 \rightarrow 2$ The feed gas (air) under atmospheric pressure is compressed (in the ideal case, this process occurs isothermally).
2. $2 \rightarrow 3$ Air compressed to high pressure is cooled isobarically in the counter-current heat exchanger (transferring own heat to the gas finishing the previous cycle).
3. $3 \rightarrow 4$ Air is being isenthalpically expanded in the throttling valve. The temperature of air drops below the condensation point due to the Joule-Thompson effect. In point 4, liquid (4'') and gas (4') are in thermodynamic equilibrium, i.e. some part of the gas is liquified and the rest remains gaseous. The whole mixture remains at condensation temperature. Part of the gas that had been liquified, can be withdrawn in point 4'' or can be evaporated.
4. $4 \rightarrow 4'$ Evaporation of liquid leads to an increase in entropy. This phase transformation takes place under constant pressure and at a constant temperature.
5. $4' \rightarrow 1$ Gas is again heated in the counter-current heat exchanger, simultaneously cooling another portion of gas in the $2 \rightarrow 3$ part of the next cycle. This process is isobaric. If the part of air has been withdrawn in 4'', this decrease is refilled in point 1 prior to the next cycle.

Figure 1.2 Diagram of the Hampson-Linde cycle (a) and its thermodynamic representation in T-S coordinates (b). Based on [41–43].

The following decades led to the further development of the technology by von Linde (e.g. improvement of a heat exchanger, increasing air compression), resulting in the shortening of liquefaction time to even below 1 hour from initial 3 days [39]. One important drawback in the early development stage of original von Linde's process was that it was not selective enough – the liquified mixture contained ca. 50/50 oxygen and nitrogen. The problem was caused by the boiling points of gases being relatively close to each other. However, this was solved by introducing the rectification system. Today's typical cryogenic air separation plants employ the discussed H-L cycle. Despite the main operating principle remaining the same, now the whole process is more sophisticated and complex due to decades of refining every single part of the plant and implementing auxiliary subsystems. **Figure 1.3** shows an example of a typical cryogenic ASP: schematic (a) and existing plant (b). Based on [16,17], the following main steps in a modern cryogenic air separation plant can be listed (numbering of plant's element as in **Figure 1.3a**):

1. Air is sucked from the atmosphere and compressed (3) to about 6 bars. Air is filtered out of dust and pollen before entering the compressor (2). During this compression, air heats up to ca. 100 °C, so it is water-cooled back to ambient temperature (4, 5).
2. The next step is the purification of feed air. Air is purified of H₂O, CO₂, hydrocarbons, and other gaseous and water-soluble contamination, using molecular sieves (6, 6'). The purpose of this purification process is not only to reduce impurities in the final product, but also to prevent damaging the liquefaction system (for instance, H₂O or CO₂ ice might clog the heat exchanger, or hydrocarbons could accumulate in the liquid O₂ in the distillation column and lead to explosion).
3. In the counter-current heat exchanger (10), compressed air is cooled nearly down to the condensation point, using cryogenic liquid or gaseous products from the previous cycle. Some part of air is additionally compressed (8, 9) to pressure higher than 6 bar (e.g. 31 bar) before entering the heat exchanger, therefore it liquefies even before the throttle valve. The condensation heat released in this process is used to evaporate liquid oxygen produced in the previous cycle (see step 6.), transforming it into compressed gaseous oxygen (so-called internal compression of oxygen).
4. This high-pressure-liquefied air flows into the rectification column through a throttling valve (22) and turbine (11). The pressure drops again to ca. 6 bar and the temperature falls (J-T cooling effect), which results in the flow of a two-phase mixture of liquid and gas. This takes place in the pressure column (12) of the two-column rectification system (setup invented by Carl von Linde and still in use). The liquid mixture of oxygen and nitrogen that is formed in the sump of this pressure column is oxygen-enriched, having an O₂ concentration typically in the 35 – 40% range.
5. Gas is further subjected to a rectification process in the pressure, and next in the low-pressure column (14). On its way between pressure and low-pressure columns, gas is also expanded through throttling valves. Liquid oxygen is formed at the bottom (13), and liquid high-purity gaseous nitrogen (GAN) at the top of the low-pressure column – the pressure in this column is near ambient. Liquid N₂ (LIN) and O₂ (LOX) can be withdrawn directly from this column if needed.

6. Gaseous N_2 and liquid O_2 are then passed through the counter-current heat exchanger (10, mentioned earlier in step 3) to recover cold. N_2 and O_2 heat up and thus compress (or evaporate and compress) which delivers the final product of pressurized gaseous N_2 (PGAN) and O_2 (PGOX).
7. Optionally, some part of Ar-enriched gas can be passed from the intermediate region of the low-pressure column to another column system (15-19) dedicated to producing liquid argon (LAR).

The interested reader is referred to chapter 2 of *Industrial Gases Processing* [16] and Linde Engineering brochures [17,29], which together are comprehensive literature positions regarding cryogenic air separation.

Figure 1.3 (a) Schematic of modern cryogenic air separation plant – dashed line indicates a coldbox – part of plant operating at cryogenic temperatures. A detailed description of the schematic can be found in the reference [16], where the figure is cited from. (b) Cryogenic air separation plant built by Linde Group company [44].

Thanks to over a hundred years of development, the cryogenic distillation of air is a mature and well-known technology. In *Industrial Gases Processing*, it stays: “Cryogenic separation requires the smallest work (...)” (compared to other separation methods: PSA and membranes) [16] and another work claims that “Cryogenic installations also allow to get the highest possible efficiencies of gas separation” [18]. Due to the cryogenic temperatures needed

to liquefy oxygen, it might sound surprising, that cryogenic distillation is the most economically/energetically favorable method of oxygen production. However, it is true for applications, where high purity (over 95%) or large production capacity (over 200-300 tpd) of O₂ is required [14,22,45,46]. For smaller purities or demands, other separation technologies might be the method of choice [19,45,46].

In cryogenic ASPs, the vast majority of power is consumed by compressors. Today's typical commercial separation plants' *SPC* achieves down to 400-600 kWh per ton of separated oxygen [14,16,18,19,21,22,28,47]. It was estimated that in an optimized plant and for high oxygen production capacities (exceeding 3500 tpd), *SPC* could decrease to 200 kWh t⁻¹ [22,48]. However, this is still 4 times the theoretical minimum air separation work, as calculated before in chapter 1 and reported in the literature [18,28]. 280 kWh t⁻¹ is declared by Air Liquide in their ASU called SIGMA, but with the decrease of O₂ purity down to 96% [19]. Also 245 kWh t⁻¹ is declared to be possible with 99.5% purity and 175 kWh t⁻¹ with 95% purity in advanced alternative system designs, as reported by Beysel (Linde Group), which seems to be a state-of-the-art value for cryogenic air separation [49].

Typical cryogenic ASPs are big facilities – the rectification tower, the highest element in **Figure 1.3b**, reaches 40-70 m in height [16,29]. Cryogenic ASPs are dedicated strictly to producing oxygen (and other byproduct gases) on a large scale – production capacities are in the order of hundreds or thousands of tons of O₂ per day. Exemplary oxygen production capacities of existing cryogenic separation units are: 3 600 tpd (started in 2011 by Air Products in Saudi Arabia), 5 250 tpd (started in 2017 by Linde in India, the world's largest ASU), 1 750 tpd (started in 1999 by Air Liquide in Poland) [29,50,51]. Some ASPs consist of several ASUs (e.g. 4 units, 3 000 tpd each, giving a total of 12 000 tpd – China, Air Products, 2016) [50]. Thus, cryogenic separators are not necessarily suitable for small-scale applications [28] (small in terms of both, ASP's physical size and production capacity). Nonetheless, some manufacturers offer small-scale, containerized units to generate liquid O₂ practically on-site [52], but these have some drawbacks, e.g. small production capacity (2.5 tpd), lack of byproducts and higher power consumption and therefore the efficiency of the separation process is significantly reduced.

As the cryogenic process is mainly used for large production capacities and because, by its nature, requires cooling separated air to very low temperatures, it stands out with a relatively long startup time (compared to other separation methods), reaching dozens of minutes or even hours [18].

1.3.2. Pressure swing adsorption

The second most important method of air separation is a pressure swing adsorption (PSA). Despite being younger than a cryogenic distillation, PSA is today also a mature and well-developed technology. The first patents in adsorptive gas separation were granted in the early 30s of the 20th century to Finlayson and Sharp, Dargan and Hasche, and Perley, and the technology was later developed by Skarstrom by 1960 [53–56]. Today it is widely commercially available and pressure swing ASUs are offered by most of the major companies in the gas industry (Linde Group, Air Products, Air Liquide, etc.) – PSA is the most important alternative to cryogenic distillation.

Pressure swing adsorption makes use of the fact, that molecules of one gas bond to a given surface stronger than the other gas. The process of bonding molecules to the surface of materials is called adsorption and the materials on which adsorption takes place are sorbents. Besides this bond strength (adsorption force), the amount of the gas adsorbed on the sorbent is proportional to its partial pressure. Thus, a gas (like O₂) can be separated from the mixture (like air) by alternately changing (swinging) the pressure. This process generally is carried out at constant, near-ambient temperatures.

As the gaseous air constituents are being adsorbed on the sorbent surface to be separated from each other, a large surface area is needed for the sorbent to allow efficient O₂ generation [16]. In PSA dedicated to O₂ generation, nitrogen-selective zeolitic molecular sieves are typically used, having the specific surface area in the range of ~800-1500 m² g⁻¹ [16,57].

Typical two-bed PSA implementation is a relatively simple installation (especially compared to cryogenic separation plants). The system consists of two adsorption beds filled with the sorbent, a compressor, and several valves (Figure 1.4, compressor not included). A single cycle consists of two stages [16,58]:

1. *Adsorption* – air is compressed by the compressor at the inlet of the system. Valves are open to allow the flow of air through the adsorption bed. N₂ is caught by the sorbent and separated O₂ is let out.
2. *Regeneration* – after the sorbent's surface is full of N₂, it cannot separate air anymore, thus it requires regeneration. The flow of pressurized feed air is stopped, the bed is depressurized to the ambient pressure and N₂ is desorbed. Additionally, a portion of the O₂ separated in the other bed is used to purge the regenerated sorbent and prevent contaminating O₂ with N₂ in the next adsorption cycle.

Two beds operate alternately to allow constant O₂ delivery. While the adsorption stage takes place in the BED-1, BED-2 is regenerated in the meantime (left side in **Figure 1.4**). After adsorption finishes in the BED-1 and BED-2 is finally regenerated, valves are switched to allow the flow of feed air through BED-2 (adsorption) and regenerate BED-1 (right side in **Figure 1.4**).

As in the PSA, the pressure change is a driving force of the adsorption process, underpressure is also an option – then, the process is called a vacuum or vacuum-pressure swing adsorption (VSA or VPSA, respectively). In the PSA adsorption step takes place under high pressure (3-4 bar) and the regeneration step under ambient pressure [16]. In the VSA, it is the adsorption step that is carried out close to ambient pressure (1.5 bar), and a vacuum (0.35-0.5 bar) is used to regenerate the bed [16]. Despite it is only a variation of the PSA and the operation principle is theoretically the same, it is classified separately because it brings significant application advantages (e.g. results in the lower *SPC* of such ASU). It is because the sorbent selectivity of N₂ over O₂ drops while increasing pressure, and thus more O₂ is adsorbed with N₂ during the feed step, and then lost in the regeneration step in standard PSA [59]. Also, PSA consumes much more power due to gas compression.

In the case of VPSA, adsorption is performed under high pressure and regeneration is done with a vacuum. Another variation of PSA is temperature-pressure swing adsorption (TPSA), where besides swinging the pressure, bed temperature is increased to weaken gas-sorbent bonds and facilitate the regeneration step [60]. Due to the thermodynamics of

adsorption swing methods, i.e. conditions (like temperature and pressure) occurring during the process, produced O₂ is in gaseous form under ambient pressure (GOX) or compressed (PGOX).

Figure 1.4 Basic schematic of the PSA operation principle.

The purity of oxygen generated by a typical PSA/VPSA process is often limited to about 90-95% [19,45,46,58,61–64]. The ~95% limit is because O₂ and Ar molecules are quite similar in terms of their adsorption behavior – they both tend to not bond with the sorbent bed [16,58]. This approx. 5% amount of impurity comes from the composition of atmospheric air (**Table 1.1**) – the ratio of Ar and O₂ concentrations is 0.934 to 20.95, which gives ~4.5%. Thus, the remaining ballast in the produced gas is mainly Ar and the rest is nitrogen [16,65].

Higher purities can be achieved either by the use of an additional separation step (once separated oxygen, having a purity of 90-95% is subjected to an additional cycle of pressure swing adsorption) [66–69] or by using sorbent materials having better O₂/Ar selectivity [11,70–72]. The highest purity reached in commercially available separation units and reported in the research papers is 99.5% [11,66,72]. However, the *SPC* would be higher because of the additional compressor operation time or investment cost would increase because of more expensive silver-based molecular sieves as sorbents [11,70]. Thus, most adsorptive ASUs offered by major manufacturers deliver a maximum of 95% pure O₂ and the application of the PSA/VPSA O₂ generation method is still limited to the application, where high gas purity is not crucial.

Figure 1.5a shows the schematic of VPSA ASU with auxiliary components needed for real-life implementation. **Figure 1.5b** shows the exemplary vacuum swing adsorption ASU. Adsorptive separation plants are visibly smaller than cryogenic ones, as they do not require a rectification tower, which is the highest (up to 40-70 m) element in the cryogenic plant (**Figure 1.3b**). VSA, PSA, and VPSA separation units do not differ noticeably from each other. The size of the adsorptive plants is much more influenced by the application, and thus by the O₂ generation capacity, as the PSA application ranges from personal oxygen concentrators in health care to large-scale O₂ plants in the glass industry [63,73]. Many manufacturers supply their adsorptive ASUs as plug-and-play solutions, in a containerized form [58,74–76].

Figure 1.5 (a) Schematic of vacuum-pressure swing adsorption air separation unit by Linde Group (based on [58]). (b) Vacuum swing adsorption air separation plant by Air Products (based on [76]).

PSA/VSA is a very flexible technology and the power consumption of this process is not as dependent on production capacity as it is in cryogenic distillation. Thus, manufacturers can offer the customer a wide range of ASUs designed to specific O₂ demand. The highest capacities supplied by a single ASU reach almost 350 tpd, while the smallest units can be used as personal O₂ concentrators in health care, delivering even below 0.01 tpd (ca. 5 liters per minute) [14,19,46,58,61–63,77].

PSA units seem to have higher *SPC* than VSA or VPSA. Moreover, even compared to cryogenic distillation and despite having much lower O₂ purity, power consumption can be larger in PSA (varying from almost 300 to over 800 kWh t⁻¹ in the 93-95% purity range) [14,16,22,64]. VSA/VPSA were reported to consume ca. 265-322 kWh t⁻¹ for 90-93% purity [19,46]. Nonetheless, a vital advantage of adsorptive plants is their short startup time (several minutes) and the flexibility of O₂ generation (it can be quickly decreased or increased without losing much efficiency) [16,76].

Recently, some alternative active oxide materials were reported, that can work by means of absorption, not only adsorption [8,78,79]. At elevated temperatures, oxygen ions in these materials can be reasonably mobile, and by swinging p_{O_2} in the surrounding atmosphere (e.g. swing between ambient air and vacuum), oxygen can be reversibly stored in, and extracted from these sorbents – almost like in standard well known PSA/VSA, but the process is not limited to the surface of the sorbent, but the whole volume (bulk) of the active material can be utilized. An example of such material is a Sr-doped Ca₂AlMnO_{5+δ} that operates isothermally at 550° C in VSA/VPSA mode [8]. The used vacuum was relatively high (absolute pressure of ~0.03 bar) which means that the process might be more energy-consuming compared to “standard” (i.e. adsorptive) VSA/VPSA. In that work, the *SPC* of air separation was estimated to be ca. 109.6 kWh Nm⁻³ (ca. 77 kWh t⁻¹), so the process could be a highly competitive alternative. However, it is only a theoretical estimation that did not include multiple stages where the heat (i.e. power) would be lost. So this value should be rather treated as a minimum limit, which might be achieved ideally. Also, the assumed O₂ purity was only 95.5%.

Another work reported the usage of perovskite-based sorbent operating in PSA mode at 600 °C [15]. Power consumption of 118 kWh t⁻¹ (≥ 95% purity) was achieved with proper optimization of the cycle. It seems that absorptive swing methods can be a promising alternative to a conventional adsorptive PSA. Nonetheless, these are still in the R&D stage. One research paper declared achieving O₂ purities of up to 99.4% when absorptive PSA was combined with oxygen permeable membrane [79]. Absorptive PSA using high-temperature perovskite

absorbers was investigated by Linde Group in terms of generating oxygen to be directly used in the oxy-fuel combustion process [80]. They called this process of O₂ separation in yet another way – Ceramic Autothermal Recovery (CAR). In their report, they declared that using CAR can reduce the *SPC* down to 40% of what is achieved by the present cryogenic ASU.

1.4. Alternative methods of oxygen production

1.4.1. Oxygen separation membranes

Another important alternative to cryogenic distillation, are air separation membranes. Typically, membranes used in air separation technology are organic polymer membranes, but the purity of generated O₂ is strongly limited (< 50%) and this product should be rather called O₂-enriched air. Indeed, it is typically treated as a byproduct (or even as a waste gas) in N₂-generating membrane systems [18,27,81–86]. This technology is utilized where only slightly O₂-enriched air is required and for relatively low O₂ demand (10-25 tpd) [18,82,87,88]. No data could be found regarding the *SPC* of O₂ generation with membrane ASU. Nonetheless, polymeric membrane technology is still being developed and research on new materials are conducted [89–91].

A promising alternative to organic materials are ceramic ionic transport membranes (ITM). Although this technology is still at a relatively early stage of development, it has one major advantage, which makes the research worthwhile to be performed, namely, the theoretical limit of obtained oxygen purity is 100%. It is because (contrary to polymeric membranes) ITMs have ideal O₂ selectivity – it means, that only oxygen can permeate through such a dense ceramic membrane.

Oxygen can be forced to permeate through ITM by applying an electrical potential gradient (in case of purely O²⁻-conducting materials, **Figure 1.6a**) or chemical potential gradient (in case of materials having mixed ionic-electronic conductivity, MIEC) across the membrane [16,92–95]. ITMs using a chemical potential (approximated by p_{O_2}) gradient as a driving force of O₂ flow, may be either single- or multi-phase systems, and ceramics used can exhibit mixed ionic-electronic or purely ionic conductivity (**Figure 1.6b** and **c**, respectively). In the case of utilizing MIEC material as a membrane for the oxygen separation process, there is no need of applying an additional metallic phase (**Figure 1.6b**), which in the other case is a pathway for electrons (**Figure 1.6c**). To ensure a gradient of the chemical potential of the oxygen, higher total pressure (p''_{O_2}) is used, and in such case, the oxygen from the pressurized air side can enrich air flowing under lower pressure (p'_{O_2}) on the other side of the membrane.

Figure 1.6 (a) Purely O²⁻-conducting membrane driven by the electrical potential gradient. (b) Single- and (c) multi-phase mixed ionic-electronic membranes. Based on [96] and [92].

The most important OPM parameter, the oxygen flux, j_{O_2} , is dependent not only on thermodynamic conditions like temperature or pressure gradient but also on the properties of the utilized material. The relationship between O_2 flux in the bulk of the membrane and the transport properties of the membrane material, its thickness, operation temperature, and partial pressures of oxygen applied on the feed and permeate sides of the membrane, can be described with the Nernst-Einstein formula [97]:

$$j_{O_2} = \frac{\sigma_i RT}{4L(z_0 F)^2} \ln \left(\frac{p'_{O_2}}{p''_{O_2}} \right) \quad (\text{Equation 1.3})$$

where z_0 is the charge of the mobile species (2 for oxygen ion, O^{2-}), F – Faraday constant, σ_i – ionic conductivity of the membrane material, R – universal gas constant, T – absolute temperature, L – membrane thickness, p'_{O_2} and p''_{O_2} – O_2 partial pressure on the feed and permeate side of the membrane, respectively. Using basic SI units for calculations, the unit of j_{O_2} is $\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, which expresses how many moles of oxygen diffuse through 1 m^2 of membrane surface per 1 second. Equation 1.3 is valid in the case, where (I) the electronic part of the conductivity is much higher than the ionic one, and (II) surface processes are fast enough, that the bulk diffusion is the limiting step of oxygen permeation [96].

Oxygen ion conductivity in ceramics is significantly hindered at ambient temperature, therefore ITM must operate at high temperatures to increase the mobility of oxygen ions and allow efficient air separation. Typically, operating temperatures of ITM range from 600 to 1000 °C [92–96,98]. Also, in practice, the p_{O_2} gradient can be induced by compressing air on the feed side, while letting the permeate side stay at ambient pressure.

The mechanism according to which oxygen is transported through the single-phase ITM is multistep (**Figure 1.7**), and can be described as follows (based on [96,98]):

1. Oxygen molecule diffusion to the membrane and adsorption on its surface.
2. Adsorbed oxygen molecule dissociation into separate oxygen atoms and incorporation into crystal structure either on vacancy or interstitial position.
3. Oxygen ion and opposite electron diffusion through the membrane.
4. Oxygen ions recombination into the O_2 molecule on the opposite surface of the OPM.
5. Desorption and diffusion away from the membrane surface.

Needs to be mentioned, that each of the above five steps can be a limiting one, especially the surface processes taking place on both sides of the membrane [96].

Figure 1.7 Multi-step oxygen transport mechanism through the oxygen permeable membrane. The top part of the figure shows the approximated distribution of oxygen chemical potential (i.e. O_2 partial pressure) across the membrane. Based on [92] and [98].

As mentioned before, ITM technology is still mainly in the R&D stage and plenty of new MIEC materials are being studied in terms of their oxygen permeation [99–102]. Major interest and progress in the subject happened in the last 2-3 decades. Air Products was a pioneer in this field [94,95,103]. The company, commissioned by the United States Air Force and in cooperation with Ceramatec, designed a system called SEOS™ (solid electrolyte oxygen separator), using O^{2-} -conducting electrolyte as a membrane and applying electrical potential difference as a driving force of air separation, but this technology seems to enjoy less interest today [95]. It was possible to generate O_2 having > 99.9% purity with the SEOS™ system operating at > 600 °C [94,95]. Simultaneously, Air Products in cooperation with the US Department of Energy led a long-term (1998-2015) R&D project regarding the commercialization of ITMs operating under p_{O_2} gradient [103]. An exemplary stack of fully ceramic ITMs and a prototype ITM air separation plant are shown in **Figure 1.8**.

The project started with developing small laboratory-scale ITMs with an O_2 generation capacity of 0.1 tpd and assumed a gradual increase in the following project phases. Finally, according to the technical report from this project, it was possible to develop the ITM ASU, being able to deliver ~2900 tpd with SPC as low as 147 kWh t^{-1} [103]. At best, 99.9% O_2 purities were achieved. This makes membrane technology probably the most competitive option among O_2 production methods: it consumes the least power, high O_2 purity is easily obtained, and the ASU could be flexibly scaled to a wide range of applications, from large-scale industry, down to portable oxygen concentrators.

Figure 1.8 Experimental stack of ceramic ITMs (O_2 production capacity of 0.5 tpd) (a) and prototype commercial-scale ITM air separation plant (footprint of ca. 9×18 m) in Maryland, USA (b). Developed by Air Products in cooperation with the US Department of Energy [103].

1.4.2. Electrolysis of water

Electrolysis of water is the process in which electricity is utilized to force the decomposition of a water molecule into hydrogen and oxygen. This process executes in the electrochemical cell called an electrolyzer – a device consisting of two electrodes (anode and cathode) and an electrolyte (conducting either H^+ or O^{2-} ions). Electrolysis is typically used as one of the hydrogen production methods. Nevertheless, O_2 is also generated in this process, which is usually not utilized. Equations of chemical reactions undergoing during H_2O electrolysis are as follows:

The theoretical minimum work required to separate H_2O using electrolysis equals to the heat of H_2O formation, ΔH [104]:

$$\Delta H = \Delta G + T\Delta S \quad (\text{Equation 1.7})$$

where: ΔH – the heat of formation, ΔG – Gibbs free energy, T – absolute temperature, and ΔS – entropy change. To separate 1 mole of H_2O at 298 K, work of 285.8 kJ/mol is needed [104]. There is 0.5 mole of O_2 formed from each 1 mole of decomposed H_2O (Equation 1.6) and therefore, work of $1/2 \times 285.8 = 571.6$ kJ/mol is needed to create 1 mole of O_2 . This is equivalent to the minimum separation work of ca. 4962 kWh per 1 ton of separated O_2 . The calculated value is 2 orders of magnitude greater than the minimum work required for O_2 separation from air (53.1 kWh t^{-1} , calculated earlier in this chapter), but it should be noted, that the main product of electrolysis is H_2 , not O_2 . This excludes the electrolysis of water from being widely utilized to produce O_2 only, even though today's electrolyzers can reach 80% efficiency

[105,106]. In high-temperature solid oxide electrolyzer cells (SOEC), this minimum work required to decompose H_2O decreases, but still, it is on the order of $10^3 \text{ kWh t}_{\text{O}_2}^{-1}$ [107].

Nonetheless, as electrolytically generated O_2 is an inevitable byproduct of electrolytic production of H_2 , there are some reports analyzing possibilities of its effective utilization (e.g. supplying medical O_2 for hospitals) [106]. Also, electrolysis is used as a source of respiratory oxygen (life support systems) in a very specific environment, where no other method is applicable and the price does not matter (e.g. in submarines or on the International Space Station) [108–112].

The great advantage of electrolysis is that this process could provide extremely pure O_2 with impurities content down to ppm level [113]. What is also important, this method is practically noiseless, which might be a significant factor in some applications (e.g. as personal O_2 concentrators for home health care). As the electrolyzers are typically used for H_2 generation, not O_2 , it is hard to find any data about the O_2 production capacity of electrolytic separation units. However, this data can be found for commercial H_2 -generating electrolyzers, and knowing that for each mole of H_2 , half a mole of O_2 is formed during electrolysis (Equation 1.6), the equivalent O_2 production capacity of such unit can be estimated. Sunfire HYLINK alkaline electrolyzer (**Figure 1.9**) is declared to deliver 2230 Nm^3 of H_2 per hour [114–117]. This gives H_2 production capacity of ca. 4.8 tpd and consequently, 38.4 tpd of O_2 production capacity. Air Liquide hydrogen production facility, equipped with the world's largest electrolyzers (manufactured by Cummins Inc.) can deliver over 3000 tons of H_2 annually, which equals to ca. 65.6 tpd of O_2 [118].

Also, the production capacity of a laboratory scale O_2 generator was reported as 2880 liters per day, which gives approx. 0.004 tpd [113]. Thus, electrolytic production of O_2 could be utilized in extremely small-scale applications as well.

Figure 1.9 HYLINK alkaline electrolyzer (by Sunfire company) [114].

1.4.3. Chemical oxygen generators

Oxygen can be obtained as a gaseous product of some chemical reactions. A device dedicated to producing O_2 this way is called a chemical oxygen generator (COG) or sometimes, an oxygen candle [119–121]. While various chemicals can be applied (usually perchlorates or superoxides), sodium perchlorate is typically used as an oxygen source in COG – it decomposes to sodium chloride (table salt) and releases a significant amount of O_2 , according to Equation 1.8 [120]:

The reaction in Equation 1.8 is initiated by the heat generated in an auxiliary “ignition” reaction (e.g. oxidation of Fe to iron oxide) [119]. The main reaction can be therefore started quickly, and it results in really short (less than a minute) start-up times of chemical oxygen generators [122].

COGs are utilized for small-scale needs, especially for respiratory purposes in special conditions. For instance, small chemical oxygen generators are widely used in aircraft to deliver O₂ to breathing masks for passengers and crew, in case of an emergency, e.g. depressurization of an airplane cabin (**Figure 1.10a**) [121,123]. Also, COGs are used as a backup O₂ source in submarines [122,124]. A volume of 1 Ndm³ is enough to deliver 380 Ndm³ of O₂ – therefore, ca. 1.8 m³-size COG is needed to generate 1 t of O₂ [122]. An exemplary single COG unit (**Figure 1.10b**) can deliver over 3000 Ndm³ of O₂ within 25 min – which gives an average production capacity of approx. 0.25 tpd [122]. As COGs are mostly used for breathing needs, high-purity O₂ is not required. Nonetheless, as the O₂ is the sole gaseous product of the reaction, purities exceeding 98% are easily achievable and are affected only by the non-idealities like dead volumes in the system [122].

Figure 1.10 Oxygen masks used in an airplane are shown in (a) [125] – the black-silver cylinder visible at the top of the picture is a COG unit. Part (b) shows an exemplary commercial chemical oxygen generator by Molecular Products (approx. dimensions in mm: 133 x 133 x 400) [122].

The use of chemical compounds instead of air as an O₂ source is an undeniable advantage if the COG is to be used in closed environments like submarines, airplanes, or spaceships. However, this O₂ generation method has its drawbacks. First, it is one-time use only – once the reaction is started, it proceeds until it runs out of reactants (the reaction is exothermic and after initiation, the heat generated keeps it spontaneous). The next one is the inconvenience of scalability. Chemical oxygen generators are relatively simple equipment and, theoretically, they could be scaled up for large production capacities. Nonetheless, once the reactants are fully reacted, no more O₂ can be generated and the whole input of COG had to be replaced, which seems to be not a convenient operation, especially considering the size of such a hypothetical generator. For instance, it can be estimated (using data from [122]) that to maintain continuous delivery of O₂ at a 100 tpd rate for 1 day, approx. 180 m³ of COG was required – and after 1 day, such a large unit had to be replaced.

1.4.4. Temperature swing adsorption

Another alternative gas separation method is a temperature swing adsorption (TSA), taking at constant pressure (no pressure swing). In this process, materials having a selective ability to adsorb air constituents play an important role. Similar to a well-developed PSA process, TSA typically employs inorganic compounds with a large specific surface area, e.g. synthetic zeolites or activated carbon [126–128].

TSA is generally not used as an industrial air separation method and, in particular, for O₂ production [12]. In his book, *Gas Separation by Adsorption Processes*, Yang mentions that the time needed for sorbent regeneration by heating (and thus, for the whole temperature swing cycle) is relatively long (from several hours to over a day). And therefore, despite the temperature swing being the oldest and (at that time – the 1980s) was the most developed adsorption cycle, the main use of TSA is the purification of gases, in which the concentrations of impurities are low [127,129]. Today, indeed TSA is still used in the removal of impurities from gases, e.g. H₂S and CO₂ from natural gas [126,130,131], or in drying of gases (i.e. H₂O removal) [131,132], but also in the separation process of other gaseous mixtures, e.g. CO₂ removal from flue gases [130,131,133–136].

In 2014, Eriksson and Kiros attempted to employ temperature swing adsorption for the separation of air constituents [12]. At best, they achieved 85.5 % of O₂ purity at 1.1 dm³ h⁻¹ flow rate (i.e. production capacity). For higher flow rates, O₂ concentration significantly decreased – down to 29.2 % at 130 dm³ h⁻¹. Nonetheless, it creates some potential for utilizing adsorptive TSA either in small-scale O₂ concentrators for respiratory purposes or cleaner combustion processes. Ca-substituted X-type (CaX) zeolite was used in this TSA process. Such zeolitic molecular sieves are also widely applied in PSA air separation [137–139]. **Figure 1.11** shows the structure of Faujasite-type (FAU) zeolite (X is a subtype of FAU zeolites and looks virtually the same) and the appearance of a commercially available molecular sieve in a form of spherical beads, ca. 4 mm in diameter.

Figure 1.11 Zeolitic molecular sieve used adsorptive swing air separation methods TSA and PSA: a) structure of a Faujasite-type zeolite and b) its appearance in a commercially available form of spherical beads [140,141].

However, the temperature swing could be performed not only with adsorptive (surface-working) materials but also with the ones in which gas (O₂) is absorbed in the volume of material. Such a process seems to be much more promising and can be called *temperature swing*

absorption (instead of adsorption). This absorptive TSA is discussed in more detail in the following chapter, and in general, this whole work is focused on investigating materials to be applied in TSA_b and on the first implementation of TSA_b for air separation and O₂ production.

1.4.5. Temperature swing absorption

A promising alternative air separation method for O₂ generation is the temperature swing absorption (TSA). The concept is relatively new – no commercial ASU using TSA is available, and not even prototypes have been reported to be created. So far, the only reports regarding TSA concern the research on materials, that particularly gained interest in the last two decades [9,142–152]. In the absorptive temperature swing process, the oxygen storage process takes place in the bulk of the material. So-called oxygen storage materials (OSM) have a unique feature associated with the reversible incorporation/release of oxygen into/from their crystal structure, (see chapter 2).

Although the temperature swing had been reported to be applied in the adsorption process of gas separation and also abbreviated as TSA (temperature swing **ad**sorption) [12,129,130,133,136,153,154], in following chapters of this work, the term TSA refers to temperature swing **ab**sorption (unless indicated otherwise), i.e. process engaging the bulk of sorbent (OSM), not only its surface.

Figure 1.12 shows the operation schematic of the TSA system. As it is not commercially developed and applied, the schematic shows an idea of possible implementation, based on a typical PSA two-bed installation. The system consists of two absorption beds filled with OSM, and several valves (**Figure 1.12**). A single cycle consists of two steps:

1. *Absorption* (or *Oxidation*) – absorption bed is kept at the oxidation temperature (T_{OX}) of OSM. Valves are open to allow the feed air to flow through the absorption bed. O₂ is captured by the OSM (Equation 1.9) and N₂-enriched (or, inner words, O₂-depleted) air flows out of the absorption bed. It is worth noting, that contrary to the adsorptive methods like PSA, it is O₂ that is captured by the sorbent, not N₂ (see chapter 1.3.2).

where M_xO_y is the general unit formula of any metal-oxide OSM, having one or more cations on the M-site, and δ is the oxygen nonstoichiometry (or number of oxygen moles absorbed by one mole of M_xO_y OSM).

2. *Regeneration* (or *Reduction*) – after the OSM reaches the maximum of its capacity, air flow is cut by closing the valves. The temperature of the absorption bed is then changed to the reduction temperature (T_{RED}) of OSM and the release of O₂ starts (Equation 1.10). Desorbed O₂ is withdrawn from the absorption bed by opening another valve.

Two beds operate alternately to allow constant O₂ delivery. While the *absorption* step takes place in the BED-1, BED-2 is *regenerated* in the meantime (left side in Figure 1.12).

After *absorption* finishes in the BED-1 and BED-2 is finally *regenerated*, temperatures of both beds are swung between T_{RED} and T_{OX} , and valves are switched to allow the flow of feed air through BED-2 (*absorption*) and *regenerate* BED-1 (right side in **Figure 1.12**). **Figure 1.13** shows how the exemplary OSM's weight and temperature change upon TSA cycling.

Figure 1.12 Schematic of the TSA system operation principle.

Figure 1.13 Diagram showing how the weight of OSM and temperature change during TSA cycling.

From the application point of view, the requirements for oxygen storage materials in the TSA are primarily the largest possible and the most reversible amount of oxygen storage capacity (OSC), a narrow range of oxidation and reduction temperatures, and moderate values of both temperatures, as well as the ability to operate in conditions close to atmospheric pressure. This process seems to be particularly interesting if the temperature range of the TSA system would correspond to the values for waste heat, which is rarely used effectively (especially in the 200-300 °C range). Materials studied in terms of TSA application are usually operating at 500-700 °C or 200-350 °C [9,142–152]. It was also reported recently that the performance of materials normally operating in TSA mode, can be boosted by adding a pressure swing to facilitate oxygen absorption and desorption [5].

As this separation technology is still in its early stage of the R&D path and no commercial TSA ASU was ever created, no data about power consumption, purity, or

production capacity is available. However, those can be approximately estimated by analyzing the theoretical basis of the TSA method itself, as follows.

O_2 production capacity would depend mostly on the ability of the OSM used in the process to absorb oxygen. If the material stored large oxygen quantities per unit mass and volume, TSA could be probably applicable in a wide range of O_2 demands. If it were too heavy, small-scale portable applications would be limited, while if it were too voluminous, it would restrain large-scale utilization as well. Moreover, the duration of the temperature swing cycle would influence O_2 production capacity – the shorter a single cycle was, the more tons of O_2 per day would be generated.

In TSA, the SPC of O_2 production would be strictly connected to the difference in temperatures, between which the temperature swing takes place, and OSMs heat capacity. The greater the temperature difference and the heat capacity, the more power is required to heat the OSM to desorb oxygen. Also, if the reduction or oxidation reaction were strongly endothermic, it would result in additional power consumption needed to maintain the reaction temperature. In the case of PSA, air has to be compressed to 3–4 bar for the adsorption stage, which generates additional power demand. TSA, similarly to VSA, can operate at close to ambient pressure and use a vacuum to sweep produced O_2 out of the absorption bed.

Similarly to materials used as ITMs, OSMs used in TSA are 100% selective towards O_2 . Thus, theoretically, oxygen generated via TSA could be 100% pure. In a real application, this purity will be slightly decreased by non-idealities of the system (e.g. gaseous contaminations adsorbed on the surface of OSM, pipes, etc.). Nonetheless, it can be expected, that O_2 purities higher than 99.9% will be easily achievable.

1.4.6. Other alternative oxygen production methods of minor industrial significance – a brief overview

It is worth at least mentioning several *even more alternative* approaches to O_2 generation, which however are not yet industrially used, mainly because of technological, economic, or efficiency limitations. Most of these methods use H_2O as a source of oxygen and therefore H_2 is a valuable byproduct. Moreover, most of those employ solar power to perform water splitting, so (excluding investment cost) O_2 generated with these methods is expected to be competitively cheap. Overcoming the abovementioned limitations in the future can bring us a handful of very important, affordable, and environmentally friendly methods of oxygen production. Therefore, despite today these technologies being out of human reach, one day they might become a basis for not only meeting industrial O_2 demand but also a crucial method of CO_2 capture and production of green fuels. Some of these methods are listed below, including references for further reading:

- Photosynthesis and Artificial photosynthesis [155–157];
- Thermochemical water splitting [158–160];
- Photocatalytic water splitting [161,162];
- Photoelectrochemical water splitting [163–165];
- Water hydrolysis using nanogalvanic aluminum alloy powder [166,167].

1.5. Comparison of oxygen production methods

Table 1.2 Summary and comparison of the major conventional and alternative oxygen production technologies.

Separation method	Purity of generated O ₂	Form of product	Typical operating conditions range inside the installation: temperature and pressure	Production capacity (typical) of a single separation unit [tpd]	Specific power consumption, <i>SPC</i> [kWh t ⁻¹]	Level of technology development	Byproducts (& their quality)	Startup time
Cryogenic distillation	99.9% (typical) 7.0N (maximum)	LOX, GOX	-200-100 °C 1 to 100 bar	From 2.5 up to >5000	400-600 (typical) < 200 (minimum)	Mature	LIN, GAN, LAR (Very good)	Hours
PSA/VSA /VPSA	95% (typical) 99.5% (maximum)	GOX	<i>T</i> ~ambient 0.3 to 4 bar	0.01-350	300-800 (PSA) 265-322 (VSA/VPSA)	Mature	GAN (Poor)	Minutes
Membranes (polymeric)	<50 %	O ₂ -enriched air	<i>T</i> ~ambient <i>p</i> ~ambient	10-25	N/D	Mature	GAN (Very good)	Minutes
Membranes (ceramic ITM)	~99.9% (100%, theoretically)	GOX	600-1000 °C <i>p</i> ~ambient	0.1-2900	~150	R&D	N ₂ -enriched air (Poor)	Minutes- hours
Electrolysis	>99.9% practically (100%, theoretically)	GOX	ambient to 1000 °C <i>p</i> ~ambient	0.004-65.6	4962 (theoretical minimum at 25 °C)	Mature	H ₂ (Very good)	Seconds- minutes
Chemical O ₂ generation	>98% (typical) (100%, theoretically)	GOX	<i>T</i> is dependent on used chemicals <i>p</i> ~ambient	0.25	Dependent on used chemicals	Mature	Dependent on used chemicals	Seconds- minutes
TSA	>99.9% expected (100%, theoretically)	GOX	200-700°C <i>p</i> ~ambient	N/D	N/D	R&D	N ₂ -enriched air (Poor)	Minutes- Hours

1.6. Oxygen applications

1.6.1. Classification of oxygen applications

A thorough study of current scientific literature, industrial reports, websites of air-gases suppliers, and other available sources, allowed the author to distinguish several criteria, which could be used to systematize and organize the tremendous field of oxygen applications. Two such classifications were created: the first one, regarding the sector in which O₂ is utilized, and the second, based on the role that O₂ plays in certain uses. Both of these classification systems are introduced in this subsection.

Firstly, applications of oxygen can be classified as follows, regarding the *application sector*, in which O₂ is utilized:

- medicine,
- exploration,
- power generation and environmental protection,
- processing of materials and fuels,
- research and development.

The above system with an indication of major subsectors is presented in Figure 1.14.

Figure 1.14 Classification of O₂ production methods, according to the source of O₂ and the principle of operation – proposed by the author of this work.

And the second, alternative classification system, based on *the role of O₂*, is as follows:

- *Respiratory and medical needs* – where higher O₂ partial pressure is required, or generally O₂ at all, for breathing purposes (e.g. oxygen therapies in health care, breathing oxygen for closed environments like submarines, airplanes, space suits).
- *Oxy-combustion-based applications* – where higher combustion temperatures or efficiencies are required, or unwanted combustion products are to be avoided (e.g. oxy-fuel combustion in power plants, oxy-acetylene cutting, and welding, flame polishing in the glass industry).
- *Oxidizer* in chemical reactions other than combustion – where O₂ is simply required as one of the reactants needed for a certain reaction to proceed (e.g. production of chemicals, cracking of hydrocarbons in petrochemistry, sulfuric acid regeneration, wastewater treatment, smelting of ore in metallurgy).

In chapter 1.6.2, *Selected applications of oxygen* are briefly described. Those applications appear in the text in a way allowing the Reader to notice the first described classification. Nonetheless, benefits coming from replacing air with O₂ are strongly connected to the second classification. For additional reading on the topic, a more detailed description of discussed technologies and other, not mentioned here applications, the Reader is, first of all, referred to the following sources [16,168,169], and the other references cited in chapter 1.6.2, as well.

1.6.2. Selected applications of oxygen

Steel making

The largest industrial consumer of oxygen is steel making [170–172]. In the early 2000s, it was reported to make up 55% of the total demand for commercially produced oxygen [172]. To produce steel, after the iron ore is purified and turned into pig iron in the blast furnace, excess carbon needs to be removed. To do so, pig iron is melted in a so-called basic oxygen furnace (or oxygen converter, **Figure 1.15a**) and blasted with an oxygen jet [173,174]. This makes some required amount of C dissolved in pig iron oxidize to CO₂ and evacuate as a gas. This process is known as *basic oxygen steelmaking* (BOS) and accounts for over 70% of the world's steel production [175]. Due to this high O₂ consumption, still mills usually have their own integrated air separation plants. The advantage of this was taken in India during the COVID-19 pandemic – steel companies could reduce production and redirect some of their O₂ capacity to deliver medical oxygen [176–179]. What is more, O₂ is used for oxy-fuel combustion in steel reheating furnaces and could enhance their thermal efficiency by ~50% (compared to air-fuel combustion), also largely boosting the rate of heat transfer [180].

Glass industry

In the manufacturing of glass, oxygen is applied mainly in two processes: *glass melting furnaces using oxy-fuel combustion*, and *flame polishing*. Implementing *oxy-fuel combustion* in glassworks brings all benefits further described *Power generation* paragraph – lower emissions, higher efficiency, higher temperatures, and lower costs. As reported by Air Liquide, introducing oxy-fuel combustion with Korean and Chinese glass manufacturers allowed to cut NO_x emissions by over 90% and 80%, respectively; 60% energy savings and a 25% increase in

productivity were also achieved [73,181]. This productivity rise is caused by faster glass melting thanks to higher combustion temperatures [16]. Moreover, oxy-fuel combustion extends the lifespan of furnaces used in glass factories [16].

Flame polishing (also known as fire polishing) is the process in which high-temperature oxy-fuel flame is blasted toward the glass to melt a thin surface layer of the glass and any roughness is ideally smoothed (**Figure 1.15b**). This method allows for eliminating the need for acid polishing and etching, which makes the process have a lower environmental impact [16]. Moreover, flame polishing eliminates the need for further mechanical processing and gives machine-made glass a more hand-made-like look [16].

Figure 1.15 (a) Oxygen converter in operation during BOS process – ThyssenKrupp steel mill in Duisburg, Germany (based on [182]). (b) Glass bottles being subjected to flame polishing (based on [183]).

Power generation

In the power generation sector, pure O_2 can be used in the process called *oxy-fuel combustion* (OFC, also called *oxy-combustion*, *oxy-combustion of fuel*, etc.). In this technology, pure O_2 or O_2 -enriched air is supplied to the boiler instead of air, to combust conventional hydrocarbon fuels, like coal [184]. Such an approach brings important benefits, especially from a point of environmental protection view.

Firstly, these benefits come from the elimination of nitrogen from gas entering the furnace. In conventional air-fuel combustion of coal, N_2 from air (~78 vol.%) translates into ~70 vol.% of flue gas, while CO_2 makes up only up to ~15% (the rest mainly consists of H_2O , excessive O_2 , and various pollutants) [185,186]. In OFC, the absence of N_2 in the furnace equals the absence of N_2 in the flue gas. Thus, flue gas contains mainly CO_2 (exceeding 50 vol.%), easy to remove, H_2O , and excessive O_2 – consequently, CO_2 capture and storage is much easier [186]. What is more, this CO_2 can reach purities high enough to be ready for industrial applications. Also, NO_x emissions can be greatly cut or even completely stopped [73,181].

Secondly, much less energy is consumed to heat up the oxidizing medium and pump it through the system, as the N_2 ballast is no longer present – there is over 75 wt.% less gas to be heated and transported. Moreover, the volume of exhaust gases is largely decreased (by the amount of eliminated N_2 but also because gas density is larger), allowing to reduce the cost of the flue gas processing and the size of the purification unit.

Today, in technical practice, the use of 100%-pure O_2 for the combustion of fuels in large-scale power generation is not economically feasible (because of the cost of ASU operation), and air is purified to have 95-99% of O_2 [186,187]. Therefore, the term *oxy-fuel combustion* is usually referred to what is actually *oxygen-enhanced combustion*, and is applied

to any combustion technology that uses oxidizing gas with an O_2 concentration higher than in air, i.e. in the 21-100% range [186]. Real-life implementations of OFC typically utilize either O_2 -enriched air, or a mixture of O_2 with CO_2 . The latter is the case in the process called *flue gas recirculation* (FGR), in which part of CO_2 is fed back from flue gas and used to dilute O_2 (already purified in ASU to said 95-99%) before entering the boiler [187]. FGR allows to additionally decrease a relative content of N_2 and thus, to keep the major benefits of *ideal* (i.e. supplied with pure O_2) oxy-fuel combustion, which first and foremost are drastic reductions of CO_2 and NO_x emissions. A schematic of a simple OFC power plant with an FGR system is shown in **Figure 1.16**.

Figure 1.16 Diagram of a coal-fired oxy-fuel combustion power plant [185]. Among indicated components, characteristic for OFC are: an air separation unit, flue gas recirculation system, and cryogenic CO_2 capture unit.

FGR has another vital significance. Combustion of fuels in pure O_2 leads to high temperatures inside the boiler (exceeding even $2500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for coal, much higher compared to conventional, air-supplied plant), which may force the need of using more expensive construction materials (boiler walls, fuel nozzles, etc.), able to operate safely in such conditions, if any are viable at all [184,186]. It is also a major issue in the case of retrofitting, i.e. adapting already existing power plants to OFC operation. This is overcome by proper FGR adjustment – O_2/CO_2 mixture requires about 30-35 vol.% O_2 content to provide heat transfer characteristics similar to air-supplied combustion [187]. However, dilution of the feed O_2 (with non-oxidizing gas like CO_2) hinders the fuel-oxidizer contact, slowing the combustion reaction rate down, which might be unfavorable in certain applications.

The substantial inconvenience of OFC is that while the CO_2 separation process is no longer a big issue, *air separation* is an additional inherent component of the power plant's cycle (**Figure 1.16**), and specific power consumption of ASU becomes a critical factor dictating the plant's efficiency [184]. Typically, total energy savings gained with all the OFC benefits, are surpassed by a huge energy penalty induced by the operation of ASU, causing the net efficiency of a power plant to drop by 7-9% [186]. Therefore, the search for new, highly efficient O_2 production methods is a key factor to let clean, coal-fired OFC become an economically competitive power generation technology.

Another application of O₂ in power generation is in technology called *integrated gasification combined cycle* (IGCC). The most basically, in the IGCC process *gasification* plant is *integrated* with a power plant operating in the *combined cycle* [188]. An exemplary schematic of the IGCC plant is shown in **Figure 1.17**. O₂ and H₂O are employed to gasify a solid fuel (e.g. coal) and in consequence, to obtain synthesis gas (syngas, a mixture of H₂ and CO) [184]. Syngas is then purified and burned in the gas turbine to power the generator and produce electricity. The gas cycle is *combined* with the steam cycle through the heat exchanger. The heat of the flue gas leaving the gas turbine is recovered to generate steam, which is then supplied to the steam turbine and more electricity is produced with the second generator [188].

Figure 1.17 Diagram of an integrated gasification combined cycle plant [188].

IGCC is one of the cleanest and most efficient *clean* coal technologies [188]. Compared to the conventional coal-fired power plant, IGCC allows to increase the power plant's efficiency even by 15%, as reported by Mitsubishi Power [189]. Most coal-introduced impurities are removed in the gasification system, i.e. before the combustion of fuel in the gas turbine, and therefore emissions of SO₂ and particulates to the atmosphere can be practically eliminated [188]. Among other benefits, the following can be named: lowered water consumption (by ~33%), reduced NO_x, and CO₂ emissions, and fuel flexibility – even poor quality coal can be used in the gasification stage [180,188,189]. IGCC is suitable for the simultaneous production of electricity, good quality chemicals (e.g. ammonia, sulfur, sulfuric acid), and fuels (hydrogen, syngas, liquid hydrocarbons) [188]. Such a poly-generation improves the coal utilization, and thus, lowers the environmental impact of IGCC even more.

Despite even air could be used as an O₂ source for gasifiers, oxygen gas of 85-95% purity is considered optimal in terms of energy consumption if electricity is the sole product of IGCC. In the case of poly-generation of electricity and chemicals, higher O₂ purity could be required [180]. Thus, either if the mono-, or poly-generation is employed, the IGCC plant is generally equipped with its own ASU to provide on-site O₂ supply. Similarly like in the case of oxy-fuel combustion power plants, the net efficiency and environmental footprint of IGCC could benefit from introducing alternative, energetically favorable, air separation methods.

Besides the need of having ASU, IGCC has several other issues, which in consequence still hinder it from being commonly implemented. Some of those are: the complexity of the system, investment cost higher compared to typical coal-fired power plants, longer startup time, and thus, suitability mainly for a stable, base load operation [184,190,191]. What is more, the

mentioned earlier fuel flexibility is at the expense of efficiency – if coal of lower calorific value is utilized, more energy is consumed for the purification process or handling ash and moisture (also, larger equipment is required), while less energy is obtained from combustion process [190].

Medicine

Medical applications may consume approx. 15% of total oxygen production [192]. In medicine and healthcare, O₂ (or O₂-enriched air) is used in various kinds of oxygen therapies and as in artificial respiratory for patients under anesthesia or in other cases when self-breathing is hindered or not possible (**Figure 1.18a**). Oxygen therapies can vary in duration. Short-term intense treatment is applied in acute conditions like decompression illness, anaphylaxis, stroke, severe pneumonia, or in case of resuscitation. In several chronic conditions, long-term oxygen therapy may be necessary, for instance in pulmonary emphysema, bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, or dyspnea [193].

As mentioned earlier in chapter 1.3.1, cryogenic distillation is less power-consuming mainly in large-scale production and for high purities of O₂. Because of the cryogenic ASU size, such an O₂ has to be produced off-site, stored in tanks, and delivered to the hospital – thus, increasing the cost and also making the hospital's O₂ supply dependent on external factors. Today hospitals' O₂ demand is usually met by deliveries of LOX or PGOX produced mostly in cryogenic plants [168,194].

According to European Pharmacopoeia, a concentration of O₂ in medical-grade oxygen gas should be $93.0 \pm 3.0\%$ (with residue consisting mainly of N₂ and Ar) [195]. Thanks to this relatively low requirement of O₂ concentration, other O₂ production technologies can be employed (**Table 1.2**) – importantly, most of them do not need large-scale plants to meet their optimal power consumption. Therefore, those can be implemented to generate O₂ for medical use on-site and make the hospital's O₂ demand independent of external suppliers. Recent numerical analysis showed, that introducing on-site production (with a PSA unit, in this case) to replace external oxygen deliveries is a real deal in reducing the cost of medical O₂ consumption in hospitals – a gigantic cost reduction of ~97% could be achieved [194].

Figure 1.18 (a) A patient subjected to short-term oxygen therapy inside a hyperbaric chamber and (b) a patient wearing a portable oxygen concentrator in long-term oxygen therapy [196,197].

In medical use, the largest oxygen demand comes from hospitals – Bałys et al. estimated, that a hospital with 100 patients needing O₂ treatment, requires approx. 65 000 Nm³ of oxygen per month (~3.1 tpd) [194]. Even larger (by 1 or 2 orders of magnitude) demands could be easily met by PSA/VPSA or ITM air separation methods (**Table 1.2**) and potentially, also by TSA.

Exemplary commercially available, compact PSA units (ORLANE by NOVAIR MEDICAL) can deliver between 2 150 and 76 000 Nm³ of O₂ per month [198]. Much smaller O₂ generation capacities are required for personal/portable oxygen concentrators (**Figure 1.18b**) used by patients for oxygen therapy at home. The typical output of commercially available concentrators ranges in 0.5-5 Ndm³ per minute (~0.001-0.01 tpd) [63,199].

Petrochemistry

In the petrochemical industry, oxygen is employed in various processes, including the following examples: Claus process in sulfur recovery units, fluid catalytic cracking, sulfuric acid regeneration, and catalytic oxidation of intermediate hydrocarbons for the production of valuable chemicals [200–206].

- *Sulfur recovery units* (SRU) are utilized to extract sulfur from so-called sour natural gas, i.e. contaminated with significant quantities of H₂S [203]. The net reaction during the Claus process occurring in SRU results in the conversion of H₂S and O₂ into H₂O and S [203,207]. This byproduct sulfur recovered in refineries in SRUs is the majority of worldwide sulfur production [208].
- *Sulfuric acid regeneration* (SAR) is applied to retrieve H₂SO₄ spent during the alkylation process, widely performed in refineries. Alkylation is the catalytic process of combining light olefins (propylene, butylene, and pentylene) with iso-butane to produce high-octane gasoline [202,209]. During alkylation, concentrated H₂SO₄ plays the role of a catalyst, and upon a time, part of it decomposes and dilutes the acid. The role of the SAR process is to decompose this diluted sulfuric acid to SO₂, oxygen, and steam at high temperatures, then SO₂ is treated with O₂ to form SO₃, and finally to combine it again with water to recover highly concentrated H₂SO₄ [210,211].
- *Fluid catalytic cracking* (FCC) – the role of this process is to break low-quality feed (consisting typically of vacuum gas oil and other fractions of crude oil, partially processed during various refining processes like atmospheric and vacuum distillation, visbreaking, etc.) into light hydrocarbons, mainly gaseous C₃/C₄, liquid gasoline and solid coke [16,206,212]. The coke is the reason for O₂ application – upon FCC process, coke deposits on the catalyst's surface and hinders reaction. A stream of O₂ is used to burn the coke off the catalyst's surface during the regeneration stage of FCC [16,206].
- *Catalytic oxidation* – this process is used for the production of a wide range of chemicals from intermediate hydrocarbons present in raw crude oil or during further stages of refinery processing. Examples of chemicals produced this way (and what hydrocarbons are used to obtain them) include: terephthalic acid (p-xylene), benzoic acid (toluene), t-butyl hydroperoxide (isobutane), ethylene oxide (ethylene), or acrylic acid (propylene) [204–206,213]. However, some of these reactions could be performed in air as an oxidant, using the atmosphere of pure O₂ or O₂-enriched air brings significant benefits – getting rid of N₂ ballast reduce the energy required to heat up and pump the processed gas through the system and makes the environmental footprint of refineries at least a little smaller [204,205]. Use of even slightly O₂-enriched air (28%) can result in a 30% increase of production capacity in

case of oxidation of p-xylene to terephthalic acid – which is an important precursor to polyethylene terephthalate, PET, widely used worldwide [205,206].

Production of chemicals

Oxygen is utilized in the production of various chemicals. Several examples are given below.

- Nitric acid, HNO₃, can be produced via the oxidation of ammonia (from Equation 1.11 to Equation 1.13) [214,215]. Nitric acid is mainly used in fertilizers production (together with ammonia) [215].

- Hydrogen peroxide, H₂O₂, is obtained in the so-called anthraquinone process [216]. Anthraquinone (Q) is first catalytically hydrogenated (Equation 1.14) and then, the solution is oxidized to form H₂O₂ (Equation 1.15). The majority of hydrogen peroxide is used as a bleaching agent (e.g. in paper manufacturing). The remaining applications include sewage treatment, sterilization, and use as a rocket propellant [217,218].

- Ethylene oxide, C₂H₄O, is almost exclusively obtained via catalytic oxidation of ethylene (Equation 1.16) at 200-300 °C and under increased pressure [213,219]. The majority of ethylene oxide is used as a precursor in the production of ethylene glycol, which is widely used in refrigeration and the production of polymers [213]. Itself, ethylene oxide can be used for microbiological sterilization of surgical instruments, food, or books [219].

Exploration

In *aircraft*, O₂ (either stored in pressurized tanks, or in a form of chemical oxygen generators) is used for breathing in emergencies like cabin depressurization [121,123]. In *space exploration*, using pure O₂ as an oxidizer for the combustion of fuel allows for a significant reduction of mass and volume of matter that needs to be transported from Earth's surface to space (and therefore fuel consumption may be reduced). In spacesuits used for extravehicular activities (EVA), pure O₂ is used for breathing. To maintain partial pressure of oxygen similar to that on Earth's surface (~0.21 bar), the pressure inside the EVA suit (**Figure 1.19a**) is reduced to 4.3 psi (~0.296 bar) – slightly higher *p*_{O₂} is the consequence of keeping the total pressure high enough to prevent astronauts from decompression illness [220]. On the other hand, pressure cannot be too high as the oxygen toxicity condition could occur [221]. Another crucial

reason for decreased total pressure inside the EVA spacesuit is to ensure the suit's flexibility in a vacuum environment and decrease leakage hazard [220,222]. In the end, O₂ pressure inside a suit is a tradeoff between safety and convenience.

In *diving, submarines, and underwater works*, people also have to rely on artificially delivered oxygen. In submarines and diving, if so-called atmospheric diving suits are utilized, breathing gas at normal atmospheric pressure is used – with proper O₂ concentration maintained. Similar is in the case of many underwater works – a special chamber (caisson) can be employed to pump-out the water and keep the atmosphere of breathing gas at normal pressure inside. This technique is widely utilized in dry underwater welding [223]. In other cases, there is no solid barrier between the surrounding water and a diver and high hydrostatic pressure is acting directly on a diver (e.g. in ambient pressure diving or wet underwater welding, **Figure 1.19b**). For these activities, increased pressure of respiratory gas is required to enable breathing. Pure O₂ can be used only at relatively shallow depths – for deeper submerge (where water hydrostatic pressure, and therefore, required total pressure of breathing gas are significantly higher), a mixture of O₂ with other neutral gas is required to avoid oxygen toxicity [224].

Figure 1.19 (a) An astronaut during extravehicular activities and (b) a diver performing wet underwater welding [225,226].

Research

In research laboratories, O₂ gas finds multiple applications. Pure O₂ is used as an artificial atmosphere in materials preparation and experiments. For instance, in experiments, where high O₂ partial pressure is required (as applied in this work) or a non-reductive atmosphere is to be ensured. Often, materials are investigated in terms of how their certain properties depend on O₂ partial pressure in the atmosphere – mixtures of O₂ with inert gas (e.g. Ar, N₂) are used, either as ready product supplied by the manufacturer or mixed on-site to a desired O₂ concentration. O₂ gas can be also used as a reactant in the synthesis of materials.

2. Oxygen storage materials

Alternative oxygen production methods (TSA, in particular) and active materials that can be utilized in those, lie in the focus point of this work. The following chapter is dedicated to introducing the Reader to the topic of these *oxygen storage materials* (OSM), explaining how they work, and briefly describing the most important material groups. Because OSMs form a distinctive subgroup of *mixed ionic-electronic conductors* (MIEC), this topic is also shortly featured in the first place.

2.1. Mixed ionic-electronic conductors

Numerous modern technologies require materials that exhibit very unique and specific functional properties, for instance: desired thermal expansion, characteristic resistance-temperature dependence, very high or low electrical or thermal conductivity, transparency to light, and so on. In several application fields, not only the high value of conductivity is desirable, but it is also required that this charge transfer is fulfilled by more than one type of carrier, e.g. electrons (and/or electronic holes) and ions simultaneously. These materials form the group called *mixed ionic-electronic conductors* (MIEC).

For example, MIECs are commonly employed in energy storage systems like lithium-ion batteries – cathode materials of Li-ion cells are materials conducting both electrons and Li⁺ cations [227–231]. MIECs which conduct charge via electronic species and oxygen O²⁻ anions, gained a special interest in many energy- and power generation-related applications (but certainly, they are not limited to this field). They are utilized as electrode materials in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) and solid oxide electrolyzer cells (SOEC), ceramic oxygen permeable membranes (OPM) for partial oxidation of methane (POM) or O₂ production, oxygen carriers in chemical looping combustion (CLC), transducers in gas sensors, resistive switching memory (RRAM, or memristors, in other words), materials for oxygen storage, oxygen buffers in three-way catalysts (TWC), and many more [230,232–245].

Oxygen-ionic component of conductivity in the bulk can be realized with hopping of oxygen anions, either via interstitial sites, O_i^{''} (as denoted according to the Kröger–Vink notation [246,247]), or oxygen vacancies, V_O^{••} [93]. Diffusion of ionic and electronic species is typically ambipolar, and thus, transport of oxygen defects is accompanied by diffusion of electrons, e['], and/or electronic holes, h[•] [248]. Those ionic and electronic defects present in MIEC material can be either *intrinsic* – thermally induced Schottky or Frenkel defects, or *extrinsic* – associated with the introduction of aliovalent dopant into the material's structure [92,246].

Typically, MIECs are extrinsic conductors, created by the partial aliovalent substitution of one or more parent cations – such a substitution is effectively seen as an e['] (or a h[•], depending on the valence of the dopant), and therefore, the right amount of V_O^{••} needs to be formed (or O_i^{''}, respectively) to preserve electroneutrality. What is more, in the majority of MIECs, dopant cations are not only aliovalent elements, but also multivalent (i.e. they can easily change their oxidation state) – those typically include *d*-block transition metals, e.g. Mn, Fe or Co, etc., but the choice is not limited to those, as rare earth metal Ce is also used [93,96].

The nature of electronic conduction in MIECs is a complex phenomenon and will not be deeply introduced here. However, limiting MIEC materials only to perovskite-like oxides, ABO_3 , having transition metal M on B-site (i.e. AMO_3), a simplified description can be provided as follows. The presence of a multivalent cation can give a rise to MIEC's conductivity [246]. $M_M^x-O_O^x-M_M^*$ or $M_M^x-O_O^x-M'_M$ (**Figure 2.1**) cationic defect couples act as pathways for electronic defects (h^\bullet or e' , respectively) and thus give a rise to the electronic component of total conductivity via the so-called small polaron hopping mechanism [249–254]. Those *small polarons* can be described as electrons (or electronic holes) localized on a multivalent cation site and, typically, their *hopping* (between oxidized and reduced sites of a multivalent cation) is a thermally activated process [249,253–255]. In some cases, *d*-orbitals (or *f*-orbitals) of these multivalent cations, can overlap with *p*-orbitals of oxygen effectively enough to create a band structure and thus, enabling superior electronic conductivity (sometimes even metallic- or superconductive-like) [256]. Orbitals originating from the A-site cations of ABO_3 do not participate directly in electronic charge transfer.

Figure 2.1 Crystal structure of a simple perovskite ($Pm-3m$) [257].

Despite a “true” MIEC being a single-phase material (**Figure 2.2a**), in some applications, so-called heterogeneous MIECs (H-MIEC) or, in other words, multiphase MIECs are utilized [92,230]. In such case, these H-MIECs are composite materials, in which one component possess high ionic conductivity, while the electronic part is introduced with another component, e.g. metallic particles evenly spread inside the ionic conductor (**Figure 2.2b**) [96,230,253]. Typically, these materials are cermet, i.e. composites of ceramics with metals. For instance, H-MIEC cermets are used as electrode materials in SOFCs (e.g. Ni-YSZ) [244,258]. It is worth mentioning, that despite in this work, mainly crystalline ceramics (or cermets) are discussed, mixed conductivity can be also found in metallic materials, glasses, polymers, and various composites [230]. Examples of MIEC oxides with their total electrical conductivities are gathered in **Table 2.1** and some O^{2-} -conducting representatives are given in **Table 2.2** with conductivity values distinguished between ionic and electronic components.

Figure 2.2 (a) Single-phase (“true”) and (b) multi-phase (heterogeneous) mixed ionic-electronic conductors. Based on [96] and [92].

Table 2.1 Exemplary compositions of MIEC materials and values of their total electrical conductivity at 600 °C.

Composition	Atmosphere of measurement	Total conductivity [S cm ⁻¹]	Charge-transferring ion	Reference
SrTiO _{3-δ}	air	7.7×10 ⁻⁶	O ²⁻	[259]
Nd _{1.9} Ni _{0.75} Cu _{0.25} O _{4±δ}	air	40	O ²⁻	[260]
LaNi _{0.25} Cu _{0.75} O _{3-δ}	air	100	O ²⁻	[261]
Ni-8YSZ cermet ^a	4 vol.% H ₂ /Ar	500	O ²⁻	[258]
La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} Co _{0.2} Fe _{0.8} O _{3-δ} (LSCF)	air	137	O ²⁻	[245,262]
Ba _{0.5} Sr _{0.5} Co _{0.2} Fe _{0.8} O _{3-δ} (BSCF)	air	15	O ²⁻	[263]
BaSmCo ₂ O _{5+δ}	air	~110	O ²⁻	[264]
Li(Mn _{1/3} Co _{1/3} Ni _{1/3})O _{2-δ}	air	~3×10 ⁻²	Li ⁺	[227]
Li _{0.34} La _{0.55} MnO _{3-δ} ^b	air	2.13×10 ⁻³	Li ⁺	[231]
Ba _{0.5} Sr _{0.5} Ti _{0.2} Fe _{0.8} O _{3-δ}	wet air (<i>p</i> _{H₂O} = 0.023 bar)	1.0	H ⁺ and O ²⁻	[265]
PrBaCo ₂ O _{5+δ} (PBCO)	air	~180	O ²⁻	[266]
OSMs below				
Ce _{0.8} Zr _{0.2} O _{2-δ} (CSZ)	air	0.018	O ²⁻	[267]
YMnO _{3+δ}	air	~0.01	O ²⁻	[268]
BaNdMn ₂ O _{5+δ} ^d	air	~20	O ²⁻	[269]
BaPrMn ₂ O _{5+δ}	air	~100	O ²⁻	[270]
BaErMn ₂ O _{5+δ}	air	~32	O ²⁻	[271]
BaGd _{0.6} Yb _{0.4} Mn ₂ O _{5+δ}	air	~100	O ²⁻	[272]
SrCoO _{2.5+δ}	air	~20	O ²⁻	[273,274]
YBaCo ₄ O _{7+δ}	10 vol.% O ₂ /Ar	~26	O ²⁻	[275]
SrMnO _{3-δ}	air	~0.1	O ²⁻	[276]

^a H-MIEC; Composite of Ni and 8 mol.% yttria-stabilized zirconia, (ZrO₂)_{0.92}(Y₂O₃)_{0.08}. Prepared from a mixture of 45 wt.% of NiO and 55 wt.% of 8YSZ.

^b Conductivity data at room temperature (RT).

^c Total conductivity calculated as the sum of ionic and electronic components.

^d Conductivity data at 550 °C.

Table 2.2 Ionic and electronic components of conductivity of several O²⁻-conducting MIEC materials at 800 °C in air. Based on [277].

Composition	Electronic conductivity [S cm ⁻¹]	Ionic conductivity [S cm ⁻¹]	Reference
La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} MnO _{3-δ} ^a	300	5.93×10 ⁻⁷	[278]
La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} CoO _{3-δ}	1 600	0.22	[279,280]
La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} FeO _{3-δ}	129	5.6×10 ⁻³	[279,281]
La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} Co _{0.8} Fe _{0.2} O _{3-δ}	269	0.058	[282,283]
La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} Co _{0.2} Fe _{0.8} O _{3-δ}	330	8×10 ⁻³	[262,279]
La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} Co _{0.2} Fe _{0.8} O _{3-δ}	87	2.2×10 ⁻³	[279]
La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} Co _{0.8} Fe _{0.2} O _{3-δ}	1 000	4×10 ⁻²	[279,282]
Pr _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} Co _{0.2} Fe _{0.8} O _{3-δ}	76	1.5×10 ⁻³	[279]
Sr _{0.9} Ce _{0.1} Fe _{0.8} Ni _{0.2} O _{3-δ}	87	0.04	[279]

^a Conductivity data at 900 °C.

2.2. Introduction to oxygen storage materials

Generally speaking, *oxygen storage materials* (OSM) can be defined as materials having the ability to reversibly store and release oxygen, independently of the mechanism of this process. Oxygen stored by the OSM can be either adsorbed on its surface or absorbed in the OSM's structure, as indicated previously in chapters 1.4.4 and 1.4.5. Both the current chapter and the subject of the whole research presented in this work concern *absorptive* OSMs, i.e. materials storing oxygen in their bulk (crystal structure). Therefore, in the following part of this dissertation, the term OSM refers to *absorptive* OSMs, if not indicated otherwise. However, at this point, it needs to be noted, that in absorptive swing methods, a particular air constituent is captured not only in the bulk of sorbent, but in some fraction also by its surface, as the gas particle has to firstly adsorb on OSM's surface prior entering the bulk.

According to the author's knowledge, absorptive OSMs can be defined in reference to their mixed ionic-electronic conductivity, as follows: OSM is a specific type of MIEC material, which:

- has *oxygen ions* being responsible for the material's ionic component of conductivity;
- is *able to change its oxygen nonstoichiometry*, δ , via the incorporation of either interstitial oxygen ions or oxygen vacancies;
- has its δ change *adequately large* (with respect to OSM's weight or volume) and *reversible*;
- has its δ change *easily controllable* with at least one external factor (temperature, pressure, etc.).

As abovementioned, oxygen intake and release in OSMs should be driven by the change of some external factors. These include temperature, oxygen partial pressure in the surrounding gas, alternating the atmosphere between reducing and oxidizing, etc., or can be a combination of multiple of those, like, for instance, in temperature-pressure swing absorption, TPSA.

Crucial parameters characterizing OSMs can be described as follows:

- *Oxygen nonstoichiometry*, δ – it says how many moles of oxygen ions (either vacancies or interstitial ions) are present per 1 mole of OSM.
- *Oxygen storage capacity*, OSC – it says how much oxygen can be reversibly introduced (stored) in OSM per a certain amount of this OSM. OSC is being expressed in various units among the literature, with two of them being used most commonly: $\mu\text{moles of oxygen stored per 1 gram of OSM}$, [$\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$], and simply, *weight percent of oxygen stored in OSM*, [wt.%]. Typically, the weight of OSM in its reduced form is taken as a reference point in calculating the OSC.
- *Reduction and oxidation (redox) temperatures*, T_{RED} and T_{OX} – these values are used typically regarding the use of OSM in TSA and say at what temperature OSM releases oxygen (*reduction temperature*, T_{RED}), and capture oxygen (*oxidation temperature*, T_{OX}).
- *Reduction and oxidation (redox) partial pressures of O_2* – values of O_2 partial pressure in the atmosphere, at which the OSM is able to capture and release oxygen.

Good oxygen storage material should meet the following criteria:

- *High reversibility* (or in other words *oxygen storage efficiency*) – the ratio of the amount of oxygen released in one cycle to oxygen previously absorbed in this cycle. Ideally, this should equal unity. As the research on OSMs and TSA is still a relatively young field, OSM's reversibility is rarely discussed in research papers, and no strict definition of it is provided. Therefore, the author of this work proposes to use the reversibility definition as above, which is analogous to coulombic efficiency used in the characterization of electrochemical cells [284].
- *Good chemical and thermal stability* – meaning if the material does not degrade (i.e. does not irreversibly change its morphology, crystal structure, or chemical composition in an unwanted manner) upon contact with components of its working environment (e.g. atmosphere, construction materials of the reactor, etc.) and in the entire range of operating temperature.
- *Good cyclability* (or in other words, *OSC retention*) – which means how much OSC remains from cycle to cycle (or sometimes compared to the initial maximum OSC); it could be also called as long-term stability of OSM's OSC. Similar like in the case of *reversibility*, the author of this work proposes to introduce OSC retention as an analog to the parameter used for the characterization of electrochemical cells, i.e. capacity retention [284]. Alternatively, the long-term stability of OSM can be expressed with *capacity loss* – i.e. how much of OSC is lost from cycle to cycle (or in relation to the initial OSC).
- *Fast redox processes* – oxidation (oxygen capture) and reduction (oxygen release) processes should occur as fast as possible.
- *Large oxygen storage capacity*, suitable for a given application.
- *Adequate redox temperatures* (T_{RED} and T_{OX}) and *atmospheres* – which means that OSM can effectively operate in conditions imposed by a certain application (e.g. temperature and partial pressure of oxygen in a three-way catalyst, low temperature to reduce heat losses in TSA process, temperatures allowing to operate in TSA mode in air or other gases with low O_2 content).
- *Low material's cost, availability, and environmental footprint* – if an OSM consisted mainly of noble metals, oxygen production via TSA is unlikely to be competitive with conventional methods. Also, elements that are toxic, environmentally harmful, ethically questionable, or less abundant should be avoided.

As prominent OSM examples, the following materials should be named: fluorite-type ceria-stabilized zirconia $\text{Ce}_{1-x}\text{Zr}_x\text{O}_{2-\delta}$, brownmillerite-type $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$, hexagonal rare-earth manganites $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$, double perovskite $\text{BaLnMn}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$, Kagome-type, layered $\text{YBaCo}_4\text{O}_{7+\delta}$, or $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$ oxygensulfates. Selected materials are described in more detail in chapter 2.4.

2.3. Selected applications of oxygen storage materials

When looking at numerous research papers, technical reports, and specialist monographs, three application areas could be distinguished, in relation to the function which OSM performs. In the first one, OSM plays the role of an oxygen carrier (also called oxygen buffer) – among others, this area covers the following technologies: temperature swing absorption, chemical looping combustion, three-way catalysts, or oxygen storage. In the second group, the mixed ionic-electronic conductivity is utilized rather than typical attributes of OSM, like large and reversible OSC – this area includes solid oxide fuel cells, oxygen-permeable membranes, or partial oxidation of methane. Last but not least, the third area includes applications, where any property-property relation is utilized, i.e. OSM acts as a transducer, allowing to indirectly measure property#1 by measuring property#2 – thus, applications include multiple sensors: temperature probes, gas sensors, photodetectors, etc. Selected examples of current and potential OSMs' applications are briefly described below.

Oxygen storage

As indicated by the name of OSM itself, these materials can be also applied for, literally, oxygen storage. Conventionally, O₂ is stored in its gaseous form in pressurized tanks or cylinders, or as a liquid, which requires even more extreme conditions and highly advanced cylinders [285]. Typical cylinders used for compressed O₂ storage have a capacity in the 10-50 dm³ range, and maximum O₂ pressure of 150-200 bar [286]. In some cases, oxygen storage in solids (i.e. in OSMs) can be a competitive alternative. Depending on the type of OSM used, such an O₂ storage system does not require high pressures or other extremal conditions to reversibly store and release oxygen – for instance, this process can be realized via temperature swing, as described in chapter 1.4.5. As reported by Klimkiewicz, an O₂ storage system using BaYMn₂O_{5+δ} OSM can provide volumetric oxygen storage capacity even larger than that of a typical pressurized O₂ storage method – 175 g of O₂ is stored in 1 dm³ of pressurized (150 bar) cylinder (excluding the volume occupied by cylinder), while 1 dm³ of OSM can store 200 g of O₂ [287]. In terms of gravimetric OSC, the OSM system performs not as well as a conventional pressurized cylinder, ~3.7 wt.% vs. ~10 wt.%, respectively, but the benefit of not having to handle high pressure in the system may outweigh lower OSC.

Three-way catalysts

The use of *three-way catalytic converters* (TWC, also called: *three-way catalysts*) started in the middle 1970s, and as such, TWC is probably the oldest and the widest application area for OSMs [288]. In general, the purpose of using TWC is to lower the environmental impact of exhaust gases coming from combustion taking place in automotive engines – the main redox reactions taking place in TWC are shown in Equations 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3 [288]. The main element of the TWC body is a honeycomb-like structured monolith, either it can be ceramic or metallic, depending on the application (**Figure 2.3**). The reason for the honeycomb structure of this substrate is to increase the surface where exhaust gases contact with catalyst particles and therefore to increase the effectiveness of such a catalyst (the larger the reaction surface is, the more exhaust gases will manage to react in a given time).

Oxidation of carbon monoxide:

Oxidation of unburned hydrocarbons:

Reduction of nitrogen oxides:

Figure 2.3 Schematic of a typical three-way catalyst for automotive application (part of the exhaust system). The OSM material acts as an auxiliary catalyst [289].

Two types of catalysts make up the active part of TWC: the main (primary) catalyst and the auxiliary (secondary) catalyst. The first one is simply fine, evenly spread particles of noble metals: platinum, rhodium, and palladium. The role of those is to facilitate redox reactions taking place in the TWC. The latter, an auxiliary catalyst, is made of oxygen storage material, OSM (typically CSZ, ceria-stabilized zirconia). It can also be either in a form of fine particles, evenly spread throughout the TWC honeycomb body, or the whole honeycomb itself can be made of OSM, as well. The auxiliary catalyst acts as an oxygen source for ongoing oxidation reactions, and as an oxygen sink for reduction reactions. It is also called an oxygen buffer or reservoir. In the case of CSZ, oxygen buffering is carried out according to the following reaction (based on [290]):

Cleaner power generation

Modern power generation technologies aimed at cleaner utilization of fossil fuels, like oxy-fuel combustion or integrated gasification combined cycle (described earlier in chapter 1.6.2), require a continuous supply of O₂ or O₂-enriched gas for operation. Therefore, the power generation sector indirectly creates possible demand for OSMs, as these may be employed for O₂ production via temperature swing absorption (see chapter 1.4.5).

Chemical-looping combustion

Chemical looping combustion (CLC) is another alternative power generation technology. In CLC, the so-called oxygen carrier, in a form of solid particles, is used to directly deliver oxygen for the combustion of fuel. This oxygen carrier is virtually the same as what the oxygen storage material is – in some way the principle of CLC is analogous to TSA, as the O₂ is reversibly and cyclically withdrawn from and recaptured by the OSM. OSM is *looped* between the fuel reactor and air reactor – in the former, oxygen is withdrawn from OSM's (carrier's) structure and utilized to combust the fuel, while in the latter, OSM is blown with an oxidizer (e.g. air) under conditions allowing the OSM to reabsorb oxygen [291]. Then the cycle repeats. CLC technology makes the combustion of fossil fuels cleaner, as NO_x and N₂ in exhaust gases can be omitted and CO₂ maintenance becomes easier. Generally, CLC is sometimes referred to as a form of oxy-fuel combustion, with only the difference in how oxygen is delivered to the fuel, and thus, CLC brings similar benefits as oxy-fuel combustion (see chapter 1.6.2) [291].

Oxygen production via absorptive swing methods

The major possible application of OSMs is O₂ separation (e.g. from air) via swing methods, like temperature or pressure swing absorption. As the former method, TSA is strictly connected to the subject of this work, it has already been extensively described earlier, in chapter 1.4.5). The latter, pressure swing absorption, differs from the TSA basically only with the driving force of the process – swing is controlled with pressure change, instead of temperature.

Electrode materials in solid-oxide cells

In SOFCs and SOECs, electrodes are mixed ionic electronic conductors, either single-, or multi-phase. The role of such an electrode is to transfer electrons and oxygen ions between solid electrolyte, gaseous phase, and current collector. As OSMs are O²⁻-conducting MIECs, they can be applied as single-phase electrodes for SOFC/SOEC, assuming reasonable values of electrical conductivity, both ionic and electronic, and a suitable coefficient of thermal expansion [292].

Gas sensors

If a given material exhibits some relationship between its physical properties, and this relationship is relatively simple, easy to measure, and repeatable, this material can function as a transducer and be employed in metrology. In the case of gas sensors, it is required that a change in the composition of the atmosphere surrounding the sensor, induces some measurable change in the material – for instance, an increase in partial pressure of O₂ causes a decrease in the material's electrical resistance. Thus, if the oxygen nonstoichiometry of a certain

OSM depended on the p_{O_2} in the atmosphere, it could be used as a transducer in p_{O_2} probes, as the electrical conductivity of this OSM would also change with nonstoichiometry. And some OSMs were indeed reported as promising conductometric oxygen sensors, e.g. materials from the Sr(Ti/Fe)O_{3-δ} group were proposed as an alternative to conventional electrochemical lambda probes employed in automotive applications [293].

Oxygen permeable membranes

In oxygen permeable membranes, OPMs, OSM in a form of dense gas-tight sinter, acts as a pathway for oxygen only. This can be used either for the efficient production of highly pure O₂ (as described earlier in chapter 1.4.1), or in the partial oxidation of methane (POM) process, to produce syngas. Implementing OPM as a part of the POM reactor can lead to a significant operating cost reduction – of up to 25-35% [253].

2.4. Review of oxygen storage materials

In this chapter, a review of the most important OSM families is given. Typical operating parameters (e.g. oxygen storage capacity, redox conditions, etc.), crystal structure, and other essential information are briefly presented for each material group. Wherever OSC is mentioned, either expressed in $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$ or wt.%, it was calculated in reference to the weight of OSMs in their reduced forms (i.e. not having any oxygen stored), as it has been observed to be done in several research papers.

2.4.1. Ceria-stabilized zirconia

The most commonly used oxygen storage material is ceria-stabilized zirconia (CSZ), which is a solid solution of CeO_{2-δ} and ZrO₂ oxides (also called ceria-zirconia, CZ). Generally, a chemical formula of CSZ can be written as Ce_{1-x}Zr_xO_{2-δ}. OSMs from the CSZ family are widely utilized as oxygen buffers in automotive catalytic converters, TWCs, and no reports were found regarding the use of CSZ, neither in O₂ production nor in TSA mode operation.

In CSZ, oxygen exchange is possible thanks to the presence of Ce⁴⁺/Ce³⁺ redox couple, and thus, maximum OSC is limited by the cerium content, 1-x [294]. According to Equation 2.4 (introduced in the previous section), 0.25 moles of O₂ can be stored per 1 mole of Ce. Theoretically, for CeO_{2-δ}, (Zr content x = 0) maximum OSC would be 4339 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$ (~6.9 wt.%), but the crystal structure of pure CeO_{2-δ} does not provide sufficient mobility of O²⁻ ions, the material is not thermally stable, and such OSM simply does not work as it should [294,295]. Despite decreasing the theoretical OSC, the partial introduction of Zr changes the structure of CSZ to tetragonal *P4₂/nmc*, improves the thermochemical stability of CSZ, and O²⁻ transport becomes possible [294,296]. *P4₂/nmc* structure can be obtained in a wide range of Zr content (~20-90 mol%), but Ce/Zr ratio is a compromise between OSC (more Ce), stability (more Zr), and oxygen absorption/release rate (proper amount of both Ce and Zr) [295]. It turns out, that substituting half of Ce with Zr (x = 0.5) is just right [294,297]. OSC of 1500 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$ (2.40 wt.%) was reported for gas swing between 20% H₂ in N₂ and 50% O₂ in N₂ at 500 °C, which corresponds to ~86% of Ce_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O_{2-δ} theoretical capacity (1740 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$, 2.78 wt.%) [297]. It needs to be mentioned, that although this value may be considered satisfactory, it is unusually high for CSZ materials – typically, CSZ is reported to reach capacities in the range of 10-800 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$ [298]. Although Ce_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O_{2-δ} is a well-known

material, and theoretically could be a candidate for O₂ production, both the price of Zr and low OSC (even theoretical maximum) makes the O₂ separation with CSZ not competitive.

2.4.2. BaYMn₂O_{5+δ}

Just behind CSZ, the BaYMn₂O_{5+δ}-based family of materials seems to be one of the best studied. The first research interest, related to oxygen storage properties of BaYMn₂O_{5+δ}, started in the early 2000s, thanks to the works of Karppinen et al. and Motohashi et al. [143,299], and the real boom began in the 2010s, in the majority dominated by Klimkowicz et al., and Motohashi et al. [142,145,239,272,300–302].

Crystal structures taken by BaYMn₂O_{5+δ} for different oxygen content, are shown in **Figure 2.4a**. In its basic, non-oxidized form ($\delta = 0$), BaYMn₂O₅ has a tetragonal, double perovskite-type structure (space group *P4/nmm*), having layered ordering of Ba²⁺ and Y³⁺ cations along the *c* direction [143,299]. Upon oxidation, oxygen is introduced into Y layers, and Mn changes its average oxidation state to maintain charge compensation. Fully oxidized material ($\delta = 1$) adopts a monoclinic *P2* structure [143,299]. In the intermediate range of oxygen content ($\delta \approx 0.5$), additional ordering of oxygen vacancies occurs, and crystal structure evolves to orthorhombic *Ammm* [299,303].

Figure 2.4 (a) Crystal structure of reduced, intermediate, and oxidized BaYMn₂O_{5+δ} [303]. **(b)** A single swing cycle performed with BaYMn₂O_{5+δ} at 500 °C – 5% H₂ in Ar gas was used for reduction and pure O₂ for oxidation [143].

Theoretically, if the whole $\delta = 1$ could be reversibly used for the swing process, the OSC of BaYMn₂O_{5+δ} would be 3.85 wt.%. As seen in **Figure 2.4b**, OSC exceeding 3.7 wt.% is easily achievable for the swing process done at 500 °C, between pure O₂ and 5 vol.% H₂ in Ar [143]. This accounts for ca. 2300 μmol-O g⁻¹, and beyond 96% of the theoretical limit for this OSM. The rate of redox reactions is remarkably rapid – below 20 s for O₂ uptake, and ~3 min for O₂ release. What is more, the process of oxygen capture and release was proven to occur with excellent reversibility [143].

BaYMn₂O_{5+δ} was generally studied in terms of its ability to store and release O₂ using PSA. Some works reported the swing process between 5% H₂ in Ar as reducing gas, and pure O₂ as oxidizing gas [143]. However, air, or even 1% O₂ in Ar gas mixture, was shown to be suitable for oxidation, while N₂ was for the reduction stage [239,299,303]. According to the more recent paper by Motohashi et al., it can be concluded that BaYMn₂O_{5+δ} might operate in high-temperature VSA (750 °C) mode, between air at ambient pressure ($p_{O_2} \sim 2 \times 10^4$ Pa), and

low-grade vacuum (p_{O_2} below 4×10^2 Pa), with approx. 1.5 wt.% of capacity [304], which makes it a very promising candidate for high-temperature VSA O_2 separation.

To date, no research was found considering the use of $\text{BaYMn}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ in TSA operation. Moreover, nonisothermal TG data in the O_2 atmosphere can be found in the literature, showing that once the $\text{BaYMn}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ is oxidized to $\delta \approx 1$, there is practically no further weight loss or gain, across the whole temperature range of RT-800 °C [143,299]. Despite $\text{BaYMn}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ most likely cannot work in TSA mode, temperature swing might be considered as an additional boost for a primarily PSA-operating material [303].

Not long after the first studies reported by Motohashi et al., extensive research was done by Klimkowicz et al., focused on the chemical and microstructural improvement of $\text{BaYMn}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$, including the partial or full substitution of Y with other lanthanides (Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy, and Er), partial substitution of Ba with Sr, or post-synthesis treatment by high energy milling [142,239,300–302,305,306]. The obtained results led to a better understanding of processes ongoing during OSM's operation, gave guidelines on proper material designing, and some of the tested modifications increased the rate of redox reactions, which makes $\text{BaYMn}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ materials a step closer to implementation readiness.

2.4.3. $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$

The next important oxygen storage material is brownmillerite-type $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$. In terms of oxygen storage-related properties, CAMO (as it is sometimes abbreviated) gained interest only recently, in the 2010s, starting with the research reported by Motohashi et al. [146]. First and foremost, CAMO is a remarkably attractive OSM, as it can operate in both, TSA, and PSA modes, it works in air atmosphere, and consists of cheap and abundant elements.

In its reduced state ($\delta = 0$), $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$ adopts an orthorhombic brownmillerite-type structure, with an $I2bm$ space group (**Figure 2.5a**) [307,308]. Upon oxidation, oxygen anions are introduced into oxygen-deficient Al-layers, and the $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$ couple is responsible for charge compensation. In its completely oxidized form ($\delta = 0.5$), CAMO has the alternating ordering of fully oxygen-occupied, and oxygen-deficient Al-layers – thus, the unit cell becomes doubled along b direction and is described by $Imma$ space group (**Figure 2.5b**) [307,308]. As the maximum oxygen nonstoichiometry is $\delta = 0.5$, the theoretical maximum OSC of CAMO is $2066 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$ (3.30 wt.%), being relatively high, compared to the conventional CSZ (2.78 wt.%).

Figure 2.5 Crystal structure of $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$: (a) reduced ($\delta = 0$) and (b) oxidized ($\delta = 0.5$) [146].

Importantly, $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$ was proven to work in TSA mode, either in the atmosphere of O_2 or, although slower, in air (**Figure 2.6a**) [146]. While swinging between 500 and 700 °C, OSC recorded in O_2 was 2.7 wt.% (approx. $1690 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$, $\Delta\delta = 0.41$), and in air was 2.1 wt.% (approx. $1320 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$, $\delta = 0.32$) [146]. High reversibility of the swing processes is also claimed [146]. $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$ performed even better in PSA-simulating experiments (**Figure 2.6b**), carried out at 500 °C with gas swing between O_2 and N_2 – OSC of ca. 3.0 wt.% ($\sim 1880 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) was met easily, which accounts for $\sim 91\%$ of theoretical maximum [146,309]. What is more, CAMO can also work in PSA with an absorption stage taken in air under atmospheric pressure – thus, it is even more application-friendly [146]. Based on the results reported in [310], operation in combined temperature and pressure swing absorption is also a possible option.

Figure 2.6 (a) CAMO during operation in TSA mode in O_2 and air, with swing done between 500 °C and 700 °C and (b) CAMO during operation in PSA mode at 500 °C, with gas swing between O_2 and N_2 [146]. Plotted weight change, Δw , corresponds to the stored and released oxygen.

The key drawback of $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$ is the operation temperature – 500-700 °C range might be problematic for certain applications. To the author’s knowledge, this issue has not been adequately addressed yet. One work reported the addition of Pt nanoparticles and managed to perform oxidation in O_2 at 300 °C (followed by oxygen release at 550 °C in Ar), but the use of noble metals is not an economically feasible solution to this problem [78]. Partial substitution of Ca with Sr ($\text{Ca}_{2-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{AlMnO}_{5+\delta}$) was examined in terms of its influence on oxygen storage-related performance, but this did not result in decreasing operation temperatures of CAMO, but contrary, increased those even more, and reduced OSC [8]. On the other hand, this temperature increase improved oxygen transport, and thus, allowed to shorten the duration of PSA cycles.

2.4.4. $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$

Another chemical compound, which can be utilized as an oxygen storage material, is strontium cobaltite, $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$. In its basic non-oxidized ($\delta = 0$) form, $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5}$ adopts a brownmillerite-type structure with *Ima2* symmetry (**Figure 2.7**, left) [311]. In standard conditions, this phase is metastable and thus is obtained by quenching perovskite $\text{SrCoO}_{3-\delta}$ from high temperatures (above 900 °C) [311]. During oxygen absorption ($\delta \approx 0.2-0.3$), brownmillerite-type ordering of oxygen vacancies disappears (**Figure 2.7**, right), and the

crystal structure evolves from *Ima2* to tetragonal perovskite *P4/mmm* (which in fact is only slightly distorted from ideal cubic perovskite, *Pm-3m*) [311,312].

Figure 2.7 Crystal structure of $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$ in its reduced, $\delta = 0$, (left side), and fully oxidized, $\delta = 0.5$, (right side) forms [311].

In terms of oxygen storage properties, $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$ was reported to work in PSA (or VPSA, to be more specific) mode – gas swing between 16 bar O_2 and vacuum (absolute pressure of the used vacuum can be deduced from the cited reference as <0.1 bar) [311]. In such conditions, an OSC of 2.23 wt.% ($1394 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) was achieved, which corresponds to the amount of reversibly introduced oxygen of $\Delta\delta = 0.26$. In the case where the absorption step was done in 16 bar air (instead of O_2), OSC was 1.9 wt.% ($1179 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$, $\delta = 0.22$). Assuming that the maximum amount of oxygen that can be absorbed by this OSM was $\delta = 0.5$, the theoretical oxygen storage capacity of $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$ would be 4.29 wt.%. Thus, real OSCs reported for material oxidized in 16 bar O_2 and 16 bar air, would reach 52% and 44% of the theoretical maximum, respectively. Research presented by Takeda et al. shows that $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$ annealed at different temperatures has different oxygen nonstoichiometry δ [274]. Thus, the use of this OSM in TSA might be possible, but no research exploring this subject was found.

While the OSC of $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$ is slightly higher than that of typical CSZ material, the need of swinging between 16 bar and vacuum is not the most convenient option, as there are alternative OSMs, that work in high-temperature VSA with absorption step done in air at atmospheric pressure (e.g. see the section on $\text{BaYMn}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ in this chapter). Moreover, Co content, makes $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$ not the material of choice, as Co equals a higher cost, and toxicity, and supports unethical mining practices [313,314].

Interestingly, several papers showed, that desorption of oxygen from $\text{SrCoO}_{2.5+\delta}$, if done at high temperatures (above ~ 900 °C), or in O_2 -poor atmospheres (e.g. N_2 , vacuum), gives in fact the oxygen content lower than 2.5 moles of oxygen per mole of the compound – down to ~ 2.29 was reported [274,311,312,315].

2.4.5. $\text{YBaCo}_4\text{O}_{7+\delta}$

The next oxide, which has been studied in terms of its oxygen storage properties, is $\text{YBaCo}_4\text{O}_{7+\delta}$ (abbreviated as YBCO). This is another OSM that gained increased scientific interest, mainly thanks to the works of Karppinen et al. and Motohashi et al., in the first decade of the 21st century [316,317]. In its reduced form, $\delta = 0$, YBCO is hexagonally structured,

having $P6_3cm$ space group (**Figure 2.8a**) [7]. During oxidation, when the amount of absorbed oxygen, δ , exceeds ~ 1 , the structure changes to orthorhombic $Pbc21$ (**Figure 2.8b**) [7].

Figure 2.8 (a) Crystal structure of reduced ($\delta = 0$) and partially oxidized ($\delta = 1$) $YBaCo_4O_{7+\delta}$ [7]. (b) YBCO during the PSA-simulating TG experiment at 350 °C – N_2 was used for reduction and O_2 for oxidation [317].

YBCO can work in PSA mode – for instance, a swing at 350 °C between pure N_2 and O_2 (atmospheric pressure) was reported [316,317]. However, the process was rather sluggish – oxidation time at 350 °C was about 2 h and reduction even up to 10 h [316]. Moreover, YBCO can operate in the TSA process, e.g. swinging between 350 °C and 450 °C in O_2 , but with redox reactions comparably slow as in the case of PSA mode [317,318]. More importantly, TSA can be also done in air, and if so, even at temperatures lower than in O_2 – 300-400 °C [316]. Summing this up, it can be expected, that YBCO is capable of operation either in VSA with air as an oxidizer, or in combined TPSA mode – however, no research on that subject was found.

Regardless of operation mode (PSA or TSA), if oxygen absorption is done in pure O_2 at atmospheric pressure, the maximum reported δ was ~ 1.3 , which gives OSC of approximately 3.62 wt.% ($2265 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) [7,316–319]. In air, δ of ~ 1.0 is typically met, which equals ca. 2.79 wt.% ($1742 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) of capacity [316,319].

Examples of the maximum reported oxygen content are $\delta = 1.56$ (but induced with a high-pressure $KClO_3$ solution treatment at 500 °C), or $\delta = 1.46$ (in pressurized O_2 , $p=100$ atm, at 340 °C), and it was stated that this is probably close to the stability limit of the material [319]. If the complete oxidation of Co^{2+} to Co^{3+} is assumed, the theoretical maximum δ would be 1.5, which seems to be in accordance with those reported record-high data of 1.56 and 1.46. The theoretical maximum OSC, calculated for $\delta = 1.5$, would be 4.18 wt.% ($2613 \mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$). Thus, real OSCs reached in O_2 and air, account for 86.7% and 66.7% of the theoretical maximum, respectively.

Regarding sluggish redox processes of YBCO, Chen et al. made quite a breakthrough – thanks to a modified preparation method of this OSM, they achieved oxygen intake and release times of 5 and 8 minutes, respectively (swing between O_2 and N_2 at 350 °C), which is enormously better than redox times counted in hours, previously reported by Motohashi et al., Karppinen et al., and Parkkima et al. [7,316,317,320]. Moreover, such prepared YBCO exhibited promising reversibility and stability [7]. Unfortunately, despite being a promising candidate for O_2 separation from air via the TSA process, $YBaCo_4O_{7+\delta}$ shares one key drawback with another already mentioned OSM, $SrCoO_{2.5+\delta}$ – the unpreferable presence of cobalt.

2.4.6. $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4 / \text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ system

Lanthanide oxysulfate/oxysulfide system, $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ (Ln – lanthanides), is quite a unique case among all other OSMs described in this chapter. This uniqueness lies in the exceptionally large amount of oxygen that can be reversibly exchanged by the OSM within a single work cycle – ideally, 4 moles of oxygen per each mole of $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$ [321]. Although upon this process, $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$ in fact reversibly decomposes to $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$, for the purpose of easier comparison with other OSMs, it can be written as $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_{4-\delta}$, where maximum $\delta = 4$. Nonetheless, in the case of Ln = Pr, this accounts for 18.50 wt.% (11 565 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) of oxygen storage capacity – ca. 4 to 7 times higher than in other OSMs.

$\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ system was thoroughly explored mainly by Machida et al., starting in the early 2000s [322–324]. The crystal structure of $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$ was characterized as monoclinic ($C2/c$), and after decomposition to $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ ($\delta = 4$), it becomes rhombohedral $P3m1$ (**Figure 2.9a**) [322]. $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ OSMs operate in PSA-like mode and, importantly, they utilize virtually their whole theoretical maximum capacity [322–324]. Real OSC is usually only slightly decreased, mainly if reaction-facilitating noble metals are introduced, as these are not oxygen-absorbing media themselves [322–324]. No reports about use in the TSA process were found.

Figure 2.9 (a) Crystal structure of oxidized (S^{6+}) and reduced (S^{2-}) forms of OSM from Ln oxysulfate/oxysulfide system [322]. (b) $\text{Pr}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Pr}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ (with 1 wt.% Pd) during absorption-desorption cycling at 600 °C – 5% H_2/He was used for reduction, and 20% O_2/He for oxidation [323].

Unfortunately, $\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Ln}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ system typically operates at temperatures starting from ~ 700 °C (**Figure 2.9b**) [322,323]. Addition of 1 wt.% Pd or Pt is used to facilitate redox processes [322,323] and allows to reduce the operating temperature by 100-200 °C [321,324]. Another drawback of this system is its poor cyclability caused by the evaporation of sulfur [143]. This high capacity loss due to material degradation (loss of sulfur as SO_2), finally leads to almost total decomposition and vanishing of oxygen storage ability [324]. Handling of SO_2 evolved during operation might be an additional issue. This decomposition can be hindered by reducing operating temperature, and this can be done, as already mentioned, by the addition of noble metals – however, adding 1 wt.% of Pd can make the cost of material to outweigh its high OSC. In terms of the cost of material needed to separate 1 kg of O_2 in a single cycle, it is counted in thousands of USD kg^{-1} (instead of dozens of USD kg^{-1} , as for other OSMs), with Pd accounting for $\sim 97\%$ of the material's cost.

2.4.7. Hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$

Hexagonally-structured rare earth manganites, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ (R – smaller rare earth elements, e.g. Y, Ho, Er, etc.), are the leading subject of this work, and as such, they are discussed in detail in the separate section – chapter 3. Here, only brief and superficial characteristics are given.

Hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ are often abbreviated as HEX (or Hex). In their basic, non-oxidized ($\delta = 0$) form, HEXs adopt hexagonal $P6_3cm$ symmetry [149]. The most remarkable feature of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ oxides is that they can operate in the ~ 150 - 400 °C temperature range [9,147,149,151,152], which is significantly lower compared to other OSMs – for instance, the ~ 500 - 700 °C range is typical for $Ca_2AlMnO_{5+\delta}$ family [146]. This might be of great practical importance, as in some industrial processes there is a large amount of waste heat available at a similar range of temperatures [325]. Interestingly, absorbed oxygen is introduced on interstitial positions, not on vacancy sites, which also distinguishes $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ from the remaining OSMs [326].

Importantly, HEX oxides can work in the temperature swing mode. Several materials can be listed as examples: $DyMnO_{3+\delta}$, $YMnO_{3+\delta}$, or $HoMnO_{3+\delta}$, having oxygen storage capacities of 942, 730, and 1081 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$, which corresponds to 1.51, 1.17 and 1.73 wt.%, respectively (reported for TSA done in O_2 atmosphere) [147,151,152]. One of the highest OSCs was reported for $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ (synthesized via sol-gel method) and was 1550 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$ (2.48 wt.%) [327]. However, at the time the research presented in this work was started, virtually none of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ operated in air – this fact excluded them from practical application for O_2 production.

2.4.8. Comparison of oxygen storage materials

Summarizing this general insight into the field of oxygen storage materials, it can be noted that there is no single OSM that would be suitable for each application and had no weaknesses. Some of them are expensive, have low capacity, or contain unwanted elements (like Co), while others may be sluggish in operation, work at undesirable temperatures, markedly degrades upon cycling, or require extreme p_{O_2} conditions to absorb/desorb O_2 . Finally, some of here described OSMs work only in PSA mode and are not likely to be utilized for air separation via temperature swing absorption.

In **Figure 2.10**, discussed OSMs are compared in terms of their possible application areas. In this graph, the real oxygen storage capacities of OSMs are plotted against their operating temperatures. The “(PSA)” note indicates materials operating at a constant temperature in pressure swing absorption mode – details of redox conditions (gas, pressure) are given in **Table 2.3**. The remaining lines are OSMs operating in TSA mode in the O_2 atmosphere. For TSA-operating materials, the temperature at $OSC = 0$ wt.% represents reduction temperature T_{RED} . Oxidation temperature, T_{OX} is indicated by the second marker, at $OSC > 0$ wt.%. Please note: lines connecting the markers of the reduced and oxidized state of each OSM, are included only for clarity and do not represent OSC as a function of temperature. As can be seen in **Figure 2.10**, hexagonal rare earth manganites, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$, create a low-temperature operating area, that is clearly distinguishable from other OSMs. Therefore, if some

given application falls in this temperature region of approx. 150-400 °C, HEXs could probably be the materials of choice.

Figure 2.10 Oxygen storage capacities of selected OSMs, plotted vs. their operating temperatures. The characteristic low-temperature application area of hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ is approximately marked with the yellow ellipse. For materials denoted with “(PSA)”, see **Table 2.3** for details of redox conditions.

Selected data (significant from the point of view of air separation via swing process) for each discussed OSM are gathered in **Table 2.3**. Materials can be compared with each other according to multiple parameters, e.g.: cost of 1 kg of OSM, maximum theoretical and real OSCs, possible modes of operation (i.e. TSA, PSA, etc.), operating temperatures and atmospheres, cost of OSM needed to separate 1 kg of O_2 in a single work cycle or, last but not least, ability to work in TSA mode in air. The cost analysis performed by the author and included in **Table 2.3** was done based on metal and metal oxides wholesale prices, reported not earlier than in 2019 in references [328–331]. Analyzing **Table 2.3** and the literature referenced earlier in this chapter, the following is worth to be highlighted: As indicated before, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ can operate in TSA at exceptionally low temperatures, in the 150-400 °C range. This virtually makes them have no competitive OSMs in low-temperature applications. $BaYMn_2O_{5+\delta}$ and $Ca_2AlMnO_{5+\delta}$ win in terms of the cost of material needed to separate 1 kg of O_2 in a single work cycle, However, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ could be affordable as well, if adequate (i.e. cheaper) rare earths were used (e.g. Y), and the material was synthesized properly (e.g. via sol-gel route instead of high-temperature reaction).

Table 2.3 Comparison of selected oxygen storage materials, including their operating parameters of oxygen separation swing-type process, estimated material prices, and cost of oxygen separation.

Material	Cost of OSM ^a	δ theoretical max.	δ real reported max.	OSC (real)		Mode of operation	Swing parameters for TSA: gas, T_{ox} - T_{red} for PSA: T , gas _{ox} , gas _{red}	Cost of OSM needed to separate 1 kg of O ₂ in a single work cycle ^b [USD kg ⁻¹]	Ability to work in TSA mode in air	Ref.
	[USD kg ⁻¹]			[μ mol-O g ⁻¹]	[wt.%]					
Ce _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} O _{2-δ}	12.39	0.25	~0.22	1500	2.40	PSA	500 °C 50% O ₂ /N ₂ 20% H ₂ /N ₂	516	n/d	[297]
BaYMn ₂ O _{5+δ}	1.40	1	~0.98	2344	3.75	PSA	500 °C, O ₂ , 5% H ₂ /Ar	37	doubtful	[143]
Ca ₂ AlMnO _{5+δ}	1.33	0.5	0.44	1818	2.91	PSA, TSA	400 °C, O ₂ , N ₂	46	YES	[146]
SrCoO _{2.5+δ}	13.62	0.5	0.26	1394	2.23	VPSA	400 °C, 16 bar O ₂ , vacuum <0.1 bar	611	maybe	[311]
YBaCo ₄ O _{7+δ}	14.33	1.5	1.3	2265	3.62	PSA, TSA	350 °C, O ₂ , N ₂	395	YES	[144,316]
Pr ₂ O ₂ SO _{4-δ} (1 wt.% Pd)	1547.35	4	~4	~11500	~18.5	PSA	600 °C, 20% O ₂ /He, 5% H ₂ /He	8447	n/d	[322]
hexagonal RMnO _{3+δ} :										
YMnO _{3+δ}	2.27	0.5	0.14	730	1.17	TSA	O ₂ , 150-290 °C	194	maybe	[147]
YMnO _{3+δ} (SG) ^c	2.27	0.5	~0.30	1550	2.48	TSA	O ₂ , 150-280 °C	91	maybe	[327]
DyMnO _{3+δ}	173.06	0.5	0.25	942	1.51	TSA	O ₂ , 350-390 °C	11483	maybe	[147]
ErMnO _{3+δ}	31.63	0.5	0.03	111	0.18	TSA	O ₂ , n/d ^d	1829	maybe	[9]
HoMnO _{3+δ}	16.57	0.5	0.29	1081	1.73	TSA	O ₂ , 180-310 °C	9330	maybe	[152]

^a Calculated using prices from references [328–331]

^b Price of material needed to separate 1 kg of O₂ in a single work cycle, calculated as: Cost of OSM (in USD kg⁻¹) divided by OSC (in wt.%) multiplied by 100.

^c Synthesized via soft chemistry sol-gel (SG) method

^d T_{ox} and T_{red} hard to determine from the cited reference

3. Hexagonal rare-earth manganites, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$

Rare earth manganites, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ (R – rare earth metal), especially hexagonally-structured ones, offer a multitude of possible applications, including materials for capacitors and supercapacitors [332,333], transducers and actuators [334], data storage devices [334,335], electrode materials for solid oxide fuel cells [254,336,337], oxygen buffers in automotive catalytic converters [338], catalyst in CO_2 methanation (method of CO_2 capture and utilization) [339], oxygen carriers in chemical looping combustion [340], gas sensors [237], photocatalysts [341], photodetectors [342], pigments [343] – and these are the most probably not all the examples yet. A detailed description of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ applications is not given here – most of those are common to all OSMs, or MIECs in general, and some result actually from their possible use in O_2 production. Thus, the reader is referred to chapters 1. and 2., where selected applications are discussed.

In some aspects, hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ have already been extensively studied, even in the previous century – with a special interest paid to their multiferroicity, i.e. simultaneous presence of ferroelectric and magnetic properties, which was found to be a rare material phenomenon [152,344–348]. In terms of other features, there is still much to explore – for instance, the possibility to use these compounds as oxygen storage materials in oxygen production only started to gain attention in the last two decades [9,147,149–151].

The following chapter describes the group of hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials, in particular, regarding their oxygen storage-related properties, as this unique OSM family is a primary subject of this PhD thesis. Please note that in this chapter, the author of the work decided to focus mainly on the literature data that were state-of-the-art at the initial stage of his research. In recent years, HEX (or Hex, as well) became a common short name for these hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials and will also be used in this work.

3.1. Crystal structure and oxygen storage behavior of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$

Among rare earth manganites, $RMnO_3$, two main polymorphs can be distinguished: perovskite-type, and hexagonal (**Figure 3.1**). The first one is typically an orthorhombic distorted perovskite with $Pnma$ symmetry (or $Pbnm$, which is the same space group, but with a unit cell “cut” differently from the crystal structure). The hexagonal one is a layered structure, usually with a non-centrosymmetric $P6_3cm$ space group. $RMnO_3$ with larger rare earth cations ($R = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb$) tend to adopt the perovskite-type structure [148,349–359]. Contrary, if smaller rare earth occupies the R site ($R = Sc, Y, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu$), a hexagonal polymorph is more likely to appear [149,151,152,355,356,360–368]. As this rule of thumb is generally true and helpful, some middle-sized rare earths ($R = Y, Dy, Ho$) can make $RMnO_3$ prone to having either perovskite-type or hexagonal structure [149,151,152,350,351,355,361,369]. In such cases, synthesis conditions seem to determine the resulting crystal structure [151,355]. Moreover, most hexagonal $RMnO_3$ ($R = Y, Dy-Lu$) could be converted into a perovskite phase, if a high-pressure treatment (e.g. ~5 GPa at 800 °C) is applied [354,356].

Importantly, in terms of oxygen storage properties, one substantial difference arises between those two $RMnO_3$ polymorphs – only the hexagonal phase can reversibly capture and release a large amount of oxygen at low temperatures (150-400 °C) [148].

Figure 3.1 Crystal structures adopted by $RMnO_3$ for different rare earths R . Structure drawings were prepared with Diamond software, based on 04-016-1775 and 04-011-9577 diffraction patterns from the PDF-4+ database.

Figure 3.2a-c shows the basic, stoichiometric ($\delta = 0$) form of hexagonal $RMnO_3$, which exhibits $P6_3cm$ symmetry at ambient conditions (abbrev. as Hex0) [9,334,369]. This structure consists of the layers of trigonal bipyramids, MnO_5 (built with Mn^{3+} cation, 5-fold coordinated by O^{2-} anions), separated by the layers of 8-fold coordinated R^{3+} [334,369,370]. The layers extend along the a - b planes. In this symmetry, MnO_5 bipyramids are tilted, which is accompanied by an alternating shifting of R^{3+} cations along the c direction, perpendicular to the a - b layers [334,369,370]. This MnO_5 tilting disappears at high temperatures (ca. 1000 °C), and a polymorph of a higher $P6_3/mmc$ symmetry is obtained (abbrev. as HexHT, **Figure 3.2d-f**). In fact, this highly ordered, undistorted HexHT, is an aristotype structure of hexagonal $RMnO_3$ oxides [369,370]. Unit cell volume of Hex0, V_{Hex0} , is tripled compared to HexHT – unit cell parameters are $a_{Hex0} = \sqrt{3}a_{HexHT}$, and $c_{Hex0} = c_{HexHT}$ [369].

In the hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$, additional oxygen is incorporated into a - b planes in the hexagonal cavity formed by three trigonal bipyramids, MnO_5 [9,147,254,326]. This leads to an increase in the oxidation state and coordination of Mn cations. Depending on the amount of oxygen incorporated, some ordering of MnO_{5+n} polyhedrons may occur, causing a change in the symmetry of the material's structure (**Figure 3.3**). As already indicated, the stoichiometric material ($\delta = 0$) at room temperature, adopts the $P6_3cm$ space group, Hex0. However, some reports suggest that Hex0 can be preserved by $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ for oxygen excess up to $\delta \sim 0.05$ [370]. Further upon oxidation, with δ in the 0.24-0.29 range, the structure transforms to $R3c$ space group (abbrev. as Hex1), which results in a tripling of the unit cell along the c direction [9,147,151]. For δ in the range of 0.38-0.41, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ becomes orthorhombic, with the $Pca2_1$ space group (abbrev. as Hex2) [9]. Recently, an even more oxygen-loaded form was documented – $P6_3mc$ (named Hex3) with $\delta = 0.45$ [4]. The more detailed discussions on the crystal structure of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ can be found in the following references [4,9,147,149–151,254,326,334,365,369–371].

Figure 3.2 (a, b, c) Crystal structure of stoichiometric ($\delta = 0$) hexagonal $RMnO_3$ ($R = Y$) at room-temperature (Hex0, space group $P6_3cm$), and (d, e, f) high-temperature centrosymmetric aristotype structure (HexHT, space group $P6_3/mmc$). The unit cell of HexHT is tripled in volume and aligned along the same direction as Hex0, to allow convenient comparison between each other. Drawings were prepared with Diamond software, based on 04-011-9577 and 04-013-7302 diffraction patterns from the PDF-4+ database.

Figure 3.3 Comparison of XRD patterns and crystal structures of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ in perovskite-type polymorph and hexagonal polymorph at different levels of oxygen nonstoichiometry δ . XRD data used for this image was retrieved from PDF-4+ database (ref. numbers: 04-016-1775, 04-011-9577, 04-022-8018, 04-022-8019, and 04-013-7302 for $Pnma$, $P6_3/mmc$, $P6_3cm$, $R3c$, and $Pca2_1$, respectively).

As indicated earlier in section 2.4.7, the most remarkable feature of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ oxides is that they can operate in the ~ 150 - 400 °C temperature range, much lower compared to other OSMs. This unique property of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ is related to the fact, that the incorporated oxygen occupies interstitial positions, instead of the vacancy sites, as it is found in the majority of other OSMs [7,9,143,144,146,147,294,295,317,372,373]. And this hopping of interstitial oxygen ions (O_i) in turn, is often characterized by the lower activation energy, compared to the vacancy (V_O) hopping mechanism [152,326,374,375]. For instance, as reported by Skjærvø et al., the energy barrier of interstitial O_i hopping in hexagonal $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ is on the order of 0.55 ± 0.21 eV,

while in the case of oxygen transport via vacancy mechanism in ABO_3 perovskites, this barrier is typically in the 0.5-2.8 eV range [326,376].

Figure 3.4 shows a TG curve recorded for hexagonal $Dy_{0.7}Y_{0.3}MnO_{3+\delta}$ during temperature swing in the O_2 atmosphere [147]. The substantial weight gain seen in the range of approx. 250-350 °C is caused by the capture of oxygen from surrounding gas and introduction of it into the interstitial positions in the material's structure – such redox characteristics are typical for hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSMs.

Figure 3.4 Oxygen storage behavior of hexagonal $Dy_{0.7}Y_{0.3}MnO_{3+\delta}$ in O_2 atmosphere [147]. Significant weight changes can be seen between 200 and 360 °C, caused by reversible oxygen absorption and desorption.

The electrical charge introduced into the structure with absorbed oxygen is compensated by the partial oxidation of manganese [326,370]. Therefore, the theoretical maximum oxygen storage capacity of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ is limited by the total Mn^{3+} to Mn^{4+} oxidation, where $\delta = 0.5$ and then, theoretical OSC varies between different $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ only due to different molecular weights of R cations – the lighter the R cation is, the larger the theoretical OSC. For example, max. OSC of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ ($\delta = 0.5$) with $R = Y, Dy, \text{ or } Ho$, would be 2606, 1884, and 1867 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$, respectively (or in wt. %: 4.17, 3.01, and 2.99). On the other hand, real reported OSC (measured in O_2) values for the same OSMs are: 1550, 942, and 1081 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$, (2.48, 1.51, and 1.73 wt. %) [147,152,327]. Therefore, taking the ratio of the real OSC to the theoretical value, one can see that today's hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ use only about 50-60% of their possible potential. Another thing is, that most of the research reporting the oxygen storage capability of HEX OSMs, describes experiments conducted only in pure O_2 gas [9,147,149,151]. There is practically a lack of studies reporting efficient air-operating $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ – few of them were able to capture any O_2 from air, and if they did (e.g. $HoMnO_{3+\delta}$, $YMn_{0.875}Ti_{0.125}O_{3+\delta}$), they exhibited too low OSC to be applicable in an efficient O_2 production from air via TSA [152,370]. In the aspect of the application for oxygen separation from air, such only- O_2 -operating OSMs are useless. Therefore, there is still plenty to work on in the search for air-operating and more efficient HEX OSMs, and addressing the following issue is within the *aim of this work*:

Is it possible to develop an $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSM which would be able to efficiently operate in an air atmosphere in a low-temperature TSA process?

3.2. Influence of chemical composition on $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ properties

It was mentioned in chapter 3.1, that rare earth cation present in the R sublattice of $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ has a direct influence on its theoretical maximum OSC. However, it seems to be only the tip of the iceberg, and a cation occupying the R sublattice can have more significant implications. Several R -site variants of hexagonal $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ can be indicated, that were investigated in terms of their oxygen storage properties: Y [9,147,149,151,327], Dy [147,150,151], Ho [9,149,152], Er [9], and mixed $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x$ [147,151].

In one of their works, Abughayada et al. examined HEXs with $R = \text{Ho}$, Er , and Y (**Figure 3.5**) [9]. Several differences are observed between all materials, and the most remarkable are two main parameters varying with R cation: oxygen storage capacity (oxygen content), and temperatures where oxidation and reduction occur. Also, XRD analysis revealed that samples with different R exhibited different phase compositions after oxidation.

Figure 3.5 Temperature dependence of oxygen content for $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ ($R = \text{Er}$, Ho , and Y) during $0.1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating (a) and cooling (b) in O_2 (based on[9]).

In their other research, Abughayada et al. and Remsen et al. investigated a series of HEX OSMs having mixed rare earth composition on R -site: $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ (for x ranging from 0 to 1, **Figure 3.6**) [147,151]. In this case, variations of OSC and redox temperatures with R were also recorded, but no simple trend of these changes was observed.

Figure 3.6 Temperature dependence of oxygen content for $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7$, and 1) during $0.1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating and cooling in pure O_2 (arrows indicate the direction of temperature change) [147].

Thus, it is clearly visible that the chemical composition of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ (i.e. elements present on R -site) influences its oxygen storage behavior (i.e. capacity, redox temperatures, reaction rate, structural transformations) *somehow*, but it was not yet explored *how exactly* – no rules or correlations were described in the literature. Therefore, the following question arises, as indicated in the *Aim of the work* chapter:

Is it possible to establish some general guidelines might be established on how to properly design the chemical composition of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSM, to make its operating parameters match the thermodynamic conditions predetermined by the technological process, by which these OSMs would be utilized?

Nevertheless, it must be emphasized, that this adjustability of operational parameters, if possible at all, certainly will be somehow limited. First, maximum OSC is limited by the maximum oxygen nonstoichiometry, δ , which in turn is fixed to $\delta = 0.5$ in the hypothetical situation, where total oxidation of Mn^{3+} to Mn^{4+} occurred. Another restriction is the stability limit of hexagonally structured $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ – if the ionic radius of R is too large, the material will adopt the perovskite-type structure. And once the $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ is in the perovskite-type polymorph, it is no longer operational at low temperatures.

Worth to mention, multiple Mn-site substitutions were also reported so far. Examples include a partial substitution of Mn with the following, mostly d -block, metals: Cr [377–380], Fe [237,377,378,381], Ti [370], Os [382], Ni [383], Co [378,383], Cu [250], Zr [384], Mo [384], Al [378], Ga [378,385], or In [378]. However, among all these Mn-lattice-substituted materials, only Ti-substituted one was studied in terms of oxygen storage properties [370]. In their work, Levin et al. observed that partial substitution of Mn with Ti ($YMn_{0.875}Ti_{0.125}O_{3+\delta}$) altered the multi-phase oxidation mechanism of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ – absorption of oxygen did not cause the transformation of the oxygen-poor Hex0 phase to any of the previously reported oxygen-loaded phases Hex1, Hex2, or Hex3. Instead, the oxygen-loaded $YMn_{0.875}Ti_{0.125}O_{3+\delta}$ adopted a higher ordered $P6_3/mmc$ structure (Hex-HT), which normally is only observed at high (~ 1000 °C) temperatures [369]. Such a change in oxidation behavior might have serious implications in certain applications, as the chemical expansion of the material is substantially reduced (which normally is significant during $Hex0 \leftrightarrow Hex1/2/3$ transformations) [151,370,386]. Another interesting feature is that the introduction of Ti into the Mn sublattice slightly facilitated the absorption of oxygen from air. However, the performance was still poor, and rather far from being satisfactory in terms of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ utilization to O_2 production from air via TSA. Modifications in Mn sublattice is beyond the scope of the research presented in this dissertation.

3.3. Influence of preparation route on $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ properties

Hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ can be prepared by a multitude of methods, some of which are: high-temperature solid-state reaction (SSR), soft chemistry sol-gel technique (SG, usually accompanied by autocombustion at the final stage of reaction), and hydrothermal synthesis [151,387,388]. Typically, works on oxygen storage properties of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$, report to prepare

samples via SSR method or, more recently, via SG technique followed by high-temperature annealing step [4,9,147,149,151,152,327,370].

Chen et al. proposed a phase diagram of the $\text{MnO}_x\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ system in air [355]. According to that diagram, hexagonal YMnO_3 could be obtained at about 789 °C, which is remarkably low, compared to 1300-1400 °C applied during SSR synthesis by Remsen et al. and Abughayada et al., or 1050 °C by Klimkowicz et al. [9,147,151,327]. Even if the synthesis was done starting with the soft chemistry SG methods, final annealing often used to be done at 1050-1300 °C [4,149].

In the O_2 atmosphere, $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ prepared by Abughayada et al. via SSR at 1300 °C, exhibited a relatively low OSC of 1.17 wt.% (**Table 3.1**) [147]. In their work, Klimkowicz et al. showed, that modification of $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ morphology (through synthesis modification) largely influenced OSC achieved during temperature swing, also in O_2 – starting from 1.33 wt.% for SSR-synthesized (HT-annealed at 1050 °C), 1.84 wt.% for SSR but additionally post-processed with high-energy mechanical milling, and 2.48 wt.% for SG-synthesized sample followed by annealing at 900 °C (**Table 3.1, Figure 3.7**) [327]. A similar impact of morphology on OSC was observed for $\text{HoMnO}_{3+\delta}$ by Świerczek et al., and also enabled some marginal ability to work in air (only 0.5 wt.% of OSC, and recorded during very slow temperature swing, 0.1 °C min^{-1}) [152].

Table 3.1 Oxygen storage capacity (in O_2) and unit cell parameters and volume (in the as-prepared state) of variously prepared $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$.

Preparation route	OSC [wt.%]	a [Å] c [Å]	V [Å ³]	Ref.
SSR with final annealing at 1300 °C in air	1.17	6.1405(2) 11.3846(4)	371.7582(3)	[147]
SSR with final annealing at 1050 °C in air	1.33	6.1530(1) 11.3848(1)	371.28(1)	[327]
SSR with final annealing at 1050 °C in air + post-processing: 15 min of high-energy mechanical milling	1.84	6.1514(1) 11.3872(2)	373.17(1)	[327]
SG with final annealing at 900 °C in Ar(5N)	2.48	6.1486(1) 11.3898(1)	372.91(1)	[327]

SSR process typically results in well-crystallized materials, but having largely grown grains, due to the high temperatures applied [389,390]. SG methods, on the other hand, allow obtaining materials with fine-grain morphology, with grain sizes down to nanometers, thanks to significantly lowering the annealing temperature [327,387,391]. Thus, the higher the temperature, the larger the grains, and the lower the specific surface area. Analyzing the differences in OSC obtained for variously prepared $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, it can be noticed that higher OSCs tend to occur in HEX samples annealed at lower temperatures, i.e. having larger specific surface area.

The next important thing is that alteration of the $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ preparation route not only changes their oxygen storage performance but also has an impact on the crystal structure of obtained samples. For instance, although variously synthesized $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ have the same hexagonal symmetry of $P6_3cm$, unit cell parameters (a , c) and volume (V) may differ (**Table 3.1**). Therefore, oxygen storage-related properties of hexagonal $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ (for a fixed R -site

cation type) might be additionally dependent on the unit cell dimensions (which apparently can depend on the preparation method as well), but no trend is observed.

Figure 3.7 Temperature dependence of oxygen content for $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ prepared on three different routes (see description in the text) during 5 , 1 , and $0.1^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating and cooling in pure O_2 [327].

Another issue with the synthesis of hexagonal $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ is that in some research, secondary phases (impurities) were present in as-synthesized samples. Those include the perovskite-type polymorph of $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$, but also residual non-reacted oxides of Mn and R [10,152,268,387,391–393]. It seems, that hexagonal $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ is prone to have those impurities, when lower annealing temperatures are tried to be used [10,387]. Some research reported performing the high-temperature annealing step of synthesis in a flow of high-purity Ar, instead of air, to avoid the formation of orthorhombic polymorph, and promote the hexagonal one [147,151,327].

Experimental methods

4. Preparation of materials

4.1. Selection of materials

From among the whole $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ family, Y was selected as the main R cation, because:

- The ionic radius of Y is small enough to form a hexagonal polymorph of $RMnO_3$.
- Y is one of the least expensive rare earth metals.
- Y is the lightest rare earth metal (excluding Sc, which is out of scope due to its high price) and thus, the theoretical maximum OSC is also the highest.

All the studied compositions are gathered in **Table 4.1**. To investigate possible correlations between the chemical composition of hexagonal rare earth manganites and their oxygen storage performance, the series of R -substituted $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials was designed – R : Pr, Gd or Yb, and $x = 0, 0.05, 0.075, \text{ or } 0.1$. R and x were chosen according to the following criteria:

- Ionic radii of R cations were taken into account. R cations and x values were set in such a way, that each material varied with the mean value of ionic radius in $Y_{1-x}R_x$, sublattice, $\bar{r}(Y_{1-x}R_x) = (1 - x)r_Y + xr_R$ (where r_Y and r_R – ionic radii of Y and R , respectively), more or less evenly. Ionic radii of R cations in +3 oxidation state and 8-fold coordination (characteristic for R in hexagonal $P6_3cm$ structure) were taken from the work of Shannon [394].
- Small amounts of substitution were chosen, $x \leq 0.1$, as other rare earths are either heavier, larger, or more expensive than Y. Therefore, depending on R , too high x would result in lower OSC, perovskite-type structure, or higher price, respectively. The selection was done in a such way, as to obtain materials both with $\bar{r}(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ larger, and smaller than the radius of parent Y.
- Pure “parent” composition, $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0$) was also synthesized and examined as a reference sample. Despite the studies on oxygen storage properties of $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ have already been reported in the literature, HEX performance is known to be sensitive to preparation technique. Thus, a sample of $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ should be prepared analogously as other $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials in this work, to ensure more reliable conclusions.

The second series of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials (R : Nd, Sm, and $x = 0.05$) was prepared to test the upgraded synthesis method (see subchapter 4.3). Moreover, the Nd- and Sm-substituted materials allowed to verify the reliability of possible trends observed in the results of the first series.

Table 4.1 Chemical compositions of the studied materials, listed ascending according to the value of their mean ionic radius in the $Y_{1-x}R_x$ sublattice, $\bar{r}(Y_{1-x}R_x)$. Applied abbreviations, molar masses, maximum theoretical OSCs, and estimated prices are included.

Chemical composition (at $\delta = 0$)	R	x	Abbrev.	M [g mol ⁻¹]	$\bar{r}(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ [Å]	Cost of OSM [USD kg ⁻¹]	OSC (theor.) [wt.%]	Cost of OSM to separate 1 kg of O ₂ in a single work cycle [USD kg ⁻¹]
Y _{0.9} Yb _{0.1} MnO ₃	Yb	0.1	Yb01	200.255	1.0156	4.00	3.995	100
Y _{0.95} Yb _{0.05} MnO ₃	Yb	0.05	Yb005	196.048	1.0173	3.16	4.080	77
YMnO ₃	-	0	-	191.841	1.0190	2.27	4.170	54
Y _{0.95} Gd _{0.05} MnO ₃	Gd	0.05	Gd005	195.258	1.0207	3.23	4.097	79
Y _{0.95} Sm _{0.05} MnO ₃	Sm	0.05	Sm005	194.914	1.0220	2.23	4.104	54
Y _{0.9} Gd _{0.1} MnO ₃	Gd	0.1	Gd01	198.675	1.0224	4.16	4.026	103
Y _{0.95} Nd _{0.05} MnO ₃	Nd	0.05	Nd005	194.608	1.0235	3.97	4.111	97
Y _{0.95} Pr _{0.05} MnO ₃	Pr	0.05	Pr005	194.441	1.0244	4.28	4.114	104
Y _{0.925} Pr _{0.075} MnO ₃	Pr	0.075	Pr0075	195.741	1.0270	5.27	4.087	129
Y _{0.9} Pr _{0.1} MnO ₃	Pr	0.1	Pr01	197.041	1.0297	6.24	4.060	154

4.2. Sol-gel autocombustion synthesis

Sol-gel synthesis followed by autocombustion and high-temperature annealing was chosen to prepare the first series of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials: $R = \text{Pr, Gd, or Yb}$ and $x = 0.05, 0.075, \text{ or } 0.1$, and parent, not substituted $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0$). As starting reagents, following chemicals were used: $Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Y(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Gd(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Pr(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, and Yb_2O_3 . All chemicals were at least 99.9% pure and were weighed with 0.1 mg accuracy (theoretically resulting in the error of each element's stoichiometry being lower than 0.3%). Firstly, nitrates (and Yb_2O_3 in the case of Yb-containing materials) were dissolved in deionized water with the addition of concentrated (65%) nitric acid in the amount of 3 ml per 1 g of the final material. The dissolution was done on a heated magnetic stirrer. Then, citric acid (CA) was added in an excess amount – molar ratio to the number of metal ions (MI) in the solution was CA:MI 1.5:1. CA plays the role of a complexing agent, to improve the homogeneity of the mixture, and additionally, is a fuel in the autocombustion reaction. Lastly, ammonia solution (25% conc.) was added to the mixture until the pH was approx. 7. Besides neutralization of the solution's pH, ammonia is a fuel for the autocombustion reaction, but more importantly, together with NO_3^- present in the solution, it constitutes ammonia nitrate – a trigger allowing for autocombustion to occur at as low as 200 °C [395].

In the next step, the solution was transferred from a beaker on a magnetic stirrer to a quartz evaporating dish and placed in a heating mantle. The mixture was heated until the water evaporated, the sol transformed into a gel, and finally, autocombustion occurred at ca. 200 °C. The obtained fine-grained powder was then heated for 2 hours at 400 °C in an air flow (50 ml min⁻¹) in order to burn off any possible residuals after the autocombustion reaction. After this

stage, the precursor consists of a partially amorphous/partially crystalline mixture of simple Mn- and R-oxides.

In the very final stage of the synthesis, the fine-grained precursor was annealed for 6 h at temperatures ranging from 900-1050 °C (with 5 °C min⁻¹ cooling and heating) in a flow of inert gas (Ar, 5N purity, 50 ml min⁻¹ flow). During this step, the desired hexagonal phase is created.

4.3. Refinement of the preparation route

The preparation route described in the previous section uses Mn nitrate hydrate as a source of Mn for the synthesis. The high water affinity of Mn nitrate caused inaccuracies during the weighing of this chemical, and as a consequence, too low Mn content in the mixture resulted in the presence of (Y_{1-x}R_x)₂O₃ impurity in the final material. However, the impurity content was relatively low and did not affect the Y/R ratio in the final Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+δ} compounds, therefore it could be neglected. This issue is also referred to in chapter 6, and the justification of the made assumption (that the Y/R ratio is not affected) is provided in the author's work [1].

Nonetheless, trials were undertaken to solve this problem and eliminate the presence of (Y_{1-x}R_x)₂O₃ impurity. Several approaches were implemented, including:

- Evaluation of the real H₂O content in Mn(NO₃)₂·(4±y)H₂O using thermogravimetry.
- Preparation of the water solution of Mn-nitrate with standardized concentration. The exact concentration of Mn²⁺ cations was determined by drying a known amount of the solution, baking the residue at 700 °C, and weighing the obtained oxide (Mn₂O₃).
- Replacement of all nitrates with oxides (especially Mn nitrate).

Finally, the approach of replacing nitrates with oxides was chosen for the preparation of the second series of Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+δ} materials (R = Nd, Sm, x = 0.05). The following chemicals, having at least 99.9% purity, were used: Y₂O₃, Nd₂O₃, Sm₂O₃, and Mn₂O₃. Chemicals were dissolved in a solution containing nitric acid (5 ml of 65% acid per 1 g of final material), citric acid (2:1 CA:MI molar ratio), and deionized water. The solution was heated and continuously stirred on a magnetic stirrer. After the complete dissolution of chemicals, ethylene glycol (EG) was added to improve homogeneity by polymerization of MI-CA complexes. The EG:CA ratio was set to 1:2. The following steps were identical as in the first series of materials: the solution was neutralized with ammonia and dried, sol-gel transition and autocombustion occurred, and the obtained precursor was annealed at a high temperature in Ar flow. Despite solving the Mn:R ratio problem, another issue appeared – in several samples annealed at less than 1000 °C, residuals of non-reacted Mn- and R-oxides were present besides the main hexagonal phase, or in some cases, even the traces of perovskite-type phase could be detected. To overcome this problem, the temperature of the final annealing had to be increased to 1000 °C with a dwell time of 6 hours (5 °C min⁻¹ cooling and heating rate).

5. Characterization of materials

5.1. X-ray diffractometry

The phase composition and crystal structure of materials were examined with X-ray diffractometry (XRD). Empyrean (PANalytical) diffractometer in θ - θ Bragg-Brentano geometry with Cu K α radiation source and PIXcel3D detector were used. The voltage and current of the X-ray tube were set to the 30-45 kV range, and 40 mA, respectively.

Ambient temperature XRD

Samples in form of polycrystalline powders were analyzed in the 10-110 deg 2θ range. Datapoints were collected with a step size of 0.01313 deg and the total time of each measurement was ca. 51 min. Ambient measurements were conducted at room temperature (RT, 25 \pm 5 °C) in atmospheric air under atmospheric pressure.

First, diffractograms were analyzed qualitatively – phase identification was done using HighScore Plus (PANalytical) software with PDF-4+ (ICDD) diffraction database. The most important phases that were considered, are Hex0 ($P6_3cm$), Hex1 ($R3c$), Hex2 ($Pca2_1$), Hex3 ($P6_3mc$), HexHT ($P6_3/mmc$), perovskite-type $RMnO_3$ (e.g. $Pbnm$ or $Pnma$), and possible residuals of precursor powder: rare earth oxides and manganese oxides. If the presence of any phase was uncertain (e.g. due to overlapping of its main reflections with the reflections from another phase), such phase was considered *possibly present*, included in the Rietveld refinement, and verified (i.e. if the refinement had significantly better quality, the presence of this uncertain phase was presumed to be true).

Rietveld refinements were performed using GSAS software with its graphical interface, EXPGUI [396,397]. The background curve was refined with the *Shifted Chebyshev* function with the number of terms set to 10. The zero-point correction was applied. *Marquardt Damping* was set to maximum in the initial refinement. For the refinement of profiles, GU and LX parameters of the type 5 function were used. All R -sites were assumed to be proportionally occupied by Y and R -dopant, according to the selected chemical compositions (**Table 4.1**). The isotropic factor of thermal atomic displacement, U_{iso} , was refined and assumed to be identical for all cations among all refined phases, and identical for all oxygen anions among all refined phases. Coordinates of rare earth and manganese cations were refined. Coordinates of Y and R -dopant occupying the same site, were fixed to stay equal. Uncertainties of the refined unit cell parameters, volume, theoretical density, etc., were taken from refinement results obtained in GSAS. The typical error of refined unit cell parameters is in the order of 0.0001 Å.

Where applicable, crystallites size, τ , was calculated using the Scherrer equation:

$$\tau = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (\text{Equation 5.1})$$

where:

$K = 0.9$ – dimensionless shape factor,

$\lambda = 0.154059$ nm – wavelength of X-ray radiation from Cu K α source (0.154059 nm),

β – full width at half maximum (FWHM) of an XRD reflection peak, corrected by the instrumental broadening,

θ – position (Bragg angle) of a specific reflection.

Crystallite sizes reported in the *Results and discussion* section were calculated as a mean of τ values retrieved for 4 of the main reflections from the hexagonal $P6_3cm$ phase: at 2θ angles of approx. 15.5, 22.8, 30.0, and 33.0 deg (002, 102, 111, and 112 planes, respectively). The relative error of such calculated crystallite size was in the 10-20% range.

High-temperature XRD

For the high-temperature measurements (HT-XRD), Anton Paar HTK 1200 N oven-chamber was used. To determine the phase stability and linearized thermal expansion coefficient (TEC, Equation 5.2), the sample was heated up to 500 °C and cooled back down to RT, in a 50 ml min⁻¹ flow of synthetic air, with the data collection every 50 °C. Recorded data were analyzed analogously, as in the case of ambient XRD measurements.

$$\text{TEC} = \frac{1}{L} \frac{\Delta L}{\Delta T} \quad (\text{Equation 5.2})$$

where L – initial dimension (e.g. unit cell parameter a , b or c , unit cell volume V , $\sqrt[3]{V}$, or other), ΔL – change in dimension L upon temperature change ΔT [K]. By plotting the $\frac{\Delta L}{L}$ data as a function of ΔT , linear refinement can be done, and TEC can be read as a slope of the refined line. The typical TEC error was $u(\text{TEC}) = 0.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Isothermal in situ HT-XRD oxidation to determine the rate-limiting process

An additional, 25 h-long, non-ambient isothermal oxidation experiment was conducted at 220 °C in air flow, aimed to explore phase transformations associated with the oxidation process. Pr005 sample was first reduced (Hex0, $\delta \approx 0$) at 500 °C inside the diffractometer, and then quickly cooled down (20 °C min⁻¹) to the $T_{\text{OX}} = 220$ °C. Diffractograms were recorded continuously for 25 hours. In this isothermal *in situ* oxidation experiment, the data range (2θ) was narrowed down to 10-70 deg, to shorten the duration of each dataset collection, and therefore to better follow ongoing phase transformations. To study the mechanism (the rate-limiting process) of the phase transition (oxidation) it was possible to utilize the kinetic studies approach as proposed by Hancock and Sharp [398,399] presented for BaYMn₂O₅–BaYMn₂O₆ system by Motohashi et al. and Klimkowicz et al. [142,145]. Assuming the nature of the observed Hex0→Hex1 transformation is two-phase, and defining the parameter α as a time-dependent fraction of the reacted material (or in other words, conversion extent, i.e. amount of the phase converted, Equation 5.3), $\ln(-\ln(1-\alpha))$ vs. $\ln(\text{time})$ function can be plotted. The slope of this line (m parameter) is related to the type of kinetics of the oxidation reaction that is limiting the process, i.e. either (1) bulk diffusion-controlled ($m \sim 0.54-0.62$), (2) phase boundary-controlled- and first-order reactions ($m \sim 1.00-1.11$), or (3) nucleation-controlled process ($m = 2$ or 3) [142,145,398,399]. A similar experiment was also performed using thermogravimetry under identical conditions (temperature, time, and atmosphere).

$$\alpha = \frac{c_{m,\text{HEX1}}}{c_{m,\text{HEX1}} + c_{m,\text{HEX0}}} \quad (\text{Equation 5.3})$$

where: α – a fraction of the reacted material (conversion extent), [-], $c_{m,\text{HEX0}}$, $c_{m,\text{HEX1}}$ – the content of Hex0 and Hex1 phases, respectively, [wt.%], (values obtained from Rietveld refinements of XRD data).

5.2. Thermogravimetry

The absorption/release of oxygen by the materials was studied with thermogravimetry (TG). All measurements were carried out using Q5000 IR thermobalance (TA Instruments), if not stated otherwise in the text. TG experiments allowed evaluation of the amount of absorbed oxygen (δ , and thus OSC as well) during temperature swing, speed of redox processes, and characteristic temperatures of oxidation (T_{OX}) and reduction (T_{RED}). The following paragraphs contain a detailed description of multiple TG experiments performed in this work.

Basic characterization of oxygen storage behavior

Samples of each HEX material in their as-synthesized state were subjected to 3 cycles of heating and cooling between room temperature and 500 °C. Different heating/cooling rate was applied in each cycle, in the following order: 5, 1, and 0.1 °C min⁻¹ for the 1st, 2nd and 3rd cycle, respectively. The slowest rate was to determine the quasi-equilibrium oxygen content of studied OSMs, and therefore to assess the real achievable maximum OSC of the materials. Faster, 5 and 1 °C min⁻¹ cycles were used to evaluate the possibility of using the materials in real-life applications. To keep a reasonable duration of TG measurements, the slowest rate was applied in the temperature range, where redox processes proceed (i.e. in 150-350 °C or 100-350 °C ranges, depending on the material), while outside this temperature range, the rate was 1 °C min⁻¹.

For each material, two of such 3-cycle measurements were done. The first was performed in a flow of high-purity O₂ (5N), to assess materials' performance analogously as reported in previous works, and allow better comparison [9,147,149–151,327]. The second measurement was done in a flow of synthetic air (dry mixture of O₂, 21(2)%, and N₂, H₂O ≤ 3 ppm) – it was carried out to determine the possibility of utilizing these OSMs for oxygen production via TSA-based air separation. In both cases, 100 ml min⁻¹ gas flow was applied – such a flowrate provided a multifold excess of gaseous O₂ to ensure it is not a limiting factor of oxidation reaction, and to maintain approximately constant p_{O_2} .

Before the 1st cycle, as-synthesized samples were subjected to an additional 5 °C min⁻¹ cycle (in synthetic air) to desorb possible surface contaminations. This caused some mild oxidation of tested materials, and as a result, the starting oxygen content was slightly higher than 3.00 at the beginning of the 3-cycle sequence of TG measurements. According to the previous reports, hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSMs are close to oxygen-stoichiometric ($\delta \approx 0$) at 500 °C [147,149–151]. This assumption was made in the calculations of oxygen content from mass recorded in TG measurements. Thus, sample mass at 500 °C in the slowest, quasi-equilibrium, 0.1 °C min⁻¹ cycle, was taken as the mass of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ with $\delta = 0$. Oxygen nonstoichiometry, δ , at any point, was calculated as follows:

$$\delta = \frac{n_O}{n_{HEX,RED}} = \frac{\Delta m M_{HEX,RED}}{M_O m_{RED}} = \frac{(m - m_{RED}) M_{HEX,RED}}{M_O m_{RED}} \quad (\text{Equation 5.4})$$

where:

$$n_O = \frac{\Delta m}{M_O} = \frac{m - m_{RED}}{M_O},$$

$$n_{HEX,RED} = \frac{m_{RED}}{M_{HEX,RED}},$$

n_O – number of moles of oxygen introduced into $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ structure,
 $n_{HEX,RED}$ – number of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ moles,
 $M_{HEX,RED}$ – molar mass of the hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ oxide in its reduced form ($\delta = 0$),
 M_O – a molar mass of oxygen,
 m_{RED} – mass of the $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ oxide in its reduced form ($\delta = 0$), i.e. at 500 °C,
 Δm – mass change of the sample caused by the absorbed oxygen,
 m – a mass of the sample at the point where the oxygen content is needed to be calculated.
 The typical error of such calculated δ did not exceed $u(\delta) = 0.001$ – see *Appendix A* for a detailed description of how the measurement errors were evaluated. However, it needs to be mentioned that the validity of this error value is dependent on the validity of the abovementioned assumption, that $\delta = 0$ at 500 °C. Nonetheless, even if the assumption were not accurate enough, it affects calculated δ for each sample the same – thus, any trends observed in TG results would be still valid, only slightly shifted towards higher or lower values of δ .

Oxygen storage capacity, OSC, expressed in wt.%, was calculated as:

$$OSC = 100 \frac{\Delta m}{m_{RED}} \quad (\text{Equation 5.5})$$

where:

Δm – mass change of the sample caused by the absorbed oxygen,
 m_{RED} – mass of the $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ oxide in its reduced form ($\delta = 0$), i.e. at 500 °C.

Oxygen storage capacity expressed in $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$ was calculated as:

$$OSC_{\mu\text{mol}} = \frac{OSC}{100} \frac{1000000}{M_O} = 10000 \frac{OSC}{M_O} \quad (\text{Equation 5.6})$$

where:

OSC – oxygen storage capacity (calculated as in Equation 5.5),
 M_O – a molar mass of oxygen.

Tested powder (typically 10-30 mg) was evenly spread across the platinum sample pan and the gas was flowing from one side through to the close vicinity of the sample. In the Q5000 IR thermobalance, the thermocouple is mounted just below the sample pan and is calibrated to give the temperature reading accuracy of 1 °C. Data readings were done with a sampling rate of 80 datapoints per minute. The accuracy of the mass reading was not worse than 0.1%. More details about the errors of calculated δ and OSC are provided in *Appendix A*.

Determination of reduction and oxidation temperatures

To evaluate reduction and oxidation temperatures at quasi-equilibrium, $T_{RED,eq}$, and $T_{OX,eq}$, the temperature derivative of the oxygen nonstoichiometry was calculated during the slowest (0.1 °C min⁻¹) cycle. Values of the temperature, T , at which maximum weight loss during heating and maximum weight gain during cooling were observed, were defined as $T_{RED,eq}$ (Equation 5.7) and $T_{OX,eq}$ (Equation 5.8), respectively. The method is visualized in **Figure 5.1**.

$$\left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial T}\right)_{0.1\text{C/min heating}} = \min \Rightarrow T = T_{\text{RED,eq}} \quad (\text{Equation 5.7})$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial T}\right)_{0.1\text{C/min cooling}} = \max \Rightarrow T = T_{\text{OX,eq}} \quad (\text{Equation 5.8})$$

Figure 5.1 Method of $T_{\text{OX,eq}}$ and $T_{\text{RED,eq}}$ temperatures determination.

Oxygen content equilibration as a function of T and p_{O_2}

In the case of the best-performing material, Pr005, the influence of p_{O_2} on oxygen content was studied to determine the potential of its application in TPSA and PSA, besides TSA only. Near-equilibrium oxygen content values for the Pr005 sample were evaluated as a function of p_{O_2} and T simultaneously. To provide different p_{O_2} , four gases were used: O_2 (5N), synthetic air (21(2) vol.%), mixture of O_2 (1 vol.%) in Ar, and pure Ar (5N, $\text{O}_2 \leq 2$ ppm). The shortest time of mass equilibrations was ca. 1 h (at higher T and/or p_{O_2} , where the oxidation occurred faster), and the longest was 40 h (at lower T or p_{O_2}). In the range where mass changes were the largest, data were collected every 10 °C.

Selection of optimal reduction and oxidation temperatures of Pr005 for TSA application

For the best-performing material, Pr005, reduction and oxidation characteristics in air were studied at T_{RED} and T_{OX} different than quasi-equilibrium $T_{\text{RED,eq}}$, and $T_{\text{OX,eq}}$ obtained as described in Equation 5.7 Equation 5.8.

To examine reduction behavior at various T_{RED} , the Pr005 sample was first reduced for 1 h at 300 °C in air and then oxidized for 5 h at $T_{\text{OX,eq}} = 230$ °C prior to every studied T_{RED} . It was done to ensure the same starting point (i.e. oxygen content) for each reduction. Then, the temperature was set to one of the studied T_{RED} and kept for 30 min. T_{RED} were in the 256-300 °C range. To study the oxidation behavior, the sample was reduced at 300 °C for 30 min in air prior to oxidation at each considered T_{OX} . After this reduction, the temperature was changed to T_{OX} , and kept for 5 h. T_{OX} were in the 190-260 °C range.

Cyclic reduction and oxidation of Pr005 – TSA process simulation

To determine the potential of using materials (developed in this work) in the TSA process for air separation, a TG experiment simulating such a process was performed. Suitable oxidation and reduction conditions (temperatures and times, as indicated in **Figure 5.2**) were chosen according to previous T_{RED} and T_{OX} selection experiments: reduction at $T_{\text{RED}} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $t_{\text{RED}} = 5\text{ min}$ and oxidation at $T_{\text{OX}} = 220\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $t_{\text{OX}} = 30\text{ min}$ were selected as the cycle parameters. Temperature swing between T_{RED} and T_{OX} lasted $\sim 1\text{ min}$ ($100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating/cooling rate), thus the whole TSA cycle took 37 min. Before cycling, the sample weight was equilibrated at $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($\delta = 0$) to allow the calculation of oxygen content, δ . 20 cycles were done for the Pr005 sample prepared as described in chapter 0, and 100 cycles for the Pr005 prepared using a modified synthesis method. All TSA-simulating experiments were performed in 100 ml min^{-1} flow of synthetic air.

Figure 5.2 Exemplary flow of the TSA process showing the elementary operational parameters.

Comparison of Pr005 performance in TSA, PSA, and TPSA

To evaluate if the Pr005 material can operate also in PSA mode and if the addition of pressure swing to temperature swing (TPSA) can improve cycling performance, six additional experiments were done. These measurements were done at Shibaura Institute of Technology (Tokyo, Japan) with the assistance of Prof. Alicja Klimkowicz. Q5500 IR thermobalance (TA Instruments) was used. The first three experiments were designed to compare Pr005 operation in TSA, PSA, and TPSA processes:

- 1) Five TSA cycles in air with swing between $T_{\text{OX}} = 220\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($t_{\text{OX}} = 150\text{ min}$) and $T_{\text{RED}} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($t_{\text{RED}} = 30\text{ min}$);
- 2) Five PSA cycles at $230\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with swing between air ($t_{\text{OX}} = 150\text{ min}$) and Ar ($t_{\text{RED}} = 150\text{ min}$);
- 3) Five TPSA cycles with swing between air at $T_{\text{OX}} = 220\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($t_{\text{OX}} = 150\text{ min}$) and Ar at $T_{\text{RED}} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($t_{\text{RED}} = 30\text{ min}$).

The temperature swing rate was $\sim 50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ and the pressure swing (gas change) rate was 50 ml min^{-2} . Gas flow was set to 100 ml min^{-1} at ambient pressure. Before each experiment, the Pr005 sample was equilibrated for 15 min at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in Ar to determine sample weight at $\delta = 0$ for calculations.

Finally, a long TPSA cycling experiment was performed. Ca. 230 cycles were done using the following cycle parameters: oxidation at $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air for 30 min, and reduction at $280 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 min in Ar. Including swing duration, the total cycle time was 37 min.

Isothermal in situ TG oxidation to determine the rate-limiting process

Isothermal, 25 h-long oxidation of Pr005 at $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air was done using TG. The sample was firstly reduced at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and then the temperature was quickly switched to $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, where the oxidation occurred. To determine the rate-limiting process of oxidation, data were analyzed analogously as in the isothermal HT-XRD experiment, described previously in *Isothermal in situ HT-XRD oxidation to determine rate-limiting process* paragraph, i.e. recorded weight of the sample was expressed as a conversion extent vs. time. In the case of this TG experiment, the conversion extent was calculated according to Equation 5.9.

$$\alpha = \frac{\delta}{\delta_{25\text{h}}} = \frac{m - m_{\text{RED}}}{m_{25\text{h}} - m_{\text{RED}}} \quad (\text{Equation 5.9})$$

where:

α – a fraction of the reacted material (conversion extent), [-],

δ – oxygen content, [-],

$\delta_{25\text{h}}$ – oxygen content after 25 hours of oxidation, [-],

m – a mass of the sample, [mg],

m_{RED} – a mass of the reduced sample (i.e. at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), [mg],

$m_{25\text{h}}$ – a mass of the sample after 25 hours of oxidation, [mg].

Influence of preparation route on material's oxygen storage behavior

To evaluate the influence of the preparation technique on the material's performance, TG experiments were done only in air. They consisted of only two cycles of heating and cooling in the RT- $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ range: 5 and $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, respectively. Besides δ (Equation 5.4) and OSC (Equation 5.5), the oxidation rate was calculated (Equation 5.10). As previously, tests were done for as-synthesized samples and preceded with one $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ cycle, to desorb any impurities from the powder's surface. For the samples contaminated with other phases (e.g. oxides of Mn or R), Equation 5.11 was used to determine oxygen content corresponding only to the active, hexagonal $\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ phase.

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = \frac{\Delta\delta}{\Delta t} = \frac{\delta_2 - \delta_1}{t_2 - t_1} = \frac{\frac{(m_2 - m_{\text{RED}}) M_{\text{HEX,RED}}}{M_{\text{O}} m_{\text{RED}}} - \frac{(m_1 - m_{\text{RED}}) M_{\text{HEX,RED}}}{M_{\text{O}} m_{\text{RED}}}}{t_2 - t_1} = \frac{\Delta m M_{\text{HEX,RED}}}{M_{\text{O}} m_{\text{RED}} (t_2 - t_1)} \quad (\text{Equation 5.10})$$

$$\delta_{\text{HEX}} = \delta \frac{100}{c_{m,\text{HEX}}} \quad (\text{Equation 5.11})$$

where:

δ – oxygen content calculated considering a single-phase sample (Equation 5.4)

$c_{m,HEX} - Y_{1-x}R_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ phase content expressed in wt.% (value got from Rietveld refinements of XRD data)

Characterization of oxygen storage behavior of sintered samples

Additional basic TG experiments were done using materials in the form of sintered pellets to allow better comparison to the results of conductivity, thermoelectric, and dilatometric measurements. All of those, including TG, were done in the same conditions: six cycles of heating and cooling with a $2\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ rate in a 20 ml min^{-1} flow of three gases with different p_{O_2} . The first two cycles were done in Ar(5N), the next two in synthetic air, and the last two in O₂(5N). Compared to the conductivity, thermoelectric, and dilatometric measurements, the temperature range of TG was narrowed down to 30-500 °C, due to equipment limitations.

5.3. Transport properties measurements

5.3.1. Direct current electrical conductivity

Electrical conductivity measurements were carried out using the direct current pseudo-4-point technique (4DC). For each material, 2 cycles of heating and cooling ($2\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) were performed in the range from ca. 50 °C to 1000 °C. Similar to TG analyses, tests were done in the flow of Ar, air, and O₂ (20 ml min^{-1}). Samples of rectangular shape (approx. $7\times 5\times 1\text{ mm}$) were mounted inside the Probostat holder (NorECs, Oslo, Norway). Data were collected with Keithley 2000 (Tektronix, Beaverton, OR, USA) multimeter, and measurement was controlled by Omega2 (NorECs, Oslo, Norway) software. Pt electrodes were used in the studies—these were prepared by doctor-blading Pt paste on the opposite faces of the samples and firing at 980 °C for 15 min. Conductivity (specific conductance) was calculated as follows:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\rho} = \frac{l}{RA} \quad (\text{Equation 5.12})$$

where:

σ – electrical conductivity of the sample, S cm^{-1} ,

ρ – electrical resistivity of the sample, $\Omega\text{ cm}$,

l – length of the sample, cm,

A – cross-section area of the sample, cm^2 ,

R – measured resistance of the sample, Ω .

Samples were prepared as follows:

- 1) Already synthesized powders (1000 °C, 6 h, Ar) were mixed with the addition of 2 wt.% of polyvinyl butyral (PVB) dissolved in propanol, to lower the friction and improve densification during the pressing.
- 2) After drying the powders out of propanol, powders were sieved through a 100 μm sieve.
- 3) Such prepared powders were uniaxially pressed using a 13 mm cylindrical die. Die was constantly connected to a vacuum pump and $\sim 0.5\text{ g}$ of powder was pressed in 4 steps, with increasing force: 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, and again 1.5 tons. The pressure was slowly released between each step.

- 4) Such prepared pellets were put in the alumina boat inside the furnace. Sintering was done at 1400 °C for 3 h, with a 3 C min⁻¹ heating and cooling rate. Pellets were put on the layer of powder to decrease the friction between the alumina boat and pellets, and therefore to minimize uneven densification.

Since the relative density of all samples ranged between 79–83%, a porosity-related correction factor was introduced in the calculations, according to Bruggeman's model [27,28]. Conductivity calculated using Equation 5.12 was multiplied by the correction factor (Equation 5.13) to obtain the conductivity of the bulk. For each sample, resistance was measured along its longest dimension. Relative error of such derived conductivity reached ~10% at worst and was mainly caused by inaccuracies in the measurement of the sample's length and cross-section dimensions.

$$\gamma_B = \frac{2}{2-3\varepsilon} = \frac{2}{2-3(1-d_{rel})} = \frac{2}{2-3\left(1-\frac{d_{real}}{d_{XRD}}\right)} = \frac{2}{2-3\left(1-\frac{m}{lA}\right)} \quad (\text{Equation 5.13})$$

where:

γ_B – Bruggeman's correction factor, - ,

ε – porosity of the sample, - ,

d_{rel} – relative density of the sample, - ,

d_{real} – real density of the sample, g cm⁻³,

d_{XRD} – theoretical density of the sample obtained from XRD analysis, g cm⁻³,

m – a mass of the sample, g.

5.3.2. Thermoelectric power

The thermoelectric power of Pr005 material was measured using the same sample as for the 4DC conductivity studies. Tests were also done in the flow of Ar, air, and O₂ (20 ml min⁻¹), in the temperature range from 50 °C to 1000 °C. Data were collected during the 2nd cycle upon cooling (2 °C min⁻¹). The temperature gradient (approx. 10 °C across a 7.56 mm long sample) was maintained by appropriately moving the Probostat holder off the furnace center. Data were collected with Keithley 2000 multimeter and Omega2 software. Voltage was measured using attached Pt electrodes. To evaluate thermoelectric power (Seebeck coefficient, Equation 5.14), the recorded thermoelectric voltage was divided by the temperature gradient, with no additional corrections done. The data obtained in this experiment are treated only as qualitative, not as quantitative, and thus no measurement error was calculated.

$$S = -\frac{\Delta V}{\Delta T} \quad (\text{Equation 5.14})$$

where: S – Seebeck coefficient, ΔV – thermoelectric voltage, and ΔT – temperature difference along the measured sample.

5.4. Microstructural studies

5.4.1. Electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Evaluation of the morphology of the studied powders at the microscopic scale was conducted using a JEOL JSM-7100F field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray detector (EDS).

To investigate the morphology of the Nd005 powders after syntheses varying with the final annealing step (see chapter 8), Phenom XL Desktop (Thermo Fisher Scientific) SEM equipped with a silicon drift detector was used. The same SEM was utilized to examine the pellets after electrical measurements (see chapter 9). Samples were reduced ($\delta = 0$) in argon at 1000 °C before the experiment.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was carried out on FEI Tecnai TF20 X-TWIN (FEG) microscope, with 200 kV accelerating voltage. Samples were prepared by drop-casting on carbon-coated copper TEM grids. Before the casting, the investigated powders were dispersed in isopropanol with ultrasonication conducted for 10 min [1]. Additional TEM measurements were conducted on a JEOL JEM-2100 microscope operating also at 200 kV.

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX/EDS)

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was done to prepare elemental maps of samples' surfaces (see chapter 6). Elemental maps were done to check if there are any visible contaminations (i.e. having some regions with higher concentrations of not all elements, meaning inhomogeneity or some unwanted phases like R_2O_3 or Mn_xO_y oxides) JEOL JSM-7100F and Phenom XL Desktop (Thermo Fisher Scientific) microscopes were used. The applied voltage for EDS analysis was 15 kV. The results were analyzed with the use of ProSuite (Thermo Scientific, USA) software.

5.4.2. Specific surface area by Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) theory

For selected samples (varying with chemical composition and preparation route), the specific surface area was calculated using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) isotherm. Experiments were done by the N_2 adsorption method. Before, samples were heated for 2 h at 200 °C in a vacuum to desorb gaseous contaminations from the surface. Gemini V Series (Micromeritics) apparatus was used.

5.5. Evaluation of oxidation state of elements

5.5.1. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

As described in [1], the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were carried out in PHI VersaProbeII Scanning XPS system using monochromatic $AlK\alpha$ (1486.6 eV) X-rays, focused to a 100 μm spot and scanned over the area of 400 $\mu m \times 400 \mu m$. The photoelectron take-off angle was 45 deg, and the pass energy in the analyzer was set to 46.95 eV, to obtain high-energy resolution spectra for the C 1s, O 1s, Pr 3d, Y 3d, Mn 3s, and Mn 2p regions.

A dual beam charge compensation with 7 eV Ar⁺ ions and 1 eV electrons was used to maintain a constant sample surface potential, regardless of the sample conductivity. All XPS spectra were charge-referenced to the unfunctionalized, saturated carbon (C–C) C 1s peak at 284.8 eV. The operating pressure in the analytical chamber was less than 3·10⁻⁹ mbar. Deconvolution of spectra was carried out using PHI MultiPak software. The spectrum background was subtracted using the Shirley method.

5.5.2. X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS)

X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) was used to determine the oxidation state of elements in Pr005 and Nd005 materials (synthesized at 1000 °C for 6 h in Ar) in its reduced ($\delta = 0$) and oxidized ($\delta > 0$) forms. An *ex situ* approach was applied – powdered samples of Pr005 were preoxidized in thermobalance prior to the experiment (**Figure 5.3a**). For seven samples having different amounts of incorporated oxygen (δ from 0.0 to 0.3), the total electron yield (TEY) signal was recorded on Pr, Mn, and O absorption edges at room temperature. Powders were mounted on the sample holders using carbon tape (**Figure 5.3b**). Reference samples were also measured: MnO (Mn²⁺), Mn₂O₃ (Mn³⁺), MnO₂ (Mn⁴⁺), Pr₂O₃ (Pr³⁺), BaPrO₃ (Pr⁴⁺). Measurements were done under high vacuum conditions (10⁻⁸ mbar). Experiments were conducted at the XAS end station at the SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (Krakow, Poland).

Figure 5.3 (a) Oxygen content profile during isothermal oxidation of Pr005, which was applied to prepare samples for *ex situ* XAS experiment. (b) Sample holder used in *ex situ* XAS with four samples mounted with carbon tape on it.

Results and discussion

6. Influence of the mean ionic radius of $Y_{1-x}R_x$ on $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ properties ($R = Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Yb$)

Research presented in this chapter is focused on determining the influence of the ionic radius of $Y_{1-x}R_x$ on the most important parameters of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$, i.e. oxygen storage capacity and reduction and oxidation temperatures. The results from the two author's papers [1,3] are combined to present a more complete view on the $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ series. The main differences between the materials preparation route in both works are summarized in **Table 6.1** – for details, see the *Experimental* section.

Table 6.1 A summary of the main differences between the preparation routes of samples.

Material	Annealing temperature [°C]	Starting chemicals	Work
Yb01	900	nitrate (Y, Mn), oxides (Yb)	[1]
Yb005	950	nitrate (Y, Mn), oxides (Yb)	[1]
YMnO _{3+δ}	900	nitrate (Y, Mn)	[1]
Gd005	950	nitrate (Y, Mn, Gd)	[1]
Sm005	1000	oxides (Y, Mn, Sm)	[3]
Gd01	1050	nitrate (Y, Mn, Gd)	[1]
Nd005	1000	oxides (Y, Mn, Nd)	[3]
Pr005	950	nitrate (Y, Mn, Pr)	[1]
Pr0075	950	nitrate (Y, Mn, Pr)	[1]
Pr01	900	nitrate (Y, Mn, Pr)	[1]

6.1. Crystal structure, phase composition, and morphology after synthesis

Figure 6.1 shows XRD results of as-synthesized materials, ordered ascending with the value of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$. The parent YMnO₃ and most of the materials doped with Yb, Gd, Sm, or Nd (Yb01, Yb005, Gd005, Sm005, Nd005) were easily obtained in the hexagonal $P6_3cm$ structure (Hex0), exhibiting no sign of perovskite-type $Pbnm$ phase. For Gd01 composition, the final annealing at 900 °C for 6 h turned out to be insufficient, and as a result, both hexagonal and perovskite phases were present (4.7 wt.% of $Pbnm$). An increase of the annealing temperature to 1050 °C allowed elimination of the perovskite-type impurity (**Figure 6.2a**).

Figure 6.1(continued on next page)

Figure 6.1 X-ray diffractograms of the as-synthesized materials. Data shown in the 15-70 deg 2θ range for clarity. Presented data based on works [1,3].

In the case of Pr-doped compounds, only Pr005 yielded pure hexagonally-structured material – samples substituted with $x = 0.075$ and $x = 0.1$ of Pr exhibited 8.0 wt.% and 20.0 wt.% of the $Pbnm$ phase, respectively. For Pr01, an increase in the annealing temperature led to the decrease of $Pbnm$ content, but did not allow to eliminate it completely – samples annealed at 1050 °C and 1400 °C still contained 16.0 wt.% and 8.2 wt.%, respectively (**Figure 6.2b**). In the case of Pr0075, an increase in the annealing temperature from 950 °C to 1050 °C did not cause a significant change in the $Pbnm$ content. These results indicate that some critical values of ionic radius $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ is exceeded – in other words, the border between the stability range of the hexagonal phase and the perovskite one, is crossed.

Figure 6.2 XRD data of Gd01 (a) and Pr01 (b) materials after annealing at different temperatures. Weight content and positions of characteristic reflections of the perovskite-type $Pbnm$ phase are indicated. Presented data based on work [1].

A closer look at the XRD data collected for the materials synthesized using Mn-nitrate as a source of Mn (Yb-, Gd-, and Pr-substituted, and parent $YMnO_3$) revealed the presence of several small diffraction peaks, which should not be present in the pure Hex0. Those reflections were identified as originating from the Y_2O_3 -type secondary phase ($Ia-3$ space group, **Figure 6.1**). However, as proven by the author in the mentioned paper [1], the influence of this impurity can be neglected and did not influence the Y/R ratio in the synthesized compounds. Y_2O_3 -type impurity was not present in the samples prepared starting with Mn oxide instead of nitrate (Nd005 and Sm005). Crystallographic data obtained from Rietveld refinements of XRD results are collected in **Table 6.2**.

Table 6.2 Structural parameters and phase composition of as-synthesized materials. Combined data from references [1,3].

Material	Annealing temperature [°C]	$P6_3cm$ (Hex0) parameters			Impurities		Fitting goodness		
		a [Å]	c [Å]	V [Å ³]	Y ₂ O ₃ -type [wt.%]	$Pbnm$ [wt.%]	R _{wp} [%]	R _p [%]	chi ²
Yb01	900	6.1468(2)	11.3761(4)	372.24(3)	3.7(2)	-	2.83	2.22	1.106
Yb005	950	6.1500(1)	11.3746(2)	372.58(2)	2.5(1)	-	2.35	1.68	3.346
YMnO _{3+δ}	900	6.1557(1)	11.3814(3)	373.49(1)	2.9(1)	-	2.88	2.26	1.250
Gd005	950	6.1602(1)	11.3783(3)	373.94(2)	2.6(1)	-	1.98	1.54	1.672
Sm005	1000	6.1604(1)	11.3800(2)	374.01(1)	-	-	2.68	1.98	1.786
Gd01	1050	6.1613(1)	11.3878(2)	374.38(1)	1.5(1)	-	3.26	2.40	1.942
Nd005	1000	6.1661(1)	11.3774(2)	374.62(1)	-	-	2.50	1.93	1.466
Pr005	950	6.1689(1)	11.3720(1)	374.78(1)	1.7(1)	-	2.29	1.64	3.291
Pr0075	950	6.1675(1)	11.3758(1)	374.75(1)	3.3(1)	8.0(1)	2.03	1.51	2.309
Pr01	900	6.1721(1)	11.3743(4)	375.25(2)	3.3(1)	20.0(2)	2.86	2.25	1.104

Structural parameters a , c , and volume V of as-synthesized materials are plotted as a function of the $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius in **Figure 6.3**. As could be anticipated, the unit cell volume, V , of the Hex0 structure depends close to linearly on $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$. This trend is directly connected to changes in the unit cell parameter a – the larger the $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius is, the more the unit cell expands along the a parameter (parallel to the rare earth, or manganese, layers). On the other hand, no simple trend in the c parameter can be seen – changes are irregular, possibly depending on slightly different oxygen contents in the as-synthesized samples. Overall, since only relatively small doping levels were investigated, the observed changes in the a and c parameters are not large. The a parameters (and thus volumes) of Pr0075 and Pr01 samples differ from the linear trend, which is understandable due to the presence of the $Pbnm$ perovskite phase, the amount of which increases with the substitution level.

Figure 6.3 Unit cell parameters (a , c) and volume (V) of Hex0 ($P6_3cm$) phase in as-synthesized materials, plotted as a function of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius. Combined data from references [1,3].

Figure 6.4 shows SEM images collected for samples of as-synthesized Yb005, YMnO₃, Gd005, and Pr005 powders. All examined materials possess similar irregular fine-grained morphology: grains are smaller than 1 μm and tend to aggregate into porous clusters, mostly 1-10 μm in size. Such a morphology is common in the case of materials prepared via the sol-gel route followed by high-temperature annealing. Interestingly, TEM revealed that even after this high-temperature treatment, there is still a nano-sized fraction present in the examined materials – grains smaller than 100 nm were found (**Figure 6.5**). These are in fact primary particles, and aggregates and agglomerates observed in SEM images are the secondary ones.

The BET method was applied to determine the specific surface area of selected samples (**Table 6.3**). Samples having different *R* substitutions, annealed at different temperatures, and synthesized using nitrates or oxides were tested to check if any of these variables influenced the specific surface area significantly and could affect any observed trends in the following TG experiments. Among the mentioned variables, only the annealing temperature has a simple inversely proportional influence on the specific surface area – the higher the temperature, the lower the area. Among the samples annealed at the same temperature (samples 3, 4, 5, 6 at 950 °C and 7, 8, and 9 at 1000 °C) specific surface area seems to be distributed randomly and does not deviate a lot. In general, specific surface areas of all materials are relatively close to each other – values are in the range of 2.7-4.9 m² g⁻¹ with a mean of 3.82 m² g⁻¹. The influence of morphology on the oxygen storage behavior may be neglected.

Table 6.3 Specific surface area of selected materials determined using BET method.

Sample No.	Material	Annealing temperature [°C]	Starting chemicals	Specific surface area [m ² g ⁻¹]
1 ^a	YMnO _{3+δ}	900	nitrates	4.53
2	YMnO _{3+δ}	900	oxides	4.08
3 ^a	Pr005	950	nitrates	3.17
4	Pr005	950	oxides	4.09
5	Nd005	950	oxides	4.13
6	Sm005	950	oxides	4.87
7	Pr005	1000	oxides	3.16
8 ^a	Nd005	1000	oxides	2.75
9 ^a	Sm005	1000	oxides	3.64
mean value				3.82
standard deviation				0.70

^a Samples used for XRD and TG experiments described in this work.

Importantly, as there are no significant differences in morphology between variously substituted Y_{1-x}R_xMnO₃ materials, it should not be the cause of any differences in oxygen storage behavior, if any observed. In such a case, it could be stated with more confidence, that the *r*(Y_{1-x}R_x) radius has a dominant influence on the material's operating parameters. The EDS elemental maps were collected along with the SEM measurements (**Figure 6.6**). Maps show the uniform distribution of all elements, and the secondary Y₂O₃-type phase (detected during XRD studies) could not be observed in the form of any segregation regions.

Figure 6.4 SEM images of as-synthesized materials: Yb005 (a, b), YMnO₃ (c, d), Gd005 (e, f), and Pr005 (g, h) [1]. The white scale bar at the bottom of each image is 10 μm for 1000x magnification (left side), and 1 μm for 10000x magnification (right side).

Figure 6.5 TEM images of as-synthesized Pr005 material. Image **a** taken from [1].

Figure 6.6 EDX elemental maps of as-synthesized materials: Yb005, YMnO_3 , Gd005, and Pr005. Images published in [1].

6.2. Oxygen storage behavior

Figure 6.7 shows the oxygen storage behavior of all studied materials, recorded during TG measurements in O₂ (left side of **Figure 6.7**) and in air (right side), sorted ascending with the value of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius. Type and amount of rare earth R used for substitution in $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ seems to have a strong influence on the oxygen storage characteristics.

Important: if not stated otherwise in the text, the mentioned δ values refer to the oxygen content in the sample at RT, after cooling. Moreover, as mentioned earlier in the *Experimental* section, sample weight at 500 °C in air is taken as a reference point of $\delta = 0$. The initial oxygen content at the beginning of the first 5 °C min⁻¹ cycles shown in **Figure 6.7** is larger than 0 because an additional 5 °C min⁻¹ cycle in air was done before the start of measurement, so the sample was already slightly oxidized.

The parent, i.e. not modified composition, $YMnO_{3+\delta}$, is able to absorb a significant amount of oxygen only in pure O₂ atmosphere and only in the slowest heating/cooling cycle (0.1 °C min⁻¹, **Figure 6.7e**), reaching the maximum of $\delta = 0.23$ (which corresponds to OSC of 1.93 wt.% or 1205 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$). The recorded here OSC is comparable to other reported for $YMnO_{3+\delta}$, in previous literature – some differences can be explained as due to altered preparation conditions [9,147,151,327]. In air (**Figure 6.7f**), even during the slowest cycle, $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ exhibits very low oxygen uptake of $\delta = 0.05$ (0.43 wt.%, 270 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) which excludes this material from practical application in TSA process.

Partial substitution of yttrium with $x = 0.05$ or 0.10 of smaller (than Y) Yb, not only did not enable operation in air atmosphere (**Figure 6.7b,d**) but also worsened performance in O₂ (**Figure 6.7a,c**). In the slowest cycle in O₂, oxygen uptake reached $\delta = 0.17$ (1.41 wt.%, 882 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) and $\delta = 0.15$ (1.19 wt.%, 743 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) for Yb005 and Yb01, respectively.

On the other hand, the introduction of larger rare earths into the yttrium sublattice led to an improvement in oxygen storage characteristics – the larger the $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius, the better, at least up to the limit, where material can exist in its hexagonal polymorph. Substitution with $x = 0.05$ Gd slightly improved oxygen uptake both in O₂ and in air (**Figure 6.7g,h**). The following compositions in series, Sm005 and Gd01, showed a further gradual increment in OSC and not only during the slowest cycle but also during 1 and 5 °C min⁻¹, which becomes promising from the practical point of view (**Figure 6.7i-l**).

The closer to the HEX stability limit, the better performance: Nd005 and Pr005 exhibited highly improved oxygen storage characteristics, the best among studied materials (**Figure 6.7m-p**). In pure O₂ these materials show the highest OSC in 0.1 °C min⁻¹ cycle: $\delta = 0.33$ (2.68 wt.%, 1676 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) and $\delta = 0.31$ (2.55 wt.%, 1592 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) for Nd005 and Pr005, respectively. What is more, these OSMs are able to absorb significant amounts of oxygen also in faster cycles: in the case of Pr005, δ reached 0.30 and 0.21 during 1 and 5 °C min⁻¹ cooling, respectively. Most importantly, these materials are able to operate effectively in air atmosphere. In the slowest cycle in air, Nd005 and Pr005 reached $\delta = 0.28$ (2.32 wt.%, 1453 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$) and $\delta = 0.30$ (2.44 wt.%, 1528 $\mu\text{mol-O g}^{-1}$), respectively. Worth emphasizing, OSC obtained by Pr005 in air accounts for about 96% of its OSC in pure O₂ – this significantly outperforms the previously best-air-operating HEX, $Y_{0.7}Tb_{0.3}MnO_{3+\delta}$, for which this ratio is ~57% [4].

Figure 6.7 (continued on next page)

Figure 6.7 (continued on next page)

Figure 6.7 Oxygen storage characteristics of each studied material recorded using TG in pure O₂ (left side) and in air (right side). Graphs are ordered from top to bottom ascending with the value of the mean ionic radius of Y_{1-x}R_x. In the case of Yb01, YMnO_{3+δ}, and Pr005 samples measured in O₂, 0.1 °C min⁻¹ cycle was recorded in a separate experiment, so the value of δ at the beginning of this cycle is not equal to δ at the end of 1 °C min⁻¹ cycle. Combined data from references [1,3].

The last two materials, Pr0075 and Pr01 (**Figure 6.7q-t**), also exhibited improved performance (compared to parent YMnO_{3+δ}) and were able to operate in air, but the presence of the perovskite-type phase (which does not work at such low temperatures and simply makes up a ballast) decreases their capacity and makes them less competitive compared to Pr005, which also requires lower Pr content (less Pr equals cheaper material).

Maximum OSCs reached during the slowest cooling (0.1 °C min⁻¹) are plotted as a function of the $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius in **Figure 6.8**. As indicated in the above description, materials lying close to the stability limit of the hexagonal phase, tend to reach higher OSCs in O₂, but more importantly, become able to operate in air. Materials being the closest to this border can reach OSC in air almost as high as in pure O₂. The ability to work in air is maintained after exceeding the stability limit of the HEX phase, but the overall OSC is lowered.

There is also some trend in how operating temperatures are influenced by the $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius. For the basic YMnO_{3+δ}, $T_{RED,eq}$ and $T_{OX,eq}$ are 260 °C and 215 °C in O₂, and in air are shifted to 229 °C and 194 °C. For Yb005, having smaller $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$, $T_{RED,eq}$ and $T_{OX,eq}$ are lower: 237 °C and 202 °C in O₂, and 213 °C and 186 °C in air. Contrary, for Pr005 (with larger $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$) $T_{RED,eq}$ and $T_{OX,eq}$ are higher: 284 °C and 270 °C in O₂, and 256 °C and 230 °C in air. Generally, the larger the radius, the higher $T_{RED,eq}$ and $T_{OX,eq}$ are (**Figure 6.9**). However, this trend seems not to be so strong and might be influenced by other factors (e.g. preparation

route). Nonetheless, as a first approximation, it can be stated that if the hexagonal OSM is to be modified to work at higher temperatures, its $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius should be increased.

What is also important, the trend is preserved both in O_2 and in air atmosphere. In the atmosphere with lower p_{O_2} (i.e. air), $T_{RED,eq}$ and $T_{OX,eq}$ are shifted towards lower values. In other words, the oxidized phase can be stable up to higher temperatures if the chemical potential of O_2 (p_{O_2}) in the surrounding gas is adequately higher. The practical consequence of this is the possibility of application of HEX in high-temperature PSA, not only TSA.

Figure 6.8 OSC in O_2 and in air recorded in the slowest ($0.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) cycle (bottom) and their ratio in % (top) plotted as a function of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius. Combined data from references [1,3].

Figure 6.9 Characteristic $T_{RED,eq}$ and $T_{OX,eq}$ temperatures in O_2 (a) and in air (b) plotted as a function of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius. Combined data from references [1,3].

Among the studied substitutions, Pr is the one that relatively easily can obtain either a +3, or +4 oxidation state. Thus, it could introduce additional redox couple (Pr^{3+}/Pr^{4+}) into $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ material, affecting the oxygen capture and release process. To verify the possible presence of the Pr^{3+}/Pr^{4+} couple and confirm (or not) that the larger ionic radius is the cause of

the improved performance of Pr005, XAS and XPS techniques were applied. For both XPS and XAS, Pr005 in its reduced ($\delta = 0$) and oxidized forms ($\delta > 0$) was examined to check the oxidation state of Mn and Pr cations.

Figure 6.10a shows the X-ray photoelectron spectra in the Mn 3s range. The magnitude of the multiplet splitting of the Mn 3s peak can be used to determine the Mn oxidation state. The split of 5.5 eV is characteristic for Mn_2O_3 (Mn^{3+}), while 4.8 eV for MnO_2 (Mn^{4+}) [400–402]. Analysis revealed that the multiplet splitting is equal to 5.6, 5.2, and 5.1 eV for the reduced, air-oxidized, and O_2 -oxidized samples, respectively [1]. This indicates that the oxidation state of Mn changes from close to Mn^{3+} for the reduced sample, to mixed $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$ for the oxidized one, which agrees with what is known in the literature about charge compensation during the oxidation of HEX OSMs. **Figure 6.10b** shows the X-ray photoelectron spectra in the Pr $3d_{5/2}$ range. For each oxygen content, the spectrum can be fitted with two components, both indicating that Pr remains on a single, +3 oxidation state [403].

Figure 6.10 XPS spectra in the Mn 3s (a) and Pr $3d_{5/2}$ (b) range, observed for Pr005 material in its reduced ($\delta = 0$), air-oxidized, and O_2 -oxidized forms. Based on [1].

Figure 6.11 shows the results of XAS experiments. Seven samples of Pr005 having different oxygen content (δ equal to 0.00, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.25, and 0.30) were examined. Spectra near the Mn absorption edge are collected in **Figure 6.11c**. Compared to the reference X-ray absorption spectra (**Figure 6.11a**) of Mn_2O_3 (Mn^{3+}) and MnO_2 (Mn^{4+}), it can be clearly seen that for Pr005 samples having higher oxygen content (δ), the spectrum shape is closer to the one of MnO_2 , while for samples with lower δ it becomes similar to the spectrum of Mn_2O_3 . This is also in agreement with the XPS measurements and literature data. For every oxygen content, Pr remained in a +3 oxidation state (**Figure 6.11b,d**). Thus, the presence of $\text{Pr}^{3+}/\text{Pr}^{4+}$ redox couple is excluded and the improvement of Pr005 oxygen storage performance can be related to its large $r(\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x)$ radius with more certainty.

Figure 6.11 X-ray absorption spectra of Pr005 samples having different oxygen content (δ from 0.0 to 0.3) near Mn (c) and Pr (d) absorption edges. Arrows in (c) indicate the direction of peaks evolution from $\delta = 0.3$ to 0.0. Spectra of reference samples are shown in a (Mn_2O_3 , MnO_2) and b (Pr_2O_3 , BaPrO_3).

The phase composition and crystal structure of all materials after TG measurements (i.e. after $0.1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ cooling in air and O_2) were examined using XRD. Diffractograms of selected O_2 -oxidized and air-oxidized samples (Yb005, $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Pr005, and Pr01) are presented in **Figure 6.12**. Results of all Rietveld refinements are collected in **Table 6.4**. In general, practically all oxidized samples are multi-phase. Materials having lower oxygen content (e.g. air-oxidized Yb01, Yb005, or $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$) contain mostly the basic Hex0 phase with some addition of the Hex1 phase (ca. 7-12 wt.%). The evidence of Hex1 presence in those samples are the reflections appearing near 2θ angle of 21.2 and 32.3 deg (**Figure 6.12b,d**). For the same compositions but oxidized in O_2 (thus having higher oxygen content, δ), Hex1 oxidized phase is much more evident, with higher intensity of reflections at 21.2 and 32.3 deg (**Figure 6.12a,c**). It can be also noticed that the Hex0 reflection at 29.0 deg becomes less intense and 28.8 deg Hex1 reflection rises in exchange. Generally, the higher δ observed in TG experiments, the more Hex0 is transformed to the Hex1 phase (**Table 6.4**). In the materials with the highest oxygen content, like Pr005, characteristic reflections of the Hex0 (e.g. at 22.9 deg) phase cannot be distinguished anymore (**Figure 6.12g,h**). However, for several highly-oxidized samples, a widening of the first main reflection of the Hex1 phase (28.8 reflection widened near 29.0) can be seen (**Figure 6.12e,f**). This can indicate the presence of either the Hex0 or Hex2 phase. In the case, where the content of Hex0 or Hex2 is low (e.g. below 15 wt.%) and in the dominant presence of the Hex1 phase, those two are practically not distinguishable. In those cases, if including Hex0, Hex2, or both phases led to reasonably better refinement quality, the respective phases were considered as present. For Pr-containing materials, including Hex2 improved the quality of Rietveld refinements. Because it is hard to unambiguously tell if there is any Hex2 present or not, δ is calculated from XRD results by multiplying the weight content of only the Hex1 phase and its oxygen excess (taken as 0.29, as typically reported – see chapter 3 for details). Such XRD-calculated δ stays in reasonably good accordance with the TG results but is slightly lower (**Table 6.5**). This might indicate, that in fact there is some small amount of Hex2 phase present.

What is also important, in the samples where Y_2O_3 -type or perovskite-type impurities were present after synthesis, their content and structural parameters are practically not changed after oxidation during TG measurements. Therefore, it confirms that those phases do not affect the oxygen storage performance of studied materials.

Figure 6.12 (continued on next page)

Figure 6.12 Oxygen storage characteristics of each studied material recorded using TG in pure O₂ (left side) and in air (right side). Graphs are ordered from top to bottom ascending with the value of the mean ionic radius of Y_{1-x}R_x. Data from references [1,3].

Table 6.4 Phase composition and structural parameters of the studied materials after TG experiments (i.e. after 0.1 °C min⁻¹ cooling) in air and in O₂. The remaining 2-4 wt.%, adding up to the total 100 wt.%, corresponds to the secondary Y₂O₃-type phase. Unit cell parameters (*a*, *b*, *c*) are given in Å, and unit cell volume (*V*) in Å³. Combined data from references [1,3].

Material	Conditions	<i>P63cm</i> (Hex0)	<i>R3c</i> (Hex1)	<i>Pca21</i> (Hex2)	<i>Pbnm</i> (perovskite-type)
Yb01	air-oxidized	wt.% = 88.9(1)	wt.% = 7.3(2)		
	<i>R</i> _{wp} = 2.66	<i>a</i> = 6.1462(1)	<i>a</i> = 6.1918(6)		
	<i>R</i> _p = 1.98	<i>c</i> = 11.3752(2)	<i>c</i> = 33.3819(61)		
	chi ² = 3.600	<i>V</i> = 372.14(1)	<i>V</i> = 1108.34(22)		
O ₂ -oxidized	wt.% = 37.1(3)	wt.% = 59.5(2)			
	<i>R</i> _{wp} = 3.33	<i>a</i> = 6.1478(3)	<i>a</i> = 6.2101(4)		
	<i>R</i> _p = 2.61	<i>c</i> = 11.3783(9)	<i>c</i> = 33.3554(27)		
	chi ² = 1.313	<i>V</i> = 372.43(5)	<i>V</i> = 1114.03(17)		
Yb005	air-oxidized	wt.% = 87.9(1)	wt.% = 9.3(2)		
	<i>R</i> _{wp} = 2.33	<i>a</i> = 6.1485(1)	<i>a</i> = 6.1947(5)		
	<i>R</i> _p = 1.75	<i>c</i> = 11.3769(2)	<i>c</i> = 33.3214(46)		
	chi ² = 3.200	<i>V</i> = 372.47(1)	<i>V</i> = 1107.38(18)		
O ₂ -oxidized	wt.% = 52.7(2)	wt.% = 44.7(2)			
	<i>R</i> _{wp} = 3.31	<i>a</i> = 6.1485(2)	<i>a</i> = 6.1923(2)		
	<i>R</i> _p = 2.31	<i>c</i> = 11.3784(4)	<i>c</i> = 33.4831(19)		
	chi ² = 5.970	<i>V</i> = 372.52(3)	<i>V</i> = 1111.89(10)		
YMnO _{3+δ}	air-oxidized	wt.% = 85.1(1)	wt.% = 12.0(1)		
	<i>R</i> _{wp} = 2.34	<i>a</i> = 6.1529(1)	<i>a</i> = 6.2031(4)		
	<i>R</i> _p = 1.83	<i>c</i> = 11.3849(2)	<i>c</i> = 33.3324(44)		
	chi ² = 1.761	<i>V</i> = 373.27(1)	<i>V</i> = 1110.74(19)		
O ₂ -oxidized	wt.% = 30.5(1)	wt.% = 65.4(1)			
	<i>R</i> _{wp} = 3.51	<i>a</i> = 6.1548(2)	<i>a</i> = 6.2052(1)		
	<i>R</i> _p = 2.68	<i>c</i> = 11.3869(7)	<i>c</i> = 33.3436(14)		
	chi ² = 1.497	<i>V</i> = 373.57(3)	<i>V</i> = 1111.86(6)		
Gd005	air-oxidized	wt.% = 76.1(1)	wt.% = 20.5(1)		
	<i>R</i> _{wp} = 2.24	<i>a</i> = 6.1569(1)	<i>a</i> = 6.2078(2)		
	<i>R</i> _p = 1.67	<i>c</i> = 11.3864(2)	<i>c</i> = 33.3503(21)		
	chi ² = 2.913	<i>V</i> = 373.81(1)	<i>V</i> = 1113.02(9)		
O ₂ -oxidized	wt.% = 96.6(1)				
	<i>R</i> _{wp} = 3.53		<i>a</i> = 6.2112(1)		
	<i>R</i> _p = 2.62		<i>c</i> = 33.3356(12)		
	chi ² = 2.329		<i>V</i> = 1113.75(6)		

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Table 6.4 (continued)

Material	Conditions	<i>P6₃cm</i> (Hex0)	<i>R3c</i> (Hex1)	<i>Pca2₁</i> (Hex2)	<i>Pbnm</i> (perovskite-type)
Sm005	air-oxidized	wt.% = 67.6(1) <i>a</i> = 6.1577(1) <i>c</i> = 11.3902(3) <i>V</i> = 374.02(2)	wt.% = 32.4(2) <i>a</i> = 6.2124(2) <i>c</i> = 33.3342(24) <i>V</i> = 1114.12(10)		
	O ₂ -oxidized	wt.% = 5.8(1) <i>a</i> = 6.1392(10) <i>c</i> = 11.4475(35) <i>V</i> = 373.66(15)	wt.% = 94.2(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2172(1) <i>c</i> = 33.3114(10) <i>V</i> = 1115.09(5)		
Gd01	air-oxidized	wt.% = 54.1(1) <i>a</i> = 6.1604(1) <i>c</i> = 11.3924(2) <i>V</i> = 374.43(1)	wt.% = 43.1(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2109(1) <i>c</i> = 33.3258(10) <i>V</i> = 1113.32(5)		
	O ₂ -oxidized		wt.% = 97.3(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2171(1) <i>c</i> = 33.3111(6) <i>V</i> = 1115.04(3)		
Nd005	air-oxidized	wt.% = 13.4(3) <i>a</i> = 6.1670(6) <i>c</i> = 11.3860(17) <i>V</i> = 375.02(7)	wt.% = 86.6(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2142(2) <i>c</i> = 33.3402(15) <i>V</i> = 1114.98(11)		
	O ₂ -oxidized	wt.% = 7.5(1) <i>a</i> = 6.1605(7) <i>c</i> = 11.1808(26) <i>V</i> = 367.48(11)	wt.% = 92.5(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2186(1) <i>c</i> = 33.3204(9) <i>V</i> = 1115.89(4)		
Pr005	air-oxidized		wt.% = 88.8(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2101(1) <i>c</i> = 33.3120(6) <i>V</i> = 1112.56(4)	wt.% = 9.1(2) <i>a</i> = 5.7844(20) <i>b</i> = 11.1859(33) <i>c</i> = 10.8424(33) <i>V</i> = 701.55(26)	
	O ₂ -oxidized		wt.% = 88.9(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2109(1) <i>c</i> = 33.3026(4) <i>V</i> = 1112.56(2)	wt.% = 8.8(1) <i>a</i> = 5.7838(15) <i>b</i> = 11.1921(29) <i>c</i> = 10.8359(27) <i>V</i> = 701.43(31)	
Pr0075	air-oxidized	wt.% = 12.8(2) <i>a</i> = 6.1661(3) <i>c</i> = 11.3875(7) <i>V</i> = 374.96(3)	wt.% = 65.8(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2089(2) <i>c</i> = 33.3236(10) <i>V</i> = 1112.55(7)	wt.% = 9.0(3) <i>a</i> = 5.7852(26) <i>b</i> = 11.1765(53) <i>c</i> = 10.8424(46) <i>V</i> = 701.05(37)	wt.% = 8.6(2) <i>a</i> = 5.3648(9) <i>b</i> = 5.8420(9) <i>c</i> = 7.4783(13) <i>V</i> = 234.38(5)
	O ₂ -oxidized		wt.% = 77.0(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2086(1) <i>c</i> = 33.3155(5) <i>V</i> = 1112.17(2)	wt.% = 10.5(1) <i>a</i> = 5.7898(15) <i>b</i> = 11.2051(31) <i>c</i> = 10.8365(28) <i>V</i> = 703.02(32)	wt.% = 8.9(1) <i>a</i> = 5.3668(7) <i>b</i> = 5.8411(7) <i>c</i> = 7.4708(9) <i>V</i> = 234.19(5)
Pr01	air-oxidized		wt.% = 71.3(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2137(1) <i>c</i> = 33.3141(6) <i>V</i> = 1113.94(3)	wt.% = 5.4(1) <i>a</i> = 5.7211(11) <i>b</i> = 11.2092(15) <i>c</i> = 10.8713(18) <i>V</i> = 697.17(20)	wt.% = 20.3(1) <i>a</i> = 5.3055(6) <i>b</i> = 5.8491(6) <i>c</i> = 7.4476(7) <i>V</i> = 231.11(4)
	O ₂ -oxidized		wt.% = 71.1(1) <i>a</i> = 6.2144(1) <i>c</i> = 33.2967(10) <i>V</i> = 1113.61(4)	wt.% = 6.6(1) <i>a</i> = 5.7686(11) <i>b</i> = 11.2617(16) <i>c</i> = 10.7592(16) <i>V</i> = 698.96(19)	wt.% = 18.1(1) <i>a</i> = 5.3017(11) <i>b</i> = 5.8522(12) <i>c</i> = 7.4629(13) <i>V</i> = 231.55(8)

Table 6.5 Comparison of the amount of absorbed oxygen (δ) derived from TG experiments and calculated based on the weight content of the Hex1 oxidized phase (refined from XRD measurements). Combined data from references [1,3].

Compound	O ₂ -oxidized		air-oxidized	
	δ_{TG}	δ_{XRD}	δ_{TG}	δ_{XRD}
Yb01	0.15	0.17	0.04	0.02
Yb005	0.17	0.13	0.04	0.03
YMnO _{3+δ}	0.23	0.19	0.05	0.03
Gd005	0.30	0.28	0.08	0.06
Sm005	0.31	0.27	0.12	0.09
Gd01	0.30	0.28	0.15	0.12
Nd005	0.33	0.27	0.28	0.25
Pr005	0.31	0.26	0.30	0.26
Pr0075	0.28	0.22	0.23	0.19
Pr01	0.26	0.21	0.24	0.21

Results discussed in this chapter allowed determining the influence of mean ionic radius in rare earth sublattice of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$, $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$, on the oxygen storage behavior of HEX OSMs. Proper manipulation of chemical composition allows to greatly improve material's OSC, enables efficient operation in air atmosphere, and gives the possibility of adjustment of working temperatures. Pr-substituted material, $Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$, turned out to be the most promising in terms of application in O₂ separation from air via the TSA process. Therefore, the following chapter focuses on Pr005 and provides much deeper characteristics of its properties.

7. Extended studies on $Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$

High-temperature structural analysis in air

High-temperature XRD measurements were done for the Pr005 sample, to better investigate structural evolution occurring upon the oxidation process in air (**Figure 7.1**). Measurements were taken every 50 °C on heating and cooling in the RT-500 °C temperature range, starting with the as-synthesized sample. On heating, in the whole temperature range, Pr005 remains single-phased Hex0. Upon heating, unit cell volume V expands linearly, exhibiting moderate TEC on the order of $9.8\text{-}12.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. However, this expansion occurs anisotropically, with the unit cell growing mainly along the parameter a ($\text{TEC} = 15.8\text{-}18.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$), while along the parameter c , the unit cell shrinks only slightly, with TEC an order or two orders of magnitude lower (between -2.1×10^{-6} and $-0.05 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$).

On cooling, Pr005 remains single-phased only at higher temperatures, above 300 °C. Entering the temperature range where oxygen absorption starts (as recorded in TG measurements, **Figure 6.7p**) is followed by the gradual phase transformation from Hex0 to Hex1. The transition from Hex0 to Hex1 is associated with a large anisotropic change of the unit cell dimensions – shrinkage along c direction and growth along a , which in total results in the decrease of unit cell volume with an extreme value of chemical expansion coefficient, ChEC, of $84.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (please note: expansion coefficient in this narrow range is mostly attributed to the chemical expansion with only a negligible influence of thermal expansion, and thus it is denoted here as ChEC for simplicity). What is more, unit cell dimensions of Hex1 largely change in the temperature range where oxygen absorption is the fastest (marked with green background in **Figure 7.1**). Further on cooling, the unit cell of Hex1 shrinks isotropically, with moderate TEC along both a and c direction: 11.0×10^{-6} and $8.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively. On cooling, the remaining Hex0 behaves virtually identically as on heating, excluding the temperature range of the fastest oxygen absorption. In this range, the c parameter slightly grows, indicating the possible introduction of some small amount of interstitial oxygen into the Hex0 structure, before it is able to transform to Hex1.

As mentioned in the previous chapter, highly oxidized ($\delta \approx 0.30$) samples of Pr005 (the ones after 0.1 °C min^{-1} cooling in TG) exhibit a plausible presence of Hex2 in their phase composition, as concluded from XRD analysis (**Figure 6.12e,f**, **Table 6.4**). However, if cooled faster (1 °C min^{-1}) in air, Pr005 absorbs less oxygen, $\delta \approx 0.14$ (**Figure 6.7p**), which makes it less likely for the Hex2 phase to appear. This seems to be the case in this HT-XRD experiment, as the average heating/cooling rate was approx. 0.8 °C min^{-1} , significantly faster than 0.1 °C min^{-1} in TG measurements. Moreover, the way the sample is mounted for HT-XRD makes it less exposed to flowing air than it is during TG – thus, hindering oxygen absorption by the sample and resulting in lower δ . If oxygen content at RT (after cooling) was to be calculated according to the weight content of the Hex1 phase in the sample ($\sim 25.6 \text{ wt.}\%$), it gives δ of approx. 0.07.

Figure 7.1 Temperature evolution of Hex0 and Hex1 structural parameters of Pr005 material in air in RT-500 °C range: *a* parameter (a), normalized *c* parameter (b), and normalized volume (c). Data obtained from Rietveld refinement of HT-XRD results. Thermal and chemical coefficients of thermal expansion are given. Based on [1].

Isothermal structural and thermogravimetric analysis of the oxidation process

The next HT-XRD experiment was the isothermal oxidation of Pr005 in air at 220 °C. In this experiment, the Pr005 sample was firstly annealed inside a diffractometer at 500 °C to obtain reduced ($\delta = 0$) material having Hex0 structure. Then, the sample was rapidly cooled

down to 220 °C and XRD measurements were taken every ~15 min for 25 hours. This experiment was done to further study the mechanism of the oxidation process.

The transformation from the Hex0 to the Hex1 phase starts just after the sample is cooled down to 220 °C and proceeds the fastest in the beginning (**Figure 7.2a**). The most remarkable changes visible in recorded diffractograms are as follows: in Hex0, reflections from planes (0 0 2), (1 0 2), and (1 0 4) decrease in intensity to finally reach a barely detectable level; in Hex1, reflections of (0 0 6), (1 0 -8), (0 0 12), and (2 0 -4) planes appear, with (0 0 12) being the most remarkable; the reflection of (1 1 0) is gradually shifted towards lower 2θ angle upon the Hex0→Hex1 transformation; intensities of (1 1 1) and (0 0 4) Hex0 reflections decrease and are replaced by (1 1 3) and (1 0 10) reflections of Hex1. The same as in the previous HT-XRD experiment, the largest changes of unit cell dimensions emerge from Hex0→Hex1 transformation – increase of a by ~0.04 Å and decrease along c direction by ~0.25 (**Figure 7.2b,c**). In both Hex0 and Hex1 phases, values of a and c fluctuate for the first ~1.5 hours, and then start to increase linearly. This isotropic expansion of both unit cells could mean that after the Hex0→Hex1 proceeded to a certain extent, both phases are being loaded with interstitial oxygen.

As shown in **Figure 7.2d**, Hex0 is already halfway transformed to Hex1 (i.e. conversion extent $\alpha = 0.5$, wt. fraction of Hex1 phase in this case) within less than 2 hours (half-time $t_{1/2}$ of approx. 100 min). This $t_{1/2}$ is close to the time after which the a and c parameters start to increase.

Time dependence of α can be utilized to determine the rate-limiting step of the oxidation process (represented here by Hex0→Hex1 transition). The approach based on works by Hancock and Sharp [398,399] can be implemented, as previously applied by Motohashi et al. and Klimkiewicz et al. [142,145,239]. To do so, $\ln(-\ln(1 - \alpha))$ needs to be plotted as a function of $\ln(t)$ – the slope (m) value of this plot (in the α range from 0.15 to 0.5) is characteristic for a specific group of rate-limiting phenomena (see *Experimental* section and cited works for details). As shown in **Figure 7.2e**, m fitted for HT-XRD data equals ~1.03. Slope m of 1 is characteristic for the reactions which proceed according to the so-called contracting sphere (or contracting volume) model, often denoted as R3 [398,404]. In this type of reaction, the reaction rate is limited by the phase boundary, i.e. the interface between reacting components – in this case, between Pr005 particles and O₂ in surrounding air (**Figure 7.2f**) [142,145,239,398,399]. Therefore, the oxidation rate can be further increased by the morphology refinement, i.e. increasing the reaction interface via improving the specific surface area of HEX (i.e. obtaining smaller grains) [1,3]. Another way to improve the oxidation rate could be increasing the velocity of the reaction interface moving through the particle, which can be achieved by improving the diffusion coefficient of interstitial oxygen in the crystal structure of HEX material.

The analogous isothermal oxidation experiment was done using TG – oxidation time, temperature, and atmosphere were set the same, but instead of diffraction data, weight change was recorded upon oxidation. In the α range of 0.15-0.5, α values derived from both XRD and TG overlap with high conformity (**Figure 7.2d**). The slope m of TG data equals ~0.98, being very close to the one obtained for XRD data, and strongly confirms the proposed conclusion.

Figure 7.2 Results of isothermal (220 °C) HT-XRD oxidation experiment of Pr005 in air. Time dependence of diffraction pattern, a parameter, and c parameter are given in (a), (b), and (c), respectively. Comparison of the time dependence of conversion extent, α , derived from HT-XRD and TG experiments (d), and its linearized form (e) used to calculate slope m (see text for details). Simplified graphical representation of oxidation of Pr005 particle, according to contracting sphere reaction model. Based on [1].

Comparison of powder's morphology before and after oxidation

Figure 7.3 shows the SEM images of Pr005 powder before and after oxidation in O_2 during TG measurements. Generally, the morphology of examined OSM does not visibly deteriorate during cyclic oxidation and reduction. This might be thanks to the relatively low operation temperatures of HEX OSMs, which are too low to allow efficient diffusion of substance, i.e. sintering of particles and decreasing the specific surface area of the material.

Thus, it may be expected that Pr005 can exhibit good stability during long TSA operation and maintain its OSC on a satisfactory level.

Figure 7.3 SEM images of Pr005 sample after synthesis (a, c, e) and after oxidation in O₂ during TG experiments (b, d, f). Images from reference [1].

Near-equilibrium oxygen content as a function of temperature and O₂ partial pressure

Near-equilibrium oxygen content in Pr005 is plotted in **Figure 7.4** as a function of temperature and oxygen partial pressure. It can be seen that for lower p_{O_2} the stability of the reduced ($\delta \approx 0$) phase is shifted towards lower temperatures, which is consistent with the TG measurements described earlier in the previous chapter. In the p_{O_2} range from pure O₂ (1 bar) to air (~ 0.21 bar), there is no significant change in the maximum oxygen content, and the temperature of Hex0 \rightarrow Hex1 transformation decreases only a little. In lower p_{O_2} , the amount of

oxygen absorbed by Pr005 is strongly decreased. This diagram can be a guideline for choosing (at least coarse) the reduction and oxidation conditions (p_{O_2} and T) of a swing cycle. Generally, **Figure 7.4** is an approximate phase diagram of reduced and oxidized phases in Pr005 material, as a function of p_{O_2} and T . In an open system, as considered here, only one phase should be thermodynamically stable at specific p_{O_2} and T conditions – therefore, it might be concluded, that in the intermediate region, where δ is too high for Hex0 phase, and too low for Hex1/Hex2 phase, there is a mixture of oxidized and reduced phases present, and this, in turn, means the phase transformation is kinetically-limited.

Figure 7.4 Near-equilibrium oxygen content in Pr005 material, $3+\delta$, as a function of temperature and O_2 partial pressure [1].

Influence of temperature on oxidation and reduction reactions

Apart from quasi-equilibrium oxidation and reduction temperatures ($T_{OX,eq}$ and $T_{RED,eq}$), other values of T_{OX} and T_{RED} could be possibly applied for operation in TSA. Proper adjustment of operating temperatures could allow tweaking the performance of the TSA process, for example via shortening the duration of absorption and desorption stages or maximizing the amount of oxygen separated in a single swing cycle. Therefore, further TG experiments in air were done to examine the influence of T_{OX} and T_{RED} values on oxygen intake and release characteristics in Pr005. In the case of T_{RED} testing, oxygen content in Pr005 was equilibrated at 230 °C ($T_{OX,eq}$) to ca. $\delta \approx 0.21$ prior to each 30 min reduction at different T_{RED} . For the testing of T_{OX} , the sample was reduced to $\delta \approx 0.01$ at 300 °C prior to each 5-hour oxidation at different T_{OX} . For a detailed description of the experimental procedure, please refer to the *Experimental* section.

As can be seen in **Figure 7.5**, changing T_{OX} or T_{RED} even by 10 °C can have a significant influence on the rate of oxygen intake and release. It needs to be highlighted that the oxidation reaction proceeds much slower than the reduction (compare the time scale of **Figure 7.5a**

and **b**). That means, that in the potential TSA implementation, the oxidation stage will be the one limiting the rate of oxygen separation. The dependence of reduction rate on T_{RED} looks rather simple – larger T_{RED} leads to faster oxygen release (**Figure 7.5a**). This can be explained by the increasing mobility of oxygen ions with temperature. The reduced form of Pr005 (Hex0 phase) is thermodynamically preferred at higher temperatures (at least to 500 °C, **Figure 7.1**) and thus, the reduction reaction is limited only kinetically, but not thermodynamically. As a consequence, the duration of the reduction stage in TSA can be easily shortened by increasing T_{RED} . For example, the reduction from $\delta = 0.21$ to 0.01 can take even as short as 10 min or 5 min, at T_{RED} of 290 and 300 °C, respectively, while at $T_{\text{RED,eq}} = 256$ °C Pr005 managed to reduce only down to $\delta \approx 0.12$ during the whole 30 min measurement.

The dependence of T_{OX} on the oxidation reaction rate is more complex (**Figure 7.5b**). Lowering the temperature moves Pr005 towards the region where oxidized phase Hex1 is thermodynamically favorable, so the material is more prone to oxidation, as the Hex0 wants to transform into Hex1. Despite higher temperatures of 250 and 260 °C allow to reach equilibrium oxygen content relatively quickly, the amount of absorbed oxygen is very low ($\delta \ll 0.05$), suggesting that the material is not yet in the region, where the Hex1 phase is thermodynamically preferred. To enable efficient oxygen absorption, T_{OX} needs to be further decreased. However, while the oxygen affinity of Pr005 increases with the lowering of the temperature, the mobility of oxygen ions decreases, making the kinetics to be rate-limiting. Therefore, there is some optimal value of T_{OX} , where oxidation proceeds the fastest. This T_{OX} should be neither too high (to prevent thermodynamic limitation), nor too low (to prevent kinetic limitation). Among the temperatures studied in this experiment, $T_{\text{OX}} = 220$ °C seems to be the optimum one, as throughout almost the whole 5-hour duration of oxidation, δ is the highest in this case.

Figure 7.5 Results of isothermal reduction (**a**) and oxidation (**b**) of Pr005 at different T_{RED} and T_{OX} [1].

The above-described oxidation and reduction at various temperatures can be presented as a conversion extent, α (**Figure 7.6a,b**). The half-time of the reaction, $t_{1/2}$, can be plotted vs. temperature to provide a quick coarse insight into the reaction behavior (**Figure 7.6c**). In the case of both reduction and oxidation, an intermediate temperature range can be spotted between 240-260 °C, where reaction half-time varies with temperature more intensively than below or above this region, which can indicate that there are some differences in the reaction kinetics (e.g. different activation energy of the process).

To further study the kinetics of oxidation and reduction, the isoconversional method can be applied, according to the Kinetics Committee of the International Confederation for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry [405]. The rate of reaction can be expressed as a function of two variables, temperature (T) and conversion extent (α):

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)f(\alpha) \quad (\text{Equation 7.1})$$

where temperature dependence of the reaction rate constant $k(T)$ is given by Arrhenius equation:

$$k(T) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (\text{Equation 7.2})$$

and the dependence on conversion extent is given by some reaction model equation, $f(\alpha)$. The isoconversional approach states that the reaction rate at a constant conversion extent is the function of temperature only. Substituting $k(T)$ in Equation 7.1 by Equation 7.2 and taking the logarithm gives:

$$\ln \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = -\frac{E_a}{RT} + \ln(Af(\alpha)) \quad (\text{Equation 7.3})$$

According to Equation 7.3, by plotting $\ln \frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ as a function of $\frac{1000}{RT}$ for $\alpha = \text{const.}$, E_a [kJ mol⁻¹] can be determined as a negative value of the slope. Therefore, the isoconversional method allows for determining the activation energy of the process, without knowing the reaction model equation $f(\alpha)$.

As seen in **Figure 7.6**, both reduction and oxidation are the decelerating type of reactions, i.e. their rate is the highest at the beginning ($t = 0$, $\alpha = 0$) and slows down with increasing conversion extent α . In the case of reduction, E_a at a lower conversion extent deviates from the remaining dataset (**Figure 7.6d**). The common issue with the isothermal isoconversional approach is the period at the beginning of conversion, where the temperature is not yet perfectly stabilized, typically up to several minutes [405]. As the reduction reaction occurs at higher temperatures, conversion proceeds faster, and therefore reaction has already proceeded to some extent ($\alpha > 0$) before the temperature stabilizes – the higher temperature, the more this period overlaps. This is the probable cause of the increased $d\alpha/dt$ rate at the beginning of reduction at the highest T_{RED} , leading to the higher slope (E_a). This abnormal increase of reaction rate further disappears with increasing conversion extent, and E_a does not change significantly throughout the rest of the reduction. The average activation energy of reduction (calculated as a mean of E_a values at all α , as previously done in [1,406]) is 82.8 ± 14.1 kJ mol⁻¹ (in the 270-300 °C range) and 140.8 ± 34.6 kJ mol⁻¹ (256-260 °C).

In the case of the oxidation reaction which proceeds much slower than reduction, the temperature stabilization period has a negligible influence on the process. E_a seems to gradually decrease with increasing conversion extent α (**Figure 7.6e**). The average activation energy of oxidation is 15.3 ± 5.2 kJ mol⁻¹ (in the 190-230 °C range) and 121.5 ± 49.0 kJ mol⁻¹ (240-260 °C).

As E_a are calculated as mean values across the wide conversion extent range (α from 0.15 to 0.95), thus they should be only taken as a coarse approximation (see the relatively large error value) and treated qualitatively, not quantitatively. Nevertheless, it is sufficient to clearly notice those three temperature regions where the reactions proceed differently. Especially, this analysis indicates that there is an intermediate temperature range (in the vicinity of $T_{RED,eq}$) where both reactions, oxidation, and reduction, are burdened with a high energy barrier and TSA operating temperatures should not be set in this range.

Figure 7.6 Isothermal reduction (a) and oxidation (b) of Pr005 at different T_{RED} and T_{OX} presented as a conversion extent, half-time of reduction and oxidation reactions performed at different temperatures (c), and $\log(d\alpha/dt)$ plots used in the determination of activation energy of reduction (d) and oxidation (e) reactions via isoconversional method.

Evaluation of Pr005 performance in cyclic TSA process for air separation

The next experiment was to simulate the TSA process using thermogravimetry. Process parameters, i.e. temperatures and durations of reduction and oxidation stages, were chosen according to the previous TG experiments evaluating the oxygen storage behavior of Pr005 at different T_{OX} and T_{RED} . The temperature of $T_{OX} = 220$ °C and duration of $t_{OX} = 30$ min were set for oxidation. For reduction, $T_{RED} = 300$ °C and duration of $t_{RED} = 5$ min were selected. Including the time needed for heating and cooling between T_{OX} and T_{RED} , the total time of a single work cycle was 37 min. The total oxygen content in Pr005 ($3+\delta$) during the first 20 cycles is presented in **Figure 7.7a**. The amount of absorbed and released oxygen by the Pr005 material in each cycle ($\Delta\delta$) and the reversibility of the process (ratio of oxygen released to oxygen captured in a single cycle) are shown in **Figure 7.7b**. During 20 cycles, $\Delta\delta$ drops from the initial 0.0494 to 0.0481 (OSC of ~ 0.41 wt.% and ~ 0.40 wt.%, respectively), which is equal to the total capacity loss of 2.6% (0.13% per cycle, on average). Two additional experiments using another Pr005 sample exhibited a further capacity loss of 2.4–4.8% from the 20th to 100th cycle (0.04–0.06% per cycle). Therefore, it can be stated that Pr005 is a promising candidate for air separation using TSA, as its capacity loss decreases upon cycling (i.e. oxygen storage reversibility increases) and seems to stabilize at some level. This could mean good long-term stability of this material.

Knowing the amount of oxygen separated in a single swing cycle by a given amount of OSM, and the duration of this cycle, OSM's performance can be characterized by how much O_2 can be produced using 1 ton of OSM per day, $m^3 \text{ ton}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$, also called *productivity* [70]. In the case of Pr005 in the above described 37 min cycle, the productivity was calculated to reach approx. $108 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ton}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$. It should be noted that this value could be further improved by a proper tweaking of working parameters. To determine if such productivity is satisfactory, or rather poor, it can be compared to any other OSMs used in swing-type air separation. For example, in the case of an Ag-containing molecular sieve used in adsorptive VPSA for the generation of high-purity O_2 , the productivity of $7 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ton}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ was reported, which gives $168 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ton}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ [70]. Therefore, HEX OSMs might in fact become competitive, especially if further development was done.

Figure 7.7 Oxygen content ($3+\delta$) in Pr005 during TSA experiment (a) and the amount of oxygen stored and released ($\Delta\delta$) in each cycle of TSA experiment (b) [1].

Air separation performance of Pr005 in different operation modes: TSA, PSA, and TPSA

Finally, the oxygen storage performance of Pr005 was examined in three different operation modes: TSA, PSA, and TPSA (**Figure 7.8**). For this TG experiment, a new sample of Pr005 was prepared via a modified synthesis route, therefore its morphology (and thus oxidation/reduction rate) might be altered, compared to previous experiments. Because of that, the new Pr005 powder was tested also in TSA mode, to allow reliable comparison between PSA, TPSA, and TSA. For a detailed description of each measurement, please refer to the *Experimental* section.

Figure 7.8 Comparison of Pr005 cycling performance in three different operation modes: TSA (a), PSA (b), and TPSA (c).

In the case of TSA and TPSA, each cycle lasted 3 hours (150 min oxidation and 30 min reduction), while in PSA it was 5 hours (150 min oxidation and 150 min reduction), due to much slower reduction kinetics. The amount of exchanged oxygen in a single swing cycle, $\Delta\delta$, reached 0.21, 0.20, and 0.24 in TSA, PSA, and TPSA, respectively, which corresponds to OSC of 1.73 wt.%, 1.65 wt.%, and 1.97 wt.%.

Productivity in each operation mode can be estimated using the recorded OSCs together with the duration of a single swing cycle. It needs to be emphasized that in these measurements, parameters of the swing cycle (i.e. time and temperature of redox reactions) were not refined, as the maximization of productivity was not the case, but only the comparison between each operating mode. Therefore, estimated productivities are expected to be not as high as obtained in the previous TSA experiment with optimized parameters (**Figure 7.7**). Among the studied operation modes, PSA gives the worst results, with a productivity of only $55 \text{ m}^3 \text{ t}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$, mainly due to the long duration of the reduction stage. In TSA, reduction proceeds almost immediately with a decrease of δ to ~ 0.03 . TSA productivity is calculated to reach $95 \text{ m}^3 \text{ t}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$, almost twice as much as in PSA. Finally, in the TPSA, the reduction is also rapid, and the oxygen storage characteristic generally looks very similar to the one of TSA, but more oxygen is withdrawn from Pr005 during the reduction stage, resulting in OSM having close to stoichiometric oxygen content ($\delta \approx 0$). This translates into the productivity of TPSA reaching about $106 \text{ m}^3 \text{ t}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$.

Performance of Pr005 in long-term cycling in TPSA mode

Figure 7.9 shows the results of the long-term cycling TPSA experiment. Initially, Pr005 was able to exchange $\delta = 0.093$ of oxygen (0.77 wt.%) per one 37 min swing cycle. Upon cycling, a gradual decrease in capacity was observed, similar to the case of the previous TSA experiment (**Figure 7.7**). At the end of this long-term TPSA cycling, i.e. in the last (230th) cycle, δ was 0.080 (0.66 wt.%). These values translate to a total capacity loss of 14.0%, and an average loss of 0.06% per cycle, which is comparable to the capacity loss observed in the case of TSA cycling.

Figure 7.9 Oxygen content ($3+\delta$) in Pr005 during the long-term TPSA experiment.

The productivity of this particular sample of Pr005 utilized in the TPSA air separation was calculated to be $208 \text{ m}^3 \text{ t}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ in the first cycle, and $179 \text{ m}^3 \text{ t}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ in the last one. Then, such productivity remarkably surpasses the one previously mentioned for the Ag-containing molecular sieve used in VPSA ($168 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ton}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$). Therefore, it makes HEX-based absorptive swing methods even more likely to in fact become a competitive alternative to the conventional O_2 separation from air.

8. Combined chemical and microstructural improvement:

In chapter 7, it was shown that the kinetics of oxidation and reduction reactions in HEX materials are phase boundary-limited. As visualized in the simplified schematic in **Figure 7.2f**, the reaction proceeds from the surface of a particle toward its center. Therefore, the rate of such reaction can be improved in two ways: (1) by increasing the speed with which the reaction interface moves through the particle, and this could be achieved by improving the mobility of oxygen ions in the structure, or (2) by decreasing particle size (i.e. improving specific surface area), so the reaction interface (and thus oxygen ions) has a shorter distance to travel through the particle, which should result in shorter reaction time and improved reaction rate. The (1) is what was implemented in chapter 6 about the influence of $Y_{1-x}R_x$ radius on $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ oxygen storage performance. In the current chapter, approach (2) is studied. Moreover, this is done using Nd005 material, i.e. composition already improved by approach (1).

The phase composition and crystal structure of as-synthesized materials

To obtain samples having different morphology, temperature, and duration of the final annealing during synthesis was modified. Nine variants of Nd005 were prepared – conditions of the final annealing are collected in **Table 8.1**. X-ray diffractograms of as-prepared samples are presented in **Figure 8.1**. Among all the materials, only Nd005-7 and Nd005-9 were obtained as pure single-phase Hex0 ($P6_3cm$). The remaining samples contained significant amounts of impurities – residual oxides of manganese (Mn_3O_4 or MnO) and rare earths ($(Y/Nd)_2O_3$), which apparently did not manage to react with each other at a certain time and temperature conditions during the final annealing step of the synthesis. The least content of the Hex0 phase (70.8 wt.%) was observed in the Nd005-1 sample, which was annealed at the lowest temperature (750 °C) for 1 hour only. What is interesting, for the undoped $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ to be obtained in its hexagonal polymorph, at least 789 °C is needed, according to the calculated phase diagram of the MnO_x - $YO_{1.5}$ system in air [355]. Therefore, either doping with Nd, or synthesis in Ar (i.e. low p_{O_2} atmosphere) allowed to decrease the temperature of hexagonal structure formation to ~750 °C. A much longer annealing time (24 hours instead of 1 hour, Nd005-2 sample) increased the Hex0 content to 87.9 wt.% but was not sufficient to obtain a single-phase hexagonal Nd005. This might suggest that the formation of hexagonal Nd005 is strongly kinetically-limited at as low as 750 °C.

On the other hand, while the final annealing was done in Ar, some of the Mn-oxides could reduce to Mn_3O_4 and MnO , before they reacted with $(Y/Nd)_2O_3$ and as a consequence, there was not enough oxygen available in the system (in both precursor powder and atmosphere) to form $Y_{0.95}Nd_{0.05}MnO_3$. In the case where Y and Nd are in the form of Y_2O_3 and Nd_2O_3 oxides, Mn should be present as at least Mn_2O_3 . An additional Nd005 sample was prepared at 700 °C, but the annealed powder remained a mixture of Y/Nd- and Mn-oxides, with no visible reflections of the $P6_3cm$ phase (**Figure 8.2**).

Table 8.1 Results of the XRD analysis of as-synthesized Nd005 samples after different preparation conditions: phase composition, structural parameters, and mean size of crystallites [3]. Unit cell parameters (a , c) are given in Å, and unit cell volume (V) in Å³.

Sample name	Final annealing conditions (temperature, time, and atmosphere)	Refinement goodness	$P6_3cm$ (Hex0)	Mean crystallites size [nm]	Impurities
Nd005-1	750 °C 1 h Ar	$R_{wp} = 2.01\%$ $R_p = 1.59\%$ $\chi^2 = 1.015$	70.8(1) wt.% $a = 6.1567(1)$ $c = 11.3832(4)$ $V = 373.67(2)$	27.8(2.3)	Y ₂ O ₃ MnO Mn ₃ O ₄
Nd005-2	750 °C 24 h Ar	$R_{wp} = 2.05\%$ $R_p = 1.62\%$ $\chi^2 = 1.007$	87.9(1) wt.% $a = 6.1668(1)$ $c = 11.3796(3)$ $V = 374.79(1)$	37.6(4.2)	Y ₂ O ₃ Mn ₃ O ₄
Nd005-3	800 °C 1 h Ar	$R_{wp} = 2.15\%$ $R_p = 1.69\%$ $\chi^2 = 1.097$	85.5(1) wt.% $a = 6.1667(1)$ $c = 11.3805(2)$ $V = 374.80(1)$	38.6(4.2)	Y ₂ O ₃ MnO
Nd005-4	950 °C 1 h Ar	$R_{wp} = 2.26\%$ $R_p = 1.77\%$ $\chi^2 = 1.218$	85.2(1) wt.% $a = 6.1660(1)$ $c = 11.3869(2)$ $V = 374.92(1)$	57.9(8.0)	Y ₂ O ₃ MnO
Nd005-5	950 °C 6 h Ar	$R_{wp} = 2.34\%$ $R_p = 1.83\%$ $\chi^2 = 1.305$	86.0(1) wt.% $a = 6.1649(1)$ $c = 11.3873(2)$ $V = 374.80(1)$	62.9(9.2)	Y ₂ O ₃ MnO
Nd005-6	950 °C 1 h Ar + 950 °C 6 h Ar	$R_{wp} = 2.34\%$ $R_p = 1.81\%$ $\chi^2 = 1.309$	91.0(1) wt.% $a = 6.1643(1)$ $c = 11.3868(1)$ $V = 374.71(1)$	63.1(9.2)	Y ₂ O ₃ MnO
Nd005-7	950 °C 6 h Ar + 1500 °C 4 h air	$R_{wp} = 3.39\%$ $R_p = 2.43\%$ $\chi^2 = 2.411$	100 wt.% $a = 6.1581(1)$ $c = 11.3893(2)$ $V = 374.05(1)$	81.3(13.8)	none
Nd005-8	1000 °C 1 h Ar	$R_{wp} = 2.51\%$ $R_p = 1.91\%$ $\chi^2 = 1.398$	92.2(1) wt.% $a = 6.1654(1)$ $c = 11.3790(2)$ $V = 374.59(1)$	50.9(6.6)	Y ₂ O ₃ Mn ₃ O ₄
Nd005-9	1000 °C 6 h Ar	$R_{wp} = 2.50\%$ $R_p = 1.93\%$ $\chi^2 = 1.466$	100 wt.% $a = 6.1661(1)$ $c = 11.3774(2)$ $V = 374.62(1)$	47.1(5.8)	none

Increasing the annealing temperature from 750 °C to 800 °C (Nd005-3 sample) resulted in significantly improved Hex0 content (85.3 wt.%), but also caused the growth of crystallites. Further increased of time and temperature up to 6 hours and 950 °C (Nd005-4, Nd005-5) did not lead to higher Hex0 content, but still contributed to a larger mean size of crystallites. Interestingly, subjecting the Nd005-4 sample to additional annealing at 950 °C for 6 h in Ar, visibly improved the Hex0 content up to 91.0 wt.% (Nd005-6). Further increase of temperature to 1000 °C resulted in Hex0 content of 92.2 wt.% after 1 hour and finally 100 wt.% after 6 hours of annealing (samples Nd005-8 and Nd005-9, respectively). Finally, to prepare sample

Nd005-7, powder already annealed at 950 °C for 6 hours in Ar, was subjected to additional annealing at a much higher temperature, 1500 °C for 4 hours in air, to determine the influence of sintering-like conditions on the material's oxygen storage behavior. Such treatment resulted in single-phase (100 wt.% of Hex0) material, but also largely increased the mean crystallites size.

Figure 8.1 X-ray diffractograms of as-synthesized Nd005 samples after different preparation routes [3]. Positions of reflections from main impurities (Y_2O_3 , Mn_3O_4 , MnO) are indicated with dashed vertical lines.

Figure 8.2 X-ray diffractogram of Nd005 sample prepared with final annealing at 700 °C for 1 h in Ar [3]. Reflection positions for Mn_3O_4 and Y_2O_3 are indicated.

Oxygen storage behavior in air

Thermogravimetry was used to examine the oxygen storage performance of all nine Nd005 materials. Each sample was subjected to three heating and cooling cycles in air atmosphere: two fast cycles with a 5 °C min^{-1} heating rate, and the third slower cycle, 1 °C min^{-1} . Recorded oxygen storage characteristics are gathered in **Figure 8.3** and presented (a) as oxygen content, $3+\delta$, in $\text{Y}_{0.95}\text{Nd}_{0.05}\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ (i.e. referred only to the weight content of the main hexagonal phase, calculated according to Equation 5.11), and (b) as an OSC of the whole material (i.e. hexagonal phase and residual oxides) expressed in wt.%. The OSC of the whole material is shown, to give a better view of the practical aspect, i.e. to see if the possible capacity profit coming from improved morphology is not surpassed by the lower content of the main hexagonal phase.

Samples prepared at the lowest temperature, Nd005-1 and Nd005-2 exhibited extraordinary oxygen storage performance. Final OSC during the slower cycle (1 °C min^{-1}) reached 1.05 wt.% ($\delta = 0.181$) and 1.02 wt.% ($\delta = 0.141$) for Nd005-1 and Nd005-2, respectively. What is even more important, these materials were able to work efficiently even during the fast 5 °C min^{-1} cycle, reaching OSC of 0.77 wt.% ($\delta = 0.132$) and 0.68 wt.% ($\delta = 0.094$), respectively. In 5 °C min^{-1} and 1 °C min^{-1} temperature swing experiments in air, these are the highest capacities obtained among all the materials studied in this work (including the series of materials described in chapter 6). Such a large performance improvement makes Nd005-1 and Nd005-2 promising OSMs to be applied for air separation with the TSA process.

Contrary, the sample annealed at 1500 °C (Nd005-7) exhibited the lowest capacity, 0.20 wt.% ($\delta = 0.025$), which is negligible in terms of application for oxygen separation. Therefore, if a HEX material was to be used as an OSM in TSA, it should be in the form of a fine powder, having possibly a large surface area contacting with the surrounding air. It eliminates any designs that would include the absorption bed in a form of, for example, an OSM deposited on the surface of a honeycomb support and sintered to it.

Figure 8.3 Oxygen absorption in differently prepared Nd005 samples during three heating/cooling cycles (two cycles with $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ rate, and the third cycle with $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$) in RT-500 °C range, presented as an oxygen content ($3+\delta$) in the hexagonal phase (a) and as an OSC (wt.%) of the whole sample (including hexagonal phase and impurities) [3].

During the 1st $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating, all samples from Nd005-3 to Nd005-6 and Nd005-1 exhibited weight gain above $\sim 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which exceeds the temperature, where the oxygen absorption by a hexagonal Nd005 is possible in air at ambient pressure (see the TG data in chapter 6). This behavior was observed only in the samples containing residual MnO after synthesis (**Table 8.1**). Therefore, this might be explained by the oxidation of MnO to Mn_3O_4 , and in fact is confirmed with the results of XRD done for samples after TG experiments – diffraction peaks characteristic for MnO disappeared (**Figure 8.4**).

Figure 8.4 X-ray diffraction patterns of as-synthesized and air-oxidized Nd005 samples after two different preparation routes: annealed at $750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (**a**) and $950\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (**b**) for 1 hour (samples Nd005-1 and Nd005-4, respectively) [3]. Positions of characteristic reflections of MnO and Mn_3O_4 impurities are indicated.

Correlation between oxygen storage performance and microstructure of HEX

Figure 8.5 shows SEM images of all nine Nd005 samples in their as-synthesized state. In the case of Nd005-1 and Nd005-2, more submicrometer-sized particles and less of large aggregates can be noticed, as compared to the remaining samples. The morphology is irregular, sharply-shaped grains can be seen, and the surface of larger grains is rugged and uneven. Such a morphology suggests a possibly large specific surface area and is often found in materials prepared by the sol-gel method [407–411]. In other samples, the amount of the smallest fraction is visibly lower, and the surface becomes less irregular. Finally, the sample exposed for the annealing at the highest temperature (Nd005-7, $1500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) consist of large regular grains (mostly larger than $1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) sintered to each other and having a smooth surface. Therefore, the specific surface area of this sample is rather strongly decreased and deteriorated oxygen storage performance can be expected.

Figure 8.5 (continued on next page)

(continued)

Figure 8.5 (continued on next page)

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Figure 8.5 SEM images presenting morphology of as-synthesized Nd005 samples after different preparation routes. Images taken with 1000x (left), 10000x (middle), and 50000x (right) magnifications [3]. Scale bars are 80 μm (left), 8 μm (middle), and 1 μm (right).

Despite it is possible to qualitatively tell the evident difference in morphology for several samples (like Nd005-1, -2, and -7), the obtained SEM images are not sufficient to more precisely determine if there is any relationship between the microstructure and oxygen storage performance. Therefore, another approach was implemented instead. Firstly, the mean crystallite size was calculated for each sample from XRD results, using the Scherrer equation (**Table 8.1**). Secondly, the specific surface area (SSA) was estimated – for approximation, the assumption was made that all n particles are spherical, and their diameter is equal to the mean size of crystallites (τ). With this assumption, it can be derived that:

$$SSA = \frac{A}{m} = \frac{n 4\pi \left(\frac{\tau}{2}\right)^2}{n d \frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{\tau}{2}\right)^3} = \frac{6}{d} \frac{1}{\tau} \Rightarrow SSA \propto \frac{1}{\tau}$$

As all the studied samples are the same compound (Nd005), the density (d) can be considered approximately constant, and therefore, SSA is inversely proportional to the crystallite size. Finally, to explore the influence of the preparation route of Nd005 (and thus its morphology) on oxygen storage characteristics, two parameters were plotted against $1/\tau$ in **Figure 8.6**: (a) maximum oxygen uptake (δ from **Figure 8.3a**) in 1°C min^{-1} cycle, and (b) maximum oxidation rate ($d\delta/dt$) during 5°C min^{-1} cycle. A close to linear trend can be seen in both plots – the smaller crystallites, the more oxygen can be absorbed and the faster oxidation proceeds. Clearly, higher capacity stems from improved oxidation rate, which in turn is caused by reduced particle size, i.e. shortened path that absorbed oxygen needs to diffuse through the bulk of HEX material to reach its not-oxidized fraction. In the case of the Nd005-1, the rate of oxidation improved more than three-fold, compared to Nd005-5 and Nd005-6 samples. This is consistent with the previous works, reporting that oxygen absorption in HEX OSMs is often limited by the morphology of the material [1,4,10,152,327]. The oxidation rate, $d\delta/dt$, might be further increased by making grains even smaller, but only to a certain extent. It might be expected, that at some point the ratio of the surface area to the diameter of particles could be high enough, that the surface exchange reactions became a limiting step (instead of transport of oxygen ions through the bulk), and in such a case, further reducing the grain size would no longer cause an increase in oxidation rate. It also should be pointed out, that the maximum

possible amount of absorbed, δ , is limited from the top to $\delta_{\max} = 0.5$, in the case where all Mn^{3+} has oxidized to Mn^{4+} . Therefore, the trend presented in **Figure 8.6a** would stop after reaching $\delta = 0.5$, or earlier if it was altered by another phenomenon (e.g. entering the possible surface exchange-limiting region).

In general, these results show that the chemical (partial substitution of Y with larger R) and microstructural (lowered annealing temperature) modifications combined can bring significant improvement in oxygen storage behavior in HEX materials.

Figure 8.6 Maximum amount of absorbed oxygen (δ) in $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ cooling (a) and maximum oxidation rate in $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ cooling (b) in air in differently prepared Nd005 samples, plotted as a function of inverse crystallite size (see text for details).

9. Oxygen transport properties

As previously indicated in chapter 2, hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSMs are mixed ionic-electronic conductors. The absorbed oxygen is located on the interstitial sites in Mn-containing layers, resulting in the creation of additional charge carriers, both ionic and electronic. Interstitial oxygen anions, O_i'' migrate through the structure of HEX material via interstitialcy mechanism, only in Mn-containing layers [254,326]. Charge introduced with oxygen is compensated via partial oxidation of Mn^{3+} to Mn^{4+} , thus creating electronic carriers, holes, h^\bullet , and making the HEX material a p-type conductor [254,326]. Electronic conductivity is realized via a small polaron hopping mechanism [250–252,254,326,393].

As the amount of absorbed oxygen (δ) has a direct impact on the charge carriers' concentration, the electrical conductivity of HEX materials is also expected to vary with δ . Results presented in chapter 6 showed that the oxygen absorption behavior of HEXs can be strongly influenced by the partial substitution of Y with other rare earth metals (i.e. modification of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius). Therefore, it is anticipated that HEX materials with different $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ would exhibit differences in their charge transport behavior.

To explore the charge transport properties of selected hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials, the following experiments were done: total electrical conductivity (by pseudo-4-probe DC method) and thermoelectric power measurements. Three materials were selected: Pr005, Nd005, and non-substituted $YMnO_{3+\delta}$. Samples were sintered at 1400 °C for 3 hours in air – for a detailed description of sample preparation, please refer to the *Experimental* section of this work.

9.1. Crystal structure and oxygen absorption of sintered samples

Crystal structure

To confirm if the sintering conditions (specifically: very high temperature connected with air atmosphere) did not affect the crystal structure of materials, XRD analysis was done on as-sintered pellets – recorded X-ray diffractograms are presented in **Figure 9.1**, and results of the Rietveld refinements in **Table 9.1**. All three materials were single-phase, with a $P6_3cm$ space group (Hex0). For materials with larger ionic radius in rare earth sublattice, $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$, increase of unit cell volume was observed. This growth occurs along a direction, with virtually no changes in the c parameter, which is consistent with the previous observation described in chapter 6. Worth to notice, unit cell dimensions in sintered materials are significantly smaller than in the case of as-synthesized powders discussed in chapter 6. From the point of view of electrical conductivity measurements, the relative density of samples is crucial. In the case of obtained samples, only approx. 80% was achieved, which means relatively high porosity. Nevertheless, such samples still can be used for conductivity measurements, but the results have to be corrected by a porosity-related factor (see *Experimental* section for details).

Figure 9.1 X-ray diffractograms of the studied materials ($\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Nd005, and Pr005) after sintering at 1400 °C for 3 hours in air. Crystallographic planes corresponding to positions of selected reflection peaks of the $P6_3cm$ (Hex0) phase are indicated in brackets. Based on [2].

Table 9.1 Refined unit cell parameters and volume of $P6_3cm$ phase in the studied materials ($\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Nd005, and Pr005) after sintering at 1400 °C for 3 hours in air. Theoretical (obtained in Rietveld refinement) and relative density are also given. Based on [2].

Material	$P6_3cm$ (Hex0) parameters			Density:		Fitting goodness		
	a [Å]	c [Å]	V [Å ³]	theoretical [g cm ⁻³]	relative [%]	R_{wp} [%]	R_p [%]	χ^2
$\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$	6.1447(1)	11.3830(2)	372.22(1)	5.135	79.5	3.50	2.36	3.003
Nd005	6.1568(1)	11.3819(2)	373.64(1)	5.189	80.0	3.40	2.33	2.792
Pr005	6.1582(1)	11.3826(2)	373.84(1)	5.182	82.1	3.40	2.35	2.731

Oxygen absorption

As found out earlier in chapters 7 and 8, the oxidation rate is strongly affected by the morphology of the sample. Thus, it might be expected that materials used for conductivity measurements (i.e. sintered pellets) would absorb significantly less oxygen during the experiment, compared to powdered samples. To allow a better understanding of transport properties experiments, TG analysis was done using fragments of the same sintered pellets as used for conductivity and thermoelectric measurements, and the same heating/cooling rate was applied. It was done to ensure a possibly reliable determination of oxygen content (and therefore, the number of charge carriers) in samples during conductivity/thermoelectric measurements.

As presented in **Figure 9.2**, the magnitude of oxygen excess, δ , increases for $\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ materials with increasing values of $r(\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x)$ radius ($\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta} \rightarrow \text{Nd005} \rightarrow \text{Pr005}$), and with increasing oxygen concentration in the atmosphere ($\text{Ar} \rightarrow \text{air} \rightarrow \text{O}_2$), which is consistent with the results described in chapter 6. **Table 9.2** contains the maximum values of oxygen excess (i.e. after cooling down to RT) in each material in air and O_2 – results obtained for sintered pellets in 2°C min^{-1} cooling are compared to data for powder samples from

chapter 6 ($5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$). As anticipated, oxidation in sintered samples proceeded to significantly lower values of δ , compared to powders even though the powders were cooled faster. This stays in accordance with findings described in chapters 7 and 8 regarding the influence of surface area on oxygen absorption rate.

Figure 9.2 Oxygen absorption behavior of the studied materials ($\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Nd005, and Pr005) after sintering at $1400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 hours in air. Presented data was recorded on $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ cooling in Ar, air, and O_2 flow. Based on [2].

Table 9.2 Comparison of the maximum oxygen excess δ obtained for the studied materials ($\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Nd005, and Pr005) in two different forms – sintered pellets and fine powders. Data given for air and O_2 atmosphere. Based on [1–3].

Material	Atmosphere	Oxygen excess, δ , in:	
		sintered pellets, $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ cooling	powders, $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ cooling
$\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$	air	0.003	0.019
	O_2	0.006	0.030
Nd005	air	0.010	0.049
	O_2	0.029	0.153
Pr005	air	0.015	0.062
	O_2	0.042	0.212

9.2. Electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power in different atmospheres

Conductivity

Figure 9.3 shows the results of direct current conductivity measurements – data collected on $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ cooling are plotted as a function of inverse temperature in Arrhenius-type coordinates. At the high-temperature region ($700\text{--}1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), conductivity is virtually independent either of the material composition, or oxygen content in the atmosphere. Example values of conductivity at $800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Nd005, and Pr005 in Ar are $6.29 \times 10^{-2}\text{ S cm}^{-1}$, $6.35 \times 10^{-2}\text{ S cm}^{-1}$, and $6.98 \times 10^{-2}\text{ S cm}^{-1}$, respectively, while in air are $6.76 \times 10^{-2}\text{ S cm}^{-1}$, $5.99 \times 10^{-2}\text{ S cm}^{-1}$, and $7.00 \times 10^{-2}\text{ S cm}^{-1}$. In this high-temperature range, also the activation energy of conductivity is the highest (**Table 9.3**, **Figure 9.3**). Moreover, E_a seems to slightly decrease with increasing O_2 content in the atmosphere – in the case of Pr005, E_a is 0.90 eV, 0.86 eV, and 0.83 eV in Ar, air, and O_2 , respectively.

Figure 9.3 Temperature dependence of the conductivity of the studied materials (plotted in Arrhenius-type coordinates) recorded on $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ cooling in Ar (a), air (b), and O_2 (c). A comparison of Pr005 conductivity in all three atmospheres is given in (d). Small artifacts observed between 10^{-3} and 10^{-2} $\log(\sigma)$ range are caused by the equipment switching between two measurement ranges. Based on [2].

Table 9.3 Activation energy of the total electrical conductivity of Pr005 in O_2 , air, and Ar, divided into low-, intermediate-, and high-temperature regions [2].

Atmosphere	Temperature range [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]		
	Activation energy, E_a [eV]		
O_2	700-1000	300-400	50-200
	0.83(1)	0.05(1)	0.47(1)
air	700-1000	300-400	50-200
	0.86(1)	0.15(1)	0.54(1)
Ar	400-1000	300-400	150-300
	0.90(1)	0.72(1)	0.69(1)

Due to the TG equipment limitations (max. operating temperature of 500 °C), oxygen content in examined materials was not determined at high-temperature region. Nevertheless, near oxygen-stoichiometric composition ($\delta \approx 0$) is expected according to the previous reports, with only slight fluctuation upon further temperature increase [254,370]. In [254], authors hypothesized, that at higher temperatures a simultaneous oxidation and reduction (i.e. charge disproportionation) of Mn^{3+} occurs ($2\text{Mn}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{4+} + \text{Mn}^{2+}$), leaving an effective charge of Mn at +3, and therefore not affecting oxygen content. The extra energy needed for this manganese reduction and oxidation might be the cause of an increase in activation energy. Phase transformation might be expected at around 950-1000 °C between aristotype non-distorted high-temperature $P6_3/mmc$ (HexHT) and “standard” low-temperature $P6_3cm$ (Hex0) [369,412]. However, if it occurs here, it has no impact on conductivity characteristics. Further on cooling in Ar, conductivity does not vary from the linear trend significantly. However, the highest values are observed for undoped $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$. A possible explanation might be the difference in unit cell parameter a , which is smaller for $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ than for Nd005 and Pr005 (**Table 9.1**), and might improve the degree of Mn and O orbitals overlapping in Mn layers, thus facilitating charge hopping [2]. Exemplary conductivity values at 200 °C in Ar are $4.16 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, $2.70 \times 10^{-7} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, and $1.47 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Nd005, and Pr005, respectively.

Another, isosymmetric (i.e. from $P6_3cm$ to $P6_3cm$) structural phase transformation was reported for YMnO_3 to occur in the vicinity of 650 °C [369] and involves sharp displacement of equatorial oxygen in MnO_5 bipyramids along c direction, which increases the tilt of MnO_5 . This transition is suspected to be related to the hybridization of orbitals of Y and apical O in MnO_5 bipyramids, and several papers reported anomalies of physical properties in this temperature region [369,412]. In fact, the observed here conductivity-temperature characteristics of $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Nd005, and Pr005 (**Figure 9.3**) start to deviate from linearity around 600-700 °C. However, this deviation is smooth, not sharp as might be expected from this sudden phase transition. Secondly, conductivity deviation is observed in O_2 -rich atmospheres (air, O_2), and practically not visible in the inert one (Ar). These two observations might suggest that the deviation in conductivity characteristics is not significantly influenced by this isosymmetric phase transition (if it occurs at all), but is rather related to an increasing charge carriers concentration, i.e. non-zero oxygen excess in materials, $\delta > 0$. Possibly, some trace amount of oxygen is being absorbed (i.e. there is an oxygen nonstoichiometry present) even at such high temperatures, and therefore this interstitial oxygen ions and Mn-related electronic holes are responsible for this deviation. Importantly, it needs to be remembered, that despite the assumption of oxygen nonstoichiometry being $\delta = 0$ at 500 °C (see *Experimental* section) is accurate enough in terms of oxygen storage properties, the real δ may slightly differ from 0, i.e. there is a certain amount of interstitial oxygens (or oxygen vacancies) present in the structure. The concentration of these oxygen defects might even be barely observable using thermogravimetry (thus negligible from an oxygen storage capacity point of view) but may potentially have a significant influence on charge transport. Such an explanation would be consistent with what is observed for $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$: at lower temperatures, its conductivity in air is greatly increased compared to the conductivity in Ar, even though the amount of incorporated oxygen is very low. For example, δ of less than 0.003, as observed in TG experiments (**Figure**

9.2), gave a rise in conductivity by almost two orders of magnitude from $4.16 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ to $3.42 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (**Figure 9.3**).

Further on cooling in O_2 -containing atmospheres (air, O_2), in the intermediate-temperature range of $500\text{-}300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, conductivity does not decrease significantly, compared to the remaining temperatures. A larger change in σ value is observed for pure $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ than for Pr005 and Nd005 – conductivity characteristics of the latter two materials remain nearly flat, resulting in highly reduced activation energy (e.g. 0.15 eV in air, and 0.05 eV in O_2 , in the case of Pr005). This intermediate-temperature conductivity behavior might resemble a saturation region in extrinsic semiconductors, but it is not the case here, as the charge carrier concentration changes with temperature (increases on cooling due to oxygen absorption). In this case, the decrease in carriers' mobility is effectively compensated by the increase in charge carriers' concentration [326], and thus σ does not vary significantly in this range. A larger conductivity decrease in $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ is therefore explained due to its slower oxygen absorption (i.e. lower gain of charge carrier concentration).

In the low-temperature range (i.e. below $\sim 300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) in air and in O_2 , parent $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ has the lowest conductivity among all three materials. What is more, it exhibits a slightly steeper slope in Arrhenius-type coordinates, meaning higher activation energy (e.g. 0.59 eV for $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ vs. 0.54 eV for Pr005, both in air). Such behavior might be the result of two factors. Firstly, the ionic component of conductivity (via interstitial oxygen anions, O_i'') is improved in materials with larger $r(\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x)$ radius, plausibly thanks to enlarged unit cell dimensions along a direction. As the oxygen transport in hexagonal $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ -based materials is realized in Mn layers, parallel to the a direction [326,336], larger a parameter (resulting in increased free volume in Mn layers) might enlarge the bottleneck for interstitial oxygen hopping, improving the mobility of O_i'' and decreasing activation energy. Secondly, total (ionic and electronic) conductivity is improved due to a higher concentration of charge carriers (O_i'' and h^*) in materials with larger $r(\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{R}_x)$, thanks to better oxygen absorption (higher δ). Nonetheless, it needs to be emphasized that the difference in conductivity value between $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ and Nd005/Pr005 is not very significant – at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air, σ reaches $3.42 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, $5.68 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, and $4.57 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$, Nd005, and Pr005, respectively. This gap is broader in the O_2 atmosphere, but only a bit: $5.67 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ versus $1.42 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ and $1.51 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for Nd005 and Pr005. This is consistent with the prior conclusion, that even a very low amount of interstitial oxygen gives a large improvement in conductivity. Moreover, it seems like $\log(\sigma)$ is not linearly proportional to the magnitude of oxygen nonstoichiometry. Indeed, further oxidation leads to further conductivity improvement, but not as prominent as might be expected – which can be concluded by comparing conductivity values (**Figure 9.3**) with the amount of absorbed oxygen (**Figure 9.2**, **Table 9.2**).

In **Figure 9.3d**, there are compared conductivity characteristics of Pr005 in three different atmospheres – Ar, air, and O_2 . σ of Pr005 shifts towards higher values with increasing p_{O_2} , which is also related to the larger amount of absorbed oxygen. Exemplary values at $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ are $7.24 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, $1.13 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, and $3.51 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ in Ar, air, and O_2 , respectively, and correspond to oxygen nonstoichiometry of ~ 0.000 , 0.010 , and 0.026 . These results are in accordance with the previous conclusions, that further oxidation does not bring significant improvement in conductivity and the largest jump of σ is caused by the presence of even a small amount of interstitial oxygen.

Figure 9.4 Isothermal conductivity relaxation of Pr005 at 250 °C after atmosphere change from Ar to air. For reference, conductivity values recorded at 250 °C in Ar and in air during non-isothermal experiments (on 2 °C min⁻¹ cooling) are indicated. Based on [2].

Figure 9.4 presents the results of 25-hour conductivity relaxation experiment, performed isothermally at 250 °C using a Pr005 sample. After 20 hours of equilibration of σ in Ar, gas was switched to air and kept for approx. 25 hours. The equilibrium value of σ could not be reached within 25-hour relaxation, which is not surprising, as the specimen is a sintered sample (i.e. it has a low specific surface area) and, as observed in chapters 7 and 8, the rate of oxygen absorption is phase boundary-limited (therefore SSA-limited as well). Importantly, the highest gain in conductivity is observed within the first ca. 1 hour of relaxation ($\log(\sigma)$ is increased by one order of magnitude in less than 10 min), which is followed by a much slower continuous increase – this observation also stays in agreement with the earlier statement, that the major conductivity change is observed in the beginning of oxidation, where the content of interstitial oxygen, δ , despite being still low, is already a non-zero value.

Worth to mention that such a large conductivity change in the studied $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials, induced with O_2 presence in the atmosphere, makes HEXs potential candidates for application as oxygen sensors. Such a sensor could operate at relatively low temperatures, e.g. 250 °C, which is remarkably lower compared to the conventional zirconia probes, operating even at 700 °C [413]. The low operating temperature might allow the HEX-based O_2 sensor to work in harsh environments (e.g. in gases containing H_2 , CO , H_2O , etc.) without degradation of the sensor's material.

Thermoelectric properties

As the Seebeck coefficient is sensitive to the nature of charge carriers near the Fermi level, conductivity results are supplemented by measurements of thermoelectric power, conducted in analogous conditions, i.e. heating/cooling rate, the same sample was used, etc. Seebeck coefficient (S) of Pr005 as a function of temperature in three atmospheres with different p_{O_2} (Ar, air, and O_2) is presented in **Figure 9.5**. The shape of Seebeck coefficient temperature characteristics in each atmosphere is generally very similar but shifted towards lower temperatures for gases with lower p_{O_2} . In the case of O_2 -rich gases, air, and O_2 , the thermoelectric power of Pr005 remains positive in the whole range of studied temperatures. Starting from moderate values of ca. 100-200 $\mu V K^{-1}$ at 1000 $^{\circ}C$, S increases rapidly on cooling, even exceeding 1500 $\mu V K^{-1}$. This growth starts to decelerate at the temperature region, where conductivity characteristics in air and O_2 (**Figure 9.3d**) start to deviate from the linear trend, i.e. around 600 $^{\circ}C$. In the 600-350 $^{\circ}C$ range, thermoelectric power does not vary significantly with temperature, and it decreases further on cooling, where the largest oxygen absorption occurs (**Figure 9.2c**). This low-temperature drop of the Seebeck coefficient is more prominent in O_2 than in air, and thus it might be related to the higher amount of introduced interstitial oxygen, δ , i.e. largely increased concentration of charge carriers, O_i'' and h^{\bullet} . The here observed temperature dependence of the thermoelectric power of Pr005 is very similar to the one previously found for $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ in air, which showed a positive sign in the entire temperature range and reached a maximum value around 600 $^{\circ}C$ [268].

A positive sign of the Seebeck coefficient usually means that the dominant charge carriers are positive. Therefore, in the case of here discussed Pr005, electronic holes related to Mn^{4+} are main charge carriers, which is consistent with the previous works reporting the presence of p-type conductivity in undoped $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ [268,326].

Figure 9.5 Temperature dependence of Seebeck coefficient of Pr005 in different atmospheres: Ar, air, and O_2 . Data recorded on $2^{\circ}C min^{-1}$ cooling. Based on [2].

Interestingly, at high temperatures in Ar, thermoelectric power takes a negative sign. The value of S is the lowest at 1000 °C (ca. $-500 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$), gradually increases on cooling to ca. $-100 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$ at around 800 °C, and remains almost constant down to around 550 °C. Further cooling leads to a rapid increase in the Seebeck coefficient, and at 510 °C it changes its sign from negative, to positive. The highest recorded values, recorded at around 300 °C, exceeded $2000 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$ – a further increase would be probably observed, but in the low-temperature range where the sample's resistance becomes extremely high, a readout of thermoelectric voltage became too noisy to be reliable. The same problem of noisy readout was observed in air and O₂, but shifted towards lower temperatures, due to better conductivity in O₂-containing atmospheres. Such values of the Seebeck coefficient are extremely high – it might be expected that they are burdened with a large measurement error, resulting from the non-equilibrium state of the sample. Therefore, the recorded thermoelectric data should be treated as qualitative, not quantitative. However, the magnitude of S is not crucial in determining the dominating type of oxygen carriers – the shape and sign are more significant.

A negative sign of S in Ar at higher temperatures can be caused by the presence of oxygen vacancies, which were reported to be possible in hexagonal $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$, and are more probable to appear at higher temperatures and lower p_{O_2} [414–417]. These oxygen vacancies are compensated by the partial reduction of Mn^{3+} to Mn^{2+} , which effectively acts as electrons, and therefore Pr005 conductivity character changes from p-type to n-type. Alternatively, a negative S could be explained by the mentioned earlier charge disproportionation of Mn^{3+} – electrons corresponding to Mn^{2+} would be dominating charge carriers if they had higher mobility than the electronic holes associated with Mn^{4+} .

Degradation of sintered samples upon high-temperature measurements

The surface of the pellets after being subjected to high-temperature conductivity and thermoelectric measurements are shown in the SEM images in **Figure 9.6**. High porosity (dark spots) can be easily noticed in each sample, which agrees with the low relative density calculated from XRD analysis (given in **Table 9.1**). What is more, numerous cracks are visible – these most probably result from the large chemical expansion and contraction during several cycles of oxygen absorption and release (inevitably occurring in the lower temperature range during measurements of transport properties), as previously observed in HT-XRD experiment (**Figure 7.1**) and discussed in chapter 7. This issue should be addressed in future research, if Pr005 would be considered for certain applications, where it is required in a form of the sintered body, e.g. oxygen permeable membranes or electrodes for SOFCs. Nonetheless, preliminary trials were undertaken to determine Pr005 applicability as an air-electrode for SOFC – results of this assessment are given in Appendix B. The obtained data suggest that the hexagonal $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ mixed ionic-electronic conductors might be of interest in terms of their application as an air-electrode, especially at low (from the SOFC point of view) temperatures (~ 400 °C), where Pr005 exhibited improved electrode polarization resistance.

Figure 9.6 SEM images of the surfaces of samples after conductivity and thermoelectric measurements: $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ (a), Nd005 (b), and Pr005 (c). Pellets were reduced at 1000 °C in Ar prior to SEM measurements. Images taken using 1000x magnification are on the left, and 5000x on the right. Based on [2].

10. HEX-based TSA: Assessment of applicability for O₂ separation from air

10.1. Prototype of HEX-based TSA air separation unit

A prototype of a small-scale air separation unit has been designed and constructed. This ASU is dedicated to operating in TSA mode and utilizing HEX OSMs developed in this work, able to efficiently absorb oxygen from air. To date, this is the first reported proof of concept of HEX-based TSA ASU. The front view of the prototype is shown in **Figure 10.1** and the inside of the process control unit is in **Figure 10.2**.

Figure 10.1 The designed prototype TSA air separation unit – front view. The following components are indicated: (1) Air supply tank, (2) Compressor, (3) O₂ tank, (4) Absorption bed, (5)-(7) Solenoid valves, (A) Temperature controller, (B) Process control unit, and (C) Heating element.

A generic operation principle of the TSA process can be described similarly as previously in chapter 1.4.5. The main difference is that the built prototype is a single-bed unit instead of a two-bed described in chapter 1.4.5.

The absorption bed (4) is filled with OSM. The bed temperature is alternately swung between T_{OX} and T_{RED} , controlled by the temperature controller (A). At T_{OX} , O₂ from air flowing through the bed is absorbed by OSM, while at T_{RED} , O₂ is released from OSM and can be withdrawn from the absorption bed (4) and stored in the O₂ tank (3). A set of solenoid valves (5)-(7) is used to properly direct the gas flow through the equipment during subsequent stages of the work cycle. The process control unit (B) was designed and built to control the valves

according to the real-time process parameters and setpoint parameters (T_{RED} , T_{OX} , t_{OX} , t_{RED}) set manually with the control unit during the startup stage of equipment.

Figure 10.2 The inside view of the process control unit built for the purpose of the prepared TSA prototype. The device consists of: (1) LCD screen, (2) Arduino microcontroller, (3) Compressor relay, (4) Encoder (i.e. *setting knob*), (5) Valve switching board, (6) Thermocouple amplifier, and (7) Power switch.

Some general technical features of the prototype can be named as follows:

- External dimensions of ASU are (approx.) 80 cm × 50 cm × 70 cm (width × depth × height).
- Construction materials are selected to withstand a maximum operating temperature of about 400 °C. In the case of HEX OSMs even 300 °C is sufficient, thus a safe margin is kept.
- The total cost of materials used to build the prototype is ~1000 USD.
- The absorption bed is filled with OSM in a form of fine powder.
- The O₂ production capacity of the prototype can be estimated knowing the productivity of OSM (e.g. 108 m³ t⁻¹ day⁻¹, as calculated in chapter 7. for Pr005 in TSA) and the amount of OSM filling the absorption bed (~50 g in this case). Therefore, a production capacity of ca. 5 liters of oxygen per day can be obtained.

10.2. Estimation of the specific power consumption of HEX-based TSA

An attempt was undertaken to approximately estimate the possible specific power consumption, *SPC*, of O₂ production via TSA process utilizing HEX OSMs. It is done to

determine the competitiveness of air-operating HEX-based TSA in relation to the conventional methods of oxygen production.

In the case of the TSA process, SPC , defined as the energy required to separate a certain amount of O_2 , can be calculated as follows:

$$SPC = \frac{E_{total}}{m_{O_2}}$$

where:

E_{total} – total energy consumption of a single TSA cycle,

m_{O_2} – a mass of O_2 separated in a single TSA cycle.

A simplified expression for total energy consumption can be formulated as:

$$E_{total} \approx C + \Delta H_{REDOX}$$

where:

C – heat capacity, i.e. energy needed to heat the absorption bed of the TSA unit (including OSM, vessel material, etc.) from T_{OX} to T_{RED} , [J],

ΔH_{REDOX} – enthalpy of redox reactions taking place during air separation with TSA (i.e. oxidation and reduction, or absorption and release of oxygen, in other words).

It must be emphasized that the proposed simplified formula for E_{total} does not include several secondary factors like:

- heat lost to the surrounding environment through reactor walls or with gas flowing through the reactor, etc.,
- the energy needed to power the compressor transferring air through the system,
- the heat that might be recovered at certain points of the process,

which altogether might additionally impact the real SPC , either increasing or decreasing it.

The mass of O_2 separated in a single TSA cycle can be easily calculated as:

$$m_{O_2} = \frac{OSC}{100} \cdot m_{OSM}$$

where:

OSC [wt.%] – oxygen storage capacity of the OSM used in the TSA process,

m_{OSM} – a mass of the OSM working in the TSA process.

For the purpose of this simplified SPC estimation, only the oxygen storage material is included in the heat capacity component of E_{total} :

$$C \approx C_{OSM} = m_{OSM} \cdot c_{OSM} \cdot (T_{RED} - T_{OX})$$

where:

c_{OSM} – specific heat capacity of the OSM used in the TSA process.

According to the literature [370], oxygen absorption (oxidation) in hexagonal $YMnO_3$ -type OSMs is an exothermic process, while oxygen release (reduction) is endothermic. Therefore, only the enthalpy of reduction reaction is considered here to contribute in ΔH_{REDOX} :

$$\Delta H_{REDOX} = h_{RED} \cdot n_O = h_{RED} \cdot \frac{OSC}{100} \cdot \frac{m_{OSM}}{M_O}$$

where:

h_{RED} – specific enthalpy of reduction,

n_O – number of moles of atomic oxygen exchanged by OSM in a single TSA cycle,

M_O – a molar mass of atomic oxygen.

Finally, approximated specific power consumption can be calculated as:

$$SPC = \frac{m_{OSM} \cdot c_{OSM} \cdot (T_{RED} - T_{OX}) + h_{RED} \cdot \frac{OSC}{100} \cdot \frac{m_{OSM}}{M_O}}{\frac{OSC}{100} \cdot m_{OSM}}$$

$$= \frac{100 \cdot c_{OSM} \cdot (T_{RED} - T_{OX})}{OSC} + \frac{h_{RED}}{M_O}$$

OSC and redox temperatures in the above equation are taken from this work and other literature for today's state-of-the-art HEX materials. Specific heat capacity of OSM, c_{OSM} , is taken as $620 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which is the value reported in the literature for YMnO_3 material at 500 K [418].

To find the specific enthalpy of the reduction reaction, h_{RED} , differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was employed. Specific enthalpy is obtained as an integral of endothermic peak recorded in the DSC curve – an example is shown in **Figure 10.3** for measurement done with $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating/cooling rate. Enthalpy determined using DSC is expressed as unit energy referring to the mass of Pr005, and it needs to be converted to be referring to the number of moles of atomic oxygen exchanged by Pr005 in a single swing cycle. As the DSC was conducted in the analogous procedure as TG discussed in chapter 6 (heating/cooling rate, air flow), values of δ determined therein can be utilized. Finally, h_{RED} is calculated to be $54.8 \text{ kJ mol}_O^{-1}$. h_{RED} was determined only for Pr005 material and the same value was applied in SPC calculations for other OSMs.

Figure 10.3 DSC curve recorded for Pr005 in air in the RT-400 °C range with $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating and cooling rate.

Table 10.1 contains the results of performed calculations. To have better insight into which factor has a larger impact on the total SPC , values calculated for each component individually (i.e. either heat capacity, C_{OSM} , or redox enthalpy, ΔH_{REDOX}) are also provided.

For the current state-of-the-art HEX OSMs, specific power consumption is estimated to be around 1140 kWh t⁻¹, at best. For comparison, the typical *SPC* of cryogenic distillation of air is in the range of 400-600 kWh t⁻¹, and even ~200 kWh t⁻¹ for modern large-scale plants, as indicated earlier in chapter 1. Consequently, for the TSA to become competitive with conventional O₂ production methods, *SPC* needs to be further decreased. However, this relatively low *SPC* of the cryogenic process comes from many decades of development. Therefore, further improvement of TSA technology could possibly make it a competitive alternative. The *SPC* of TSA estimated in this work does not include any eventual heat recovery during the process, so it can be further improved by a proper design of ASU. As indicated in [370], oxidation in YMnO_{3+δ}-based material is an exothermic process, and thus enthalpy of the oxidation reaction could be utilized. What is more, TSA can produce (at least theoretically) more pure O₂ than PSA, and therefore could replace it in some application fields.

As can be seen in **Table 10.1**, the enthalpy of the reduction reaction has a dominating contribution to the total magnitude of *SPC*. The heat capacity of OSM can also be a significant factor, especially if the difference between oxidation and reduction temperatures is large. Consequently, to improve the *SPC* of HEX-based TSA, future research should aim to:

- Minimizing reduction enthalpy. This could be possibly achieved through chemical modification on the Mn-site of hexagonal RMnO_{3+δ} – it was shown in the literature (in the case of perovskite-type materials) that *the redox enthalpy is mainly governed by the transition metal species M, and can be fine-tuned by mixing different transition metals*, and even negative values of reduction reaction enthalpy are possible, therefore making the reduction to become exothermic [419].
- Minimizing the difference between *T_{OX}* and *T_{RED}*. It is already shown (both in this work and in the previous literature), that this gap is somehow influenced by the chemical composition of hexagonal RMnO_{3+δ}. Thus, further studies on variously substituted HEXs might allow finding a way of controlled adjustment of this temperature difference.

Table 10.1 Specific power consumption of HEX-based TSA O₂ separation from air. *SPC* values are estimated for selected state-of-the-art HEX OSMs.

Composition	Ref.	δ [-]	OSC [wt.%]	<i>T_{OX}</i> , <i>T_{RED}</i> [°C]	<i>T_{RED}</i> - <i>T_{OX}</i> [°C]	Specific power consumption [kWh to ₂ ⁻¹]		
						<i>C_{OSM}</i>	Δ <i>H_{REDOX}</i>	total
Y _{0.95} Pr _{0.05} MnO _{3+δ} (Pr005)	[1]	0.30	2.44	230, 256	26	184	955	1138
Y _{0.95} Nd _{0.05} MnO _{3+δ} (Nd005)	[3]	0.28	2.32	201, 240	39	290	955	1244
Y _{0.7} Tb _{0.3} MnO _{3+δ}	[4]	0.25	1.81	250, 325	75	714	955	1669
Y _{0.7} Ce _{0.15} Tb _{0.15} MnO _{3+δ}	[5]	~0.4	~3.1	193, 329	136	756	955	1710

Summary and conclusions

Mixed ionic-electronic conducting hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ were shown to be able to reversibly incorporate/release relatively large quantities of oxygen during the TSA process in oxygen-containing atmospheres. The reaction, which basically is a redox process, involves bulk diffusion of oxygen anions and changes in the oxidation state of Mn. The research performed and discussed in the *Results and discussion* section of this dissertation, allowed answering the questions posed in the *Aim of the work* chapter. In this part, the main achievements and drawn conclusions are summarized. Finally, the possible impact of this work on the research field and industry is briefly discussed at the end of this section.

Main achievements

- The first hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSM has been developed, able to work in the TSA process in an air atmosphere with efficiency close to the one previously obtained only in pure O_2 . This improvement of redox reactions between HEX and oxygen in a relatively low p_{O_2} atmosphere enables the possibility of application of HEX OSMs for O_2 production by air separation using TSA performed at exceptionally low temperatures of 200-300 °C.
- The correlations between the main operational parameters of hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials and the mean ionic radius value of cations occupying the $Y_{1-x}R_x$ sublattice have been discovered and described. This provides general guidelines on how to design the chemical composition of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSMs to make them operate (i.e. facilitate redox reactions between Mn and O) at the required oxidation/reduction temperatures and O_2 content in the atmosphere or to exhibit specific OSC (within certain limits).
- It has been discovered that if the value of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius is large enough, being close to the stability limit between hexagonal and perovskite-type polymorphs of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$, an efficient oxygen absorption in air atmosphere becomes possible.
- It has been shown that even a small substitution ($x \leq 0.05$) of Y with larger rare earth, R, can significantly improve the oxygen storage performance of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$. This is a crucial result, as Y is one of the most abundant rare earths, and one of the cheapest, consequently. Therefore, the lower amount of substitution is, the less expensive material can be.
- The influence of preparation conditions modification (and therefore morphology of the samples) on the oxygen storage performance of Nd-substituted $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ has been studied. Consequently, the correlation between average crystallite size and oxygen storage capacity, and oxygen absorption rate has been observed.
- The further improvement of oxygen storage characteristics has been achieved for the first time by simultaneous chemical (Nd-substitution) and microstructural (finer morphology obtained with lowering synthesis temperature). In the practical aspect, such improvement would allow obtaining higher O_2 production capacity in the TSA process, i.e. more O_2 could be separated from air, using less OSM, and within a shorter time.
- The world's first HEX-based TSA ASU for O_2 separation from air has been designed and constructed. The coarse estimation of possible specific power consumption of O_2 production

in the TSA process has been provided and its competitiveness in relation to the conventional methods has been assessed.

Detailed conclusions

Based on Chapter 6. Influence of the mean ionic radius of $Y_{1-x}R_x$ on $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ properties ($R = Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Yb$)

- Sol-gel autocombustion synthesis followed by high-temperature annealing in Ar was successfully applied to prepare materials from $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ (R : Yb, Gd, Sm, Nd, or Pr; x : 0, 0.05, 0.075, or 0.1) series. Final annealing at 900-1000 °C was sufficient for all compositions from Yb01 to Pr005 (besides Gd01) to be obtained in their hexagonal ($P6_3cm$), while 1050 °C was required for Gd01 to prevent the formation of the perovskite-type impurity ($Pbnm$). In the case of Pr0075 and Pr01, this secondary perovskite-type polymorph was also detected besides the hexagonal one but contrary to Gd01, increasing the final annealing temperature even up to 1400 °C did not allow to eliminate $Pbnm$ phase completely. These results suggest that the stability limit of the hexagonal phase was exceeded, and only less than $x = 0.075$ of Pr can be introduced in the Y sublattice to prevent the formation of perovskite-type polymorph. This limit can be expressed with regards to the maximum ionic radius of cations in rare earth sublattice, $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$. Therefore, this limit value of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ is somewhere between 1.024 Å and 1.027 Å (i.e. $r(Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05})$ and $r(Y_{0.925}Pr_{0.075})$).
- In the case of materials synthesized with nitrates as starting chemicals (i.e. all the compositions besides Nd005 and Sm005), traces of the Y_2O_3 -type impurity were detected (2-4 wt.%), resulting from high water affinity of Mn-nitrate and therefore, too low amount of Mn in the synthesis. This impurity did not significantly influence the further results. The synthesis route of Nd005 and Sm005 materials was refined – all nitrates were replaced with oxides as starting chemicals, which allowed to avoid impurities and obtain single-phased hexagonal compounds. In the case of Nd005 and Sm005, final annealing was done at 1000 °C.
- All synthesized samples exhibited similar fine-grained morphology, independent on the type and amount of substitution. SEM images exhibited submicrometer-sized secondary particles which tend to form porous aggregates, while TEM revealed the presence of nano-sized (< 100 nm) grains as well. SSA of the examined powders was in the range of 2.7-4.9 m² g⁻¹. The morphology of examined HEX materials does not visibly deteriorate during cyclic oxidation and reduction, according to SEM images. This might be thanks to low operation temperatures of HEX materials in the TSA process – typically in the 200-300 °C range, and with max temperature not exceeding 500 °C throughout the performed TG experiments.
- The ability to the effective operation of hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ OSM in air atmosphere was achieved by a partial substitution of Y with Pr: $Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$. In this case, OSC in air was increased to 2.44 wt.%, compared to 0.43 wt.% obtained for non-modified $YMnO_{3+\delta}$. OSC of Pr005 in air is 96% of its OSC reached in pure O₂. For comparison, the previously best-air-operating HEX OSM, $Y_{0.7}Tb_{0.3}MnO_{3+\delta}$, is able to reach in air only 57% of its

capacity in O₂ and contains a relatively large amount of Tb, which is far more expensive than Pr and Y.

- The type (*R*) and amount (*x*) of substitution, and therefore the size of ionic radius in Y sublattice, $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$, has an influence on the main properties of hexagonal $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$. The following parameters have been observed to be correlated with $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$:
 - 1) Larger $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ leads to the expansion of the unit cell volume of the $P6_3cm$ phase. This expansion occurs along the unit cell parameter *a*, while no simple trend is observed in changes of parameter *c*.
 - 2) The larger $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$, the better $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ absorbs oxygen, resulting in higher achievable OSC of material. This trend is observed in both studied atmospheres, pure O₂, and air. This improvement is restricted by the stability limit between hexagonal and perovskite-type polymorphs – there is a maximum $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ that cannot be exceeded. In the case of Pr-substituted material, Pr005, it was confirmed that praseodymium does not participate in the redox reactions occurring during oxygen absorption and release. Therefore, it confirms that the improvement of oxygen storage performance in Pr005 is achieved solely by the increase of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ radius.
 - 3) Increasing the size of $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$ is followed by the increase of temperatures where redox processes in $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ take place, i.e. temperatures of oxidation $T_{OX,eq}$ and reduction $T_{RED,eq}$. This trend is not as strong as the previous two, however, as a first approximation it can be applied as a rule of thumb, that if HEX OSM is required to work at higher temperatures, its chemical composition should be modified to increase $r(Y_{1-x}R_x)$. This correlation is observed in both examined atmospheres (O₂ and air) and is shifted toward lower temperatures in gas with lower *p*_{O₂}. The practical implication of this observation is that HEX might be possibly applied not only in TSA but in PSA as well.
- The oxidation of the examined $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials is accompanied by a phase transformation: Hex0 ($P6_3cm$) is mostly transformed to Hex1 ($R3c$), and the more oxygen is absorbed, the more weight fraction of Hex1 and the less of Hex0 is present in the material. This multi-phase composition of oxidized materials might be caused by kinetic limitations of the oxidation process and should be considered as a metastable state. In the case of materials that absorbed larger amounts of oxygen, where the presence of the Hex1 phase is dominant, it is difficult to unambiguously determine if the secondary phase is the remaining Hex0, or emerging highly-oxidized Hex2, due to the large similarity of Hex0 and Hex2 diffraction patterns. However, a comparison of XRD and TG results suggests that the secondary phase Hex2 is more probable.

Based on Chapter 7. *Extended studies on $Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$*

- Phase transformation taking place during oxidation/reduction of HEX materials is associated with relatively large structural rearrangements, resulting in significant anisotropic chemical

contraction/expansion. In the case of Pr005, upon oxidation process (Hex0→Hex1 transition) unit cell expands in direction a with $129 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ coefficient and contracts in c by $517 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which in total results in a contraction of unit cell volume with linearized coefficient of $84.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. This large expansion/contraction might be an issue in certain potential applications of $\text{YMnO}_{3+\delta}$ -based materials, like OPMs, SOFCs, etc., and thus it should be addressed in future research.

- As shown in the example of Pr005 material, oxidation (oxygen absorption) in the studied materials proceeds according to the contracting volume reaction model and as such, is a phase boundary-limited process. Therefore, the rate of oxidation reaction (and consequently, OSC of material) can be improved in two ways: (1) by increasing the mobility of oxygen ions in the structure of HEX, or (2) by improving the specific surface area of reacting material. The same reaction model could probably be suitable for the remaining HEX materials studied in this work, however, additional experiments are required to verify this assumption.
- According to the TG experiments of oxidation and reduction of Pr005 material performed at various temperatures, the following observations are made. The oxidation reaction proceeds much slower than the reduction. Thus, in the potential TSA implementation, the stage of oxygen absorption will be the one limiting the rate of oxygen separation (i.e. production capacity of air separation plant). The dependence of reduction rate on T_{RED} is simple – larger T_{RED} leads to faster release of oxygen. In the case of T_{OX} , there is some optimal value, where oxidation proceeds the fastest. This T_{OX} should be neither too high (to prevent thermodynamic limitation) nor too low (to prevent kinetic limitation). For Pr005 material, a T_{OX} of 220 °C turns out to be optimal. An intermediate temperature range was observed, where both reduction and oxidation are not facilitated, burdened with elevated activation energy. Therefore, selecting operating temperatures for the TSA process should be avoided in this range. The average E_a is $82.8 \pm 14.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for reduction (270-300 °C), and $15.3 \pm 5.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for oxidation (190-230 °C), while in the intermediate range (around 240-260 °C) it is $140.8 \pm 34.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $121.5 \pm 49.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for reduction and oxidation, respectively.
- TG experiments simulating the TSA process confirmed the applicability of Pr005 material for the separation of O_2 from air. According to these experiments, productivity was estimated – ca. 108 m^3 of O_2 could be separated from air daily, using 1 ton of Pr005 operating in 37 min-lasting cycles. During 20 cycles, the total capacity loss observed during the first 20 cycles of operation was 2.6% (average of 0.13% per cycle). The capacity loss gradually decreased upon cycling – further experiments showed the decrease of capacity by 2.4-4.8% from the 20th to 100th cycle (average 0.04-0.06% per cycle). Consequently, Pr005 seems to be a promising candidate for TSA air separation.
- The oxygen storage performance of Pr005 was examined in three different operation modes: TSA, PSA, and TPSA, to assess the possibility of further improvements in air separation process. TPSA moderately increased the amount of oxygen separated in a single cycle, while in the case of PSA, a marginal decrease was observed but the process required significantly longer reduction time (and cycle duration, consequently).

- The long-term cycling performance of Pr005 in TPSA mode was studied. In the beginning, Pr005 absorbed $\delta = 0.093$ of oxygen (0.77 wt.%) per one 37 min-lasting cycle. The gradual capacity loss occurred, comparable in magnitude to the one observed in the TSA experiment: an average capacity loss of 0.06% per cycle. In the end, δ was 0.080 (0.66 wt.%). The productivity of Pr005 in the TPSA air separation was calculated to be $208 \text{ m}^3 \text{ t}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ in the initial cycle, and $179 \text{ m}^3 \text{ t}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ in the last one, which outperforms the results obtained previously in TSA experiment.

Based on Chapter 8. Combined chemical and microstructural improvement:

- Chemical refinement of the oxygen storage behavior of Nd005 (reached by $x=0.05$ substitution with Nd in $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$) was combined with microstructural modification to evaluate the possibility of additional improvement. A proper decrease in annealing time and temperature allowed to a large increase in the oxidation/reduction rate. Despite the decreased amount of hexagonal (oxygen-storing) phase was observed in Nd005 synthesized at $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour, oxygen storage capacity and oxidation rate were the highest among all the samples – 1.05 wt.% (in $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ cycle) vs. 0.80 wt.% (for the basic Nd005, annealed at $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 hours) or even 0.20 wt.% (in Nd005 annealed at $1500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).
- It was shown that the amount of absorbed oxygen and oxidation rate correlates well with the inverse of average crystallite size derived from XRD analysis – the smaller crystallites are, the more oxygen can be absorbed and the faster oxidation proceeds.

Based on Chapter 9. Oxygen transport properties

- Transport properties of pure $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ and substituted Nd005 and Pr005 were studied. In all three materials, the presence of O_2 in the atmosphere led to a large increase in conductivity. This increase is caused by oxygen absorption, which introduces additional charge carriers – interstitial oxygen ions and electronic holes localized on Mn^{4+} . Even a marginal amount of oxygen nonstoichiometry has a significant impact – for example, δ of less than 0.003 in the case of $YMnO_{3+\delta}$, increased the conductivity by ca. two orders of magnitude from $4.16 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ to $3.42 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The introduction of a larger amount of oxygen gives a further increase in conductivity but not as prominent as at the beginning of oxidation.
- The conductivity behavior stands out in the intermediate temperature range for all samples in O_2 -containing atmospheres. In this range, conductivity does not change significantly with temperature, and activation energy is largely decreased – even down to 0.05-0.15 eV in the case of Pr005. This behavior is explained by the simultaneous decrease in the mobility of charge carriers and the increase in their concentration.
- In the case of O_2 -rich gases, air, and O_2 , the thermoelectric power of Pr005 remains positive in the whole range of studied temperatures. A positive sign of the Seebeck coefficient confirms that the electronic holes related to Mn^{4+} are dominating charge carriers, making

Pr005 a p-type conductor. At high temperatures (above 510 °C) in Ar, the Seebeck coefficient becomes negative, changing the conductivity character of Pr005 from p-type to n-type. This is explained either by the presence of oxygen vacancies compensated by the partial reduction of Mn^{3+} to Mn^{2+} (effectively acting as electrons) or by the charge disproportionation of Mn^{3+} to Mn^{4+} and Mn^{2+} (electrons corresponding to Mn^{2+} would be dominating carriers due to larger mobility than electronic holes associated with Mn^{4+}).

- SEM images taken for pellets after high-temperature conductivity measurements revealed numerous cracks on the surface of the pellets. This observation confirms the possibility of thermomechanical stability issues suggested previously by a large chemical expansion observed in HT-XRD experiments.
- Preliminary experiments were done to determine Pr005 applicability as an air-electrode for SOFC. Pr005 exhibited improved electrode polarization resistance at low temperatures of ~400 °C, as compared to literature data for $\text{NdBaCo}_{1.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ electrode material. The obtained results suggest that further research focused on the application of hexagonal $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ mixed ionic-electronic conductors as SOFC air-electrodes might be of interest.

Based on Chapter 10. *HEX-based TSA: Assessment of applicability for O_2 separation from air*

- A prototype of a small-scale air separation unit has been designed and constructed. This ASU is dedicated to operating in TSA mode and utilizing HEX OSMs developed in this work, able to efficiently absorb oxygen from air. To date, this is the first reported proof of concept of HEX-based TSA ASU.
- The coarse estimation of possible specific power consumption of O_2 production in the TSA process utilizing HEX OSMs has been provided and its competitiveness in relation to the conventional methods has been assessed. For the current state-of-the-art HEX OSMs, specific power consumption is estimated to be around 1140 kWh t^{-1} . For comparison, the typical *SPC* of cryogenic distillation of air is in the range of $400\text{-}800 \text{ kWh t}^{-1}$ (~200 kWh t^{-1} for the modern large-scale cryogenic plants), which means that for the TSA to become competitive with conventional O_2 production methods, *SPC* needs to be further decreased. However, this relatively low *SPC* of the cryogenic process comes from many decades of development. Therefore, further improvement of TSA technology could make it a competitive oxygen production method. Indeed, the *SPC* of TSA estimated in this work does not include any eventual heat recovery during the process, so it can be further improved by a proper design of ASU.
- It was found, that the power consumption in HEX-based TSA is mainly dictated by the oxygen release (i.e. enthalpy of endothermic reduction reaction). Therefore, the next possible direction of research on $\text{RMnO}_{3+\delta}$ materials is to focus on finding a way to minimize this reduction enthalpy.

The anticipated impact on the research field and industry

The research presented in this work can be of interest to a wide community from multiple fields – materials science, power engineering, and medical science, to name a few. Many researchers working on oxygen storage materials, mixed ionic-electronic conductors, materials involving Mn-related redox processes, or alternative oxygen production methods, could find this dissertation interesting. These studies have made an important contribution to improving insight into the properties of the $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ family of materials. The characterized correlations between properties of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ and their composition provide the basis for designing them in the way allowing their application for example for O_2 production for the power generation processes while utilizing the waste heat of these processes.

As this work is strongly related to the topic of O_2 production methods, it has also an indirect impact on all the sectors of science and industry that are inherently connected with the use of O_2 , including medicine, glass industry, steelmaking, chemical industry, or petrochemistry. The development of the TSA unit prototype designed in this work may be a step closer to its implementation in many industries. This device can be used as an additional system in conventional power plants – a waste heat of combustion could be utilized to power the TSA process and enrich the combustion air with O_2 , possibly improving the net power conversion efficiency of the plant. Moreover, such O_2 -enriched combustion could reduce (or even eliminate) the presence of nitrogen oxides in exhaust gases, thus significantly simplifying the CO_2 capture and reducing the environmental footprint. Equally important, such a device could also be used as a stand-alone installation and used to produce oxygen in hospitals, which would make it possible to become independent of external O_2 supplies.

Relatively low T_{OX} and T_{RED} of $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ reduce the risk of chemical degradation of OSM if operating in harsh environment (like gases containing H_2 , H_2O , CO_2 , CO , etc.), so $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ could be applied for oxygen capture from those gases (either if such gas is a product and has to be purified out of O_2 , or such gas is a waste but O_2 can be recovered, or combination of both purposes). Also, $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ able to work in atmospheres with lower O_2 content could be utilized as an oxygen buffer, e.g. in three-way catalytic converters.

The results obtained in this work may also affect the development of electronics and metrology – the observed large changes in the conductivity of $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$ materials under the influence of changes in temperature and O_2 content in the atmosphere, make it possible to use them in gas or temperature sensors, or memory devices.

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Appendix A Measurement errors calculations

Mean size of crystallites, τ (Scherrer equation)

$$\tau = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (\text{Equation A1})$$

Error propagation of τ :

$$w(\tau) \approx \sqrt{w^2(\beta) + w^2(\cos \theta)} \quad (\text{Equation A1.1})$$

where:

$$w(\beta) = 100 \frac{u(\beta)}{\beta} \quad (\text{Equation A1.2})$$

$u(\beta)$ – value of standard deviation of β (from Rietveld refinements of XRD data) was taken

$$w(\cos \theta) = 100 \frac{u(\cos \theta)}{\cos \theta} \quad (\text{Equation A1.3})$$

$$u(\cos \theta) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{d \cos \theta}{d\theta} u(\theta)\right)^2} = \sin \theta u(\theta) \quad (\text{Equation A1.4})$$

$$u(\theta) = 0.005 \text{ deg}$$

$w(\lambda)$ was neglected in Equation S8.1 as it is several orders of magnitude smaller than $w(\beta)$ and $w(\cos \theta)$

Thermal expansion coefficient

$$\text{TEC} = \frac{1}{L} \frac{\Delta L}{\Delta T}$$

Error of TEC:

$u(\text{TEC})$ – taken as an error of data refinement with a linear function

Oxygen content, δ in $Y_{1-x}R_x\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ (R : Nd, Sm)

$$\delta = \frac{n_O}{n_{\text{HEX,RED}}} = \frac{\Delta m M_{\text{HEX,RED}}}{M_O m_{\text{RED}}} = \frac{(m - m_{\text{RED}}) M_{\text{HEX,RED}}}{M_O m_{\text{RED}}} [-] \quad (\text{Equation A2})$$

Error propagation of the oxygen content, δ :

$$u(\delta) = \frac{w(\delta)}{100} \delta = \frac{\sqrt{w^2(\Delta m) + w^2(M_{\text{HEX,RED}}) + w^2(M_O) + w^2(m_{\text{RED}})}}{100} \delta = \frac{\sqrt{\left(100 \frac{u(\Delta m)}{\Delta m}\right)^2 + w^2(M_{\text{HEX,RED}}) + w^2(M_O) + w^2(m_{\text{RED}})}}{100} \delta \quad (\text{Equation A2.3})$$

where:

$$u(\Delta m) = 0.01 \mu\text{g}$$

$$u(M_{\text{HEX,RED}}) = 0.005 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$$

$$u(M_O) = 0.0005 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$$

$$w(m_{\text{RED}}) = 0.1 \%$$

$$w(M_{\text{HEX,RED}}) = 0.0026 \%$$

$$w(M_O) = 0.0031 \%$$

Oxygen storage capacity, OSC (expressed in wt.%)

$$OSC = 100 \frac{\Delta m}{m_{RED}} [\text{wt. \%}] \quad (\text{Equation A3})$$

Error propagation of the oxygen storage capacity, OSC:

$$u(OSC) = \frac{w(OSC)[\%]}{100} OSC [\text{wt. \%}] \quad (\text{Equation A3.1})$$

where:

$$w(OSC) = \sqrt{w^2(\Delta m) + w^2(m_{RED})} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u(\Delta m)}{\Delta m} 100\right)^2 + w^2(m_{RED})} [\%] \quad (\text{Equation A3.2})$$

$$u(\Delta m) = 0.01 \mu\text{g}$$

$$w(m_{RED}) = 0.1 \%$$

Oxygen storage capacity, OSC_{μmol} (expressed in μmol-O g⁻¹)

$$OSC_{\mu\text{mol}} = \frac{OSC}{100} \frac{1000000}{M_O} = 10000 \frac{OSC}{M_O} \left[\frac{\mu\text{mol-O}}{\text{g}} \right] \quad (\text{Equation A4})$$

Error propagation of the oxygen storage capacity, OSC_{μmol}:

$$u(OSC_{\mu\text{mol}}) = \frac{w(OSC_{\mu\text{mol}})}{100} OSC_{\mu\text{mol}} = \frac{\sqrt{w^2(OSC) + w^2(M_O)}}{100} OSC_{\mu\text{mol}} \left[\frac{\mu\text{mol-O}}{\text{g}} \right] \quad (\text{Equation A4.1})$$

where:

$$w(OSC) \text{ – as in Equation S2.2}$$

$$w(M_O) = 0.0031 \%$$

Oxygen content related to the amount of, the active phase Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+δ}, δ_{HEX} (in Nd005 materials contaminated with other oxides)

$$\delta_{HEX} = \delta \frac{100}{c_{m,HEX}} [-] \quad (\text{Equation A5})$$

where:

Uncertainty propagation of the oxygen content, δ_{HEX}:

$$u(\delta_{HEX}) = \frac{w(\delta_{HEX})}{100} (\delta_{HEX}) = \frac{\sqrt{w^2(\delta) + w^2(c_{m,HEX})}}{100} (\delta_{HEX}) [-]$$

where:

$$w(c_{m,HEX}) = 100 \frac{u(c_{m,HEX})}{c_{m,HEX}} [\%]$$

$$u(c_{m,HEX}) = 0.1 \text{ wt. \%}$$

Temperature of oxidation, T_{OX,eq}, (determined from the cooling step during 0.1 °C min⁻¹ cycle of the temperature swing)

$$\left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial T}\right)_{0.1\text{C/min cooling}} = \text{max} \Rightarrow T = T_{OX,eq} \quad (\text{Equation A6})$$

$$u(T_{OX,eq}) = 1 \text{ °C}$$

Temperature of reduction, $T_{RED,eq}$, (determined from the heating step during $0.1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ cycle of the temperature swing)

$$\left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial T}\right)_{0.1\text{C/min heating}} = \min \Rightarrow T = T_{RED,eq} \quad (\text{Equation A7})$$

$$u(T_{RED,eq}) = 1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

Oxidation rate, $d(\delta)/dt$

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = \frac{\Delta\delta}{\Delta t} = \frac{\delta_2 - \delta_1}{t_2 - t_1} = \frac{\frac{(m_2 - m_{RED}) M_{HEX,RED}}{M_O m_{RED}} - \frac{(m_1 - m_{RED}) M_{HEX,RED}}{M_O m_{RED}}}{t_2 - t_1} = \frac{\Delta m M_{HEX,RED}}{M_O m_{RED} (t_2 - t_1)} [\text{min}^{-1}] \quad (\text{Equation A8})$$

Error propagation of the oxidation rate, $d(\delta)/dt$:

$$u\left(\frac{d\delta}{dt}\right) = \frac{w\left(\frac{d\delta}{dt}\right)}{100} \frac{d\delta}{dt} [\text{min}^{-1}] \quad (\text{Equation A8.1})$$

where:

$$w\left(\frac{d\delta}{dt}\right) = \sqrt{w^2(\Delta m) + w^2(M_{HEX,RED}) + w^2(M_O) + w^2(m_{RED}) + w^2(\Delta t)} \quad (\text{Equation A8.2})$$

$$w(\Delta m) = 100 \frac{u(\Delta m)}{\Delta m} = 100 \frac{\sqrt{u^2(m_1) + u^2(m_2)}}{\Delta m} = 100 \frac{u(m)\sqrt{2}}{\Delta m} \quad (\text{Equation A8.3})$$

$$u(m) = 0.01 \text{ } \mu\text{g}$$

$$w(M_{HEX,RED}) = 0.0026 \%$$

$$w(M_O) = 0.0031 \%$$

$$w(m_{RED}) = 0.1 \%$$

$$w(\Delta t) = 100 \frac{u(\Delta t)}{\Delta t} = 100 \frac{\sqrt{u^2(t_1) + u^2(t_2)}}{\Delta t} = 100 \frac{u(t)\sqrt{2}}{\Delta t} \quad (\text{Equation A8.4})$$

$$u(t) = 0.05 \text{ s}$$

Appendix B Pr005 as a SOFC electrode material

Preliminary research was performed to assess the applicability of hexagonal rare earth manganites, $Y_{1-x}R_xMnO_{3+\delta}$, as an air electrode in solid oxide fuel cells. For these experiments, $Y_{0.95}Pr_{0.05}MnO_{3+\delta}$ (Pr005) composition was chosen, as it exhibited improved conductivity in air atmosphere, compared to parent $YMnO_{3+\delta}$, and the fastest oxygen exchange characteristics among all materials studied in this work and discussed in chapter 6.

Firstly, the thermochemical stability of Pr005 in contact with commercial oxygen-conducting electrolytes was investigated. Two commonly used compounds were selected for these tests: $La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Ga_{0.8}Mg_{0.2}O_{3-\delta}$ (LSGM) and $Ce_{0.9}Gd_{0.1}O_{1.95}$ (GDC). Pr005 and electrolyte powders were mixed in a 1:1 weight proportion using agate mortar. Samples of each mixture were annealed in air at 800 °C for 100 hours and at 1000 °C for 10 hours. To verify possible reactivity between Pr005 and LSGM or GDC, XRD analysis was applied [2].

Results of the XRD measurements prove good stability of Pr005 in contact with both electrolytes, LSGM and GDC, in high-temperature air conditions (**Figure B.1**). No additional reflections were observed – recorded diffractograms are composed of diffraction patterns of Pr005 and respective electrolyte only. Therefore, in terms of thermochemical stability, Pr005 is suitable for application in SOFC as an air electrode.

Figure B.1 X-ray diffractograms recorded before and after the thermochemical stability tests of Pr005 mixed with (a) LSGM and (b) GDC solid electrolytes [2]. Diffractograms of pure Pr005, LSGM, and GDC are given for reference.

Next, the electrode polarization resistance was determined using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The Pr005|LSGM|Pr005 symmetrical electrolyte-supported cell was prepared for this experiment. LSGM electrolyte powder was uniaxially pressed (ca. 100 MPa) and sintered at 1450 °C for 8 hours to obtain a dense gas-tight pellet. The dimensions of the sintered pellet were 10.3 mm (diameter) by 1.5 mm (thickness). Electrodes of approx. 6 mm diameter were screen-printed on both sides of the electrolyte, two layers on each side. Electrode paste used for screen-printing was prepared by mixing fine Pr005 powder with organic binder and starch in a weight proportion of 1.5:2:0.05. Starch was used as a pore-forming agent. The such prepared cell was annealed at 1100 °C for 4 hours in air. For the measurement of polarization resistance with EIS, the cell was installed in the Probostat sample holder, and the Solartron 1252A frequency response analyzer was used to record the data. Impedance was

measured in air atmosphere on cooling, starting from 900 °C, with data collected in the 0.1 Hz – 300 kHz frequency range [2].

Figure B.2 Selected impedance spectra of Pr005[LSGM]Pr005 symmetrical cell in air at (a) 900 °C, (b) 440 °C, and (c) 287 °C [2].

Selected impedance spectra obtained for Pr005|LSGM|Pr005 cell at different temperatures are shown in **Figure B.2** in form of Nyquist plots. The shape of impedance characteristics evolves with the temperature change. At the highest temperatures (**Figure B.2a**), a single depressed semicircle is observed, shifted from the origin of the Z_{RE} axis, and with some inductance component visible at the highest frequencies (above 30 kHz). These high-temperature spectra are well fitted with the equivalent circuit of resistive component (R1, corresponding to the shift in Z_{RE} axis) in series with inductance (L1) and combined resistance with constant phase element (R2 and CPE2 in parallel). In the intermediate-temperature range (**Figure B.2b**), R2||CPE2 semicircle becomes only partially observable, cut off in the lower frequency range, where the data was not recorded (below 100 mHz), inductance L1 is virtually not seen anymore, the magnitude of R1 shift is increased, and additional semicircle (R2a||CPE2a) emerges in the high-frequency range, located between R1 shift and R2||CPE2 semicircle. At low temperatures (**Figure B.2c**), the newly formed R2a||CPE2a starts to dominate the impedance spectra in the recorded frequency range, and it was not possible to reliably fit the parameters of R2||CPE2 semicircle anymore. ZView (SAI) software was used to refine the numerical values of the components chosen for equivalent circuits. Values of R1, R2, and R2a resistive components were converted to ASR (*area-specific resistance*, i.e. resistance multiplied by cross-section area) and plotted as a function of temperature in the Arrhenius-type plot (**Figure B.3**).

Figure B.3 Resistive components of the refined equivalent circuits of Pr005|LSGM|Pr005 cell (R1, R2, and R2a) expressed as area-specific resistance (ASR) and plotted as a function of temperature.

R1 seems to come from the ohmic resistance of the electrolyte – in the high-temperature range, conductivity calculated using values of R1 and dimensions of the electrolyte pellet (e.g. 0.097 S cm^{-1} at 800 °C) corresponds well to the conductivity reported for LSGM in the literature ($\sim 0.1 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 800 °C) [420]. Unfortunately, no conductivity data was found in the literature for LSGM in the low-temperature range, and in the here recorded data, R1 deviates

from its original trend, becoming almost temperature-independent. As the intercept at high frequencies is not recorded at low temperatures (**Figure B.2c**) in the studied frequency range, that temperature-independent behavior might be an artifact resulting from refinement or inaccuracy of measurement at the highest frequencies.

While the R1 component has been assigned to the LSGM electrolyte, the remaining R2 and R2a possibly correspond together to the polarization of Pr005 electrodes and Pr005|LSGM interfaces. As the examined cell was symmetrical (Pr005|LSGM|Pr005), the polarization resistance of a single Pr005 was obtained by dividing the sum of R2 and R2a by two.

The inverse of the ASR of the Pr005 electrode is plotted in Arrhenius coordinates (**Figure B.4a**) together with conductivity recorded previously for the Pr005 sample in air (**Figure 9.3**). The shape of $\log(\text{ASR}^{-1})$ characteristic of electrode polarization is similar to the conductivity behavior of pure Pr005: in the high-temperature range the slope (and thus, activation energy) is the highest, in the intermediate-temperature range (where interstitial oxygen is absorbed and electronic holes are introduced) slope is the lowest, and at lower temperatures, the slope is again increased but is not as steep as at high temperatures. The most prominent difference is that the $\log(\text{ASR}^{-1})$ data is shifted toward higher temperatures, compared to the $\log(\delta)$ characteristics of Pr005.

Figure B.4 (a) Temperature dependence of ASR^{-1} of Pr005 electrode in Pr005|LSGM|Pr005 cell compared to the conductivity previously recorded for the Pr005 material itself. (b) ASR of Pr005 electrode compared with the ASR of $\text{NdBaCo}_{1.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ electrode reported in [421].

In **Figure B.4b**, the ASR of the Pr005 electrode is compared to the literature data reported for other SOFC electrode material, $\text{NdBaCo}_{1.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{O}_{5+\delta}$, prepared at two different temperatures (1050 °C and 1100 °C) [421]. Despite the ASR of Pr005 being generally worse than the one of $\text{NdBaCo}_{1.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{O}_{5+\delta}$, it needs to be emphasized that the polarization resistance of an electrode is strongly influenced by the preparation conditions – a large difference can be observed even when the temperature of electrode preparation is changed from 1050 °C to 1100 °C. Therefore, it is credible that with a proper modification of Pr005 electrode preparation, its ASR might be further improved (i.e. decreased) and possibly even surpass the performance of $\text{NdBaCo}_{1.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{O}_{5+\delta}$. This might be especially achievable at lower temperatures, where the gap between those two materials is not very large. Thus, Pr005 (or even the whole family of

hexagonal $RMnO_{3+\delta}$ oxides) could be of interest in the development of low-temperature SOFCs and further research on this topic is worth to be considered. Indeed, reports regarding the application of Zr-doped and pure $YMnO_{3+\delta}$ as SOFC electrodes started to appear in recent years, showing promising results [422].